

Engineering Design Report

LHC External Beam Dumps (TDE) Modifications and upgrades during LS2 for Run3

ABSTRACT:

This document describes the work carried out during Long Shutdown 2 of the LHC to upgrade the LHC beam dump blocks (TDEs) to cope with the operating conditions of LHC Run 3. Operational problems encountered during Run 2 are explained along with the findings from the different investigations to understand the thermo-mechanical behaviour of the dump blocks in response to dumping of LHC beams. The resulting set of modifications to the dump blocks, beam windows, dump block supports, and infrastructure undertaken during LS2 are described along with supporting analysis. Information is provided on new instrumentation installed to monitor the behaviour of the dumps during Run 3.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

This document describes the work carried out during Long Shutdown 2 (LS2) of the LHC to upgrade the LHC beam dump blocks (TDEs) to cope with the operating conditions of LHC Run 3.

The introduction explains the design of the TDE and its integration underground before LS2. The operational problems that led to the modifications covered in this document are described along with the interventions carried out before LS2 in response to the problems.

1.2 TDE DESIGN

1.2.1 Requirements

The dump block (TDE) is part of the LHC Beam Dumping System (LBDS). The LBDS is described in Section 1.2.3.

The TDE has to repeatedly absorb the energy of the dumped beam without being damaged - including in the event of defined failures of the dilution elements of the LBDS. The evolution of dumped energy over the runs of the LHC is given in Table 1 (see [1])

Table 1 - TDE beam dumps per year and energy per beam.

	Run 2 2015-2018	Run 3 2021-2024	HL-LHC 2028 onwards
Beam dumps / year	220 days x 2 = ~ 400		
Energy per beam	~319MJ	555MJ	709MJ

1.2.2 Position

The LHC beam dumps are located in purpose-built caverns at each side of point 6 of the LHC. The dumped beam travels along 600 m long tunnels from the LHC main ring to the beam dumps. The dump blocks are installed inside shielded enclosures built up from old magnets that were used in CERN's ISR (intersecting storage ring) accelerator. The layout is shown in Figure 1 to Figure 3.

Figure 1 - Schematic layout of underground works at LHC point 6. The beam dumps are in caverns UD62 and UD68

Figure 2 - Scale layout of underground works at LHC point 6. The beam dumps are in caverns UD62 and UD68

Figure 3 - Isometric section view of beam dump cavern. The beam dump block (in beige) is inside shielding blocks (in green). The shielding blocks above dump block are removed / transparent in the image. The vacuum pipe leading from the LHC main ring can be seen on the left of the figure.

1.2.3 Dump block structure

The dump block has the following characteristics:

- 8.5 m long, $\varnothing 720$ mm diameter, 6200 kg cylinder.
- Duplex stainless steel (318L, Uranus 45) vessel, 12 mm thick walls, filled with two types of graphite:
 - High density (SIGRAFINE®) blocks (1.73 g/cm^3)
 - Low density (SIGRAFLEX®) graphite sheets. ($1.1 - 1.2 \text{ g/cm}^3$)
- The high-density blocks are shrink-fitted into the stainless-steel vessel sections
- The Sigraflex sheets are loose fitting in the vessel.
- Vessel sections with the two types of graphite are welded together

See Figure 4 for the layout, Figure 5 for an overview of the dump and Figure 6 for the Sigraflex sheets. Summary of relevant drawings can be found in Table 2.

Figure 4 - Schematic section of the TDE dump block showing the regions of high density and low-density graphite.

Figure 5 - Photo of both TDE dump blocks in their lifting frames placed in the UX-65 previous to the LS2-upgrade.

Figure 6 - Photo of SIGRAFLEX® sheets before assembly into the TDE.

1.2.4 TDE integration in beam dump caverns (Before LS2)

The TDE integration in the UD68 cavern before LS2 is shown in Figure 7. UD62 is a mirror image.

The dump is inside a shielded enclosure and was rigidly connected to the vacuum beam pipe coming from the LHC main ring by means of a "connecting line". The dump block and connecting line were filled with nitrogen in order to prevent oxidation of the graphite at the high temperatures produced by the beam impact on the dump. The vacuum in the

beam pipe was isolated from the nitrogen in the connecting line and TDE by means of a UHV beam window Made of CfC and a stainless steel foil (LHCVDWB_0011).

Figure 7 - Integration of the TDE in the beam dump caverns before LS2. (UD 62 shown)

1.2.5 TDE and Connecting line (before LS2)

The TDE was connected to the beam line coming from the LHC main ring by a connecting line of approximately 10 m long (see Figure 7 and Figure 8). The connecting line and dump were nitrogen filled.

The beam dump block was connected to the beam line because it was originally intended to operate with the dump under vacuum. At some point (quite late on in the LHC design and build project) concerns about air getting into the dump and leading to a fire or oxidation of the graphite led to decision to change from vacuum to nitrogen at a slight over-pressure (0.2 bar) [2].

It was not anticipated at the time that dumping of the beam would lead to severe vibrations. Note that no problems were observed until late 2015, consistent with an increase of intensity of the machine. This is logic since, as exposed in section 5, the amplitude and violence of such vibrations is proportional to the impacted intensity.

Figure 8 - Isometric view of the connecting line and dump block.

1.2.6 Beam windows and connections (before LS2)

Before LS2 there were two beam windows in the UD caverns:

- The UHV window which separated the vacuum portion of the beam line from the nitrogen-filled connecting line and dump block.
- The dump downstream window which closed the downstream end of the dump block.

Figure 9 shows the positions of the UHV-window, the dump-downstream window and the connection between TDE block and connecting line before LS2. Chain clamps combined with helicoflex[®] metallic gaskets were used to seal the flanges and mechanically connect the components.

Figure 9 - TDE Beam windows and connections before LS2.

1.2.7 Bellows and supports (before LS2)

Figure 10 shows the bellows in the connecting line and the supports for the connecting line and dump blocks before LS2. The end bellows on the connecting line were equipped with screw jacks to compress the bellows when needed for initial installation or for maintenance interventions such as gasket exchange.

Figure 10 - TDE bellows and supports before LS2.

Before LS2 the dump sat on two supports inside the shielding. In the pre-LS2 design the dump was not located longitudinally by the supports; the only resistance to longitudinal movement of the dump provided by the supports was due to the metal-on-metal friction between the supports and the dump vessel. Figure 11 shows the pre-LS2 dump supports.

Figure 11 - Photo of Pre-LS2 TDE supports inside shielding. Note ventilation pipes alongside the supports.

1.2.8 Chain clamps and gaskets (before LS2)

Chain clamps and Helicoflex metallic gaskets were used to seal flanges on the TDE, connecting line and the UHV window. The chain clamps have 12 segments, tightened using 4 nuts (250 Nm nominal tightening torque). The chain clamps were mounted on a backing plate which supported the chain clamp and allowed the chain to be opened to allow disconnection / reconnection for maintenance (see Figure 12).

Figure 12 - Pre-LS2 TDE connection to the connection line using chain clamp. Note the end of the screw jack used to compress the bellows via "ears" bolted to the end of the connection line.

Figure 13 - Partial section through TDE connection to the connection line using chain clamp.

1.3 LIFTING AND HANDLING OF THE DUMP

The design of the TDE allows for it to be exchanged once it has become radioactive. The dump block is therefore equipped with a lifting frame which can be picked by a spreader beam suspended from an overhead travelling crane without the need for any manual intervention. This is achieved by the use of four "mushroom" lifting attachments on the lifting frame that are picked up by the spreader beam (see Figure 14 and Figure 15).

Figure 14 - Installation of the dump block inside the shielding using the UD cavern overhead travelling crane and the dump block spreader beam.

Figure 15 - Close up of interface between the lifting frame and the spreader beam Four "mushrooms" on the corners of the lifting frame are engaged in "forks" on the corners of the spreader beam. Once the spreader beam is lifted, the mushrooms are trapped inside the forks and cannot slide out.

In order to transfer the dump block to the UD cavern from the surface it is necessary to travel along the LHC tunnel on a purpose-built trailer and then transfer over the LHC machine cryomagnets and cryoline and also the UHV tube from the LHC ring to the UD cavern. The UJ caverns are equipped with two hoists running on I-section beams to carry out this transfer. A second purpose-built trailer is used for the transport from the UJ to the UD (see Figure 16 and Figure 17).

Figure 16 - Cross section view of UJ cavern at point 6 showing the overhead hoists on I beams passing over the LHC machine and crinoline and also the (higher) vacuum tube going to the UD cavern.

Figure 17 - Photo of UJ68 during transport of a dump block. The dump block is on a purpose-built trailer in the LHC machine transport passage. The dump spreader beam is suspended from the hoists. The trailer for the transport between the UJ and the UD cavern can be seen on the right of the picture.

1.4 OPERATIONAL PROBLEMS DURING LHC RUN 2 AND INTERVENTIONS

1.4.1 Problems

During LHC operation in 2015 nitrogen started to leak out of the connection line and dump block. Interventions during the course of Run 2 (both in Technical Stops and Year-End Technical Stops) revealed the following things:

- Leaks at all the helicoflex® gasket connections apart from the upstream side of the UHV window. (see Figure 18 for downstream window)
- When the connections at the upstream ends of the dumps were opened it was found that the helicoflex® gaskets had been damaged.
- The nuts on the chain clamps had become loose (note that it was difficult to tighten all the nuts on the chain clamp at the upstream end of the dump as access to the lower nut was hindered by the position of the ventilation ducts that run under the dump blocks).
- The fasteners securing the ears that the screw jacks pull on to compress the bellows had become loose.
- The nuts on the threaded rods used to temporarily stabilise the central bellows of the connection line during vacuum pumping operations were found to be tight – despite having been loosened a few turns before the start of operation. This indicates that the central bellows had lengthened during operation of the LHC as a result of movement of the dump on its supports.
- Graphite powder was found inside the nitrogen sectors of both dumps.
- Water (approximately 0.5 litres) was found in the nitrogen side of the UHV window in UD68. This is thought to be a one-off occurrence.

Figure 18 - The dump downstream window. This was only accessible during the extended end of year technical stop after the shielding above the DS window has been removed. The dose rate was around 3 mSv/h near the gasket (20 mSv/h at contact so it was not feasible to change the gasket in situ.

1.4.2 Summary of interventions during Run2

Several interventions were made on both dumps during Run2 (2015 – 2018). The cumulative dose to personnel during these interventions was ~3 mSv. The interventions included:

- Leak detection ;
- Tightening of loosened fasteners and adding lock screws to the chain clamp nuts
- Replacement of damaged helicoflex gaskets;
- Installation and maintenance of interferometers to measure displacements of the dumps;
- Modifications to nitrogen supply system to increase stored nitrogen capacity in response to leaks and to move the supply on the surface rather than in the TD zone;

1.4.3 Leak detection interventions

Several separate interventions were made to carry out leak detection using manual methods and also using a twin arm robot suspended from the cavern crane for the measurements made on the dump downstream window (see Figure 19 to Figure 21).

Figure 19 - Manual leak detection on the dump downstream window.

Figure 20 - Remote leak detection on the dump downstream window using a robot suspended from the UD cavern crane.

Figure 21- The twin arm robot suspended from the UD cavern crane used for remote leak detection on the dump downstream window.

1.4.3.1 Modifications to N₂ supply system to increase capacity

The capacity of the nitrogen supply system was gradually increased during Run 2 in response to leaks. Until 2015 one gas bottle installed in the TD tunnel was sufficient. From mid-2016 this was increased to a rack of six bottles in the TD tunnel. Finally a piped nitrogen supply from the surface was installed for use from February 2018. See Figure 22 and Figure 23

Figure 22 - Rack of six nitrogen bottles installed in the TD tunnels in mid-2016.

Figure 23 - Layout of the piped nitrogen supply installed for use from February 2018 for UD62 (symmetric for UD68).

1.5 SUMMARY OF INSTRUMENTATION INSTALLATION AND MEASUREMENTS DURING RUN 2

1.5.1 Instrumentation installation

Interferometers were installed on the dumps in order to measure accelerations and movements during Run 2. The interferometers were installed on fixed supports at each end of the connecting line (see Figure 24). The interferometers measured the movements the dump and connecting line by means of mirrors attached at the dump end and at the vacuum window end of the connecting line.

Figure 24 - Interferometer installation in UD 68. Interferometers were installed on supports bolted to the floor at both ends of the connecting line.

The interferometer mirrors were clamped onto the "ears" bolted to the end flanges of the connecting line (see Figure 25). These ears are part of the bellows compression arrangements; manually operated screw jacks attached to the connecting line compress the bellows to provide clearance during initial installation of the connecting line and during beam window seal replacement etc.

Figure 25 - Detail of interferometer installation. The interferometer mirrors were clamped on the "ears" for the bellows compression jacks – not directly to the dump or the connecting line. The left-hand image shows the clamping arrangement. The right-hand image shows the "ears" and screw jacks used to compress the connecting line bellows (before the installation of the interferometer).

When investigating loss of signal from the interferometers it was found that one of the mirrors had broken and also that other mirrors had become misaligned due to movement of the dump (see Figure 26).

Figure 26 - Movement of the dump. The mirrors installed on the dump/connecting line moved relative to the fixed interferometers. The left-hand image illustrates the longitudinal movement of the dump and the right-hand image illustrates the rotation of the dump.

1.5.2 Instrumentation measurements - summary

The measurements showed a combination of two types of movement:

- Fast vibrations
- Slow displacements of the dump

These are illustrated in the Figure 27 and Figure 28 - more details are given in Section 9.

Figure 27 - Fast vibration measurements of the movement of the dump, with X-axis showing time and Y-axis showing displacement. The total timescale shown is 0.2 seconds. The maximum oscillation is -1.8, +0.8mm. The blue trace is longitudinal movements, the green and red traces are horizontal and vertical movements.

Figure 28 - Slow displacements of the dump. The timescale shown is 8 days. The total displacement over the 8 days is around 7 mm. The circled portion indicates thermal expansion over approximately 30 minutes followed by a cool down period of over 10 hours. The thermal cycling leads to permanent displacement of the dump on its supports.

1.6 KEY SIMULATION FINDINGS IN 2019 – EXPLAINING THE MOVEMENTS OF THE DUMP

Extensive simulation work was carried out in 2019 in parallel with conceptual design work to try to find a way of constraining the dumps. The simulation work, combining FLUKA and thermo-mechanical analysis, is reported in detail in sections 4 and 5, but the key finding was that the movement of the dump can be explained by the rapid thermal expansion of the stainless steel dump core vessel due to the energy deposition of the particle “shower” generated by the primary beam dump on the graphite core.

The simulation results gave a much clearer understanding of the behaviour of the dump and the accelerations and forces involved. This in turn led to a decision to not try to constrain the dumps but to allow them to expand and contract freely whilst finding a way to ensure that they do not migrate over time as had happened during Run 2. Following on from this a programme of work on the TDE was defined to be carried out in LS2. This work is summarised in section 2.

1.7 REFERENCE DRAWINGS PRE-LS2 AND POST-LS2

Before entering in detail about the upgrade of the TDE dump system and aiming to ease the understanding of this document, Table 2 lists the main drawings pre and post LS2.

Table 2 - List of main drawings Pre-LS2 and Post-LS2

Pre-LS2	
<u>Drawing Number</u>	<u>Name/Description</u>
LHCTDE__0001	TDE UD68 Assembly
LHCTDE__0011	TDE absorber block assembly
LHCTDE__0015	UD62/UD68 shielding assembly dump support
ST0642594	Titanium sheet Grade-2 (downstream window)
LHCVDWB_0001	Window separating vacuum and N ₂ (upstream)
LCHTDE__0028	Lifting support assembly
Post-LS2	
LHCTDE__0051	TDE block Full assembly (including instrumentation, and cradle)
LHCTDE_0052	UD62 Cradle Equipped

LHCTDE__0067	Upstream Window (DUS_W)
LHCTDE__0044	Welded Extension for the downstream Window
LHCTDE__0045	Bolted Downstream Window (DDS_W)
LHCTDE__0150	Instrumentation Support Upstream
LHCVDWB_0009	New upstream window vacuum side (UHV_W)

2. SUMMARY OF WORK ON THE TDE AND IN THE DUMP CAVERN IN LS2

2.1 SUMMARY OF REQUIREMENTS FOR THE MODIFICATIONS TO BE IMPLEMENTED IN LS2

The extremely high acceleration and force values obtained from the simulation work (described in section 5) led to a change in the foreseen activities on the TDEs during LS2. The main driver for the change in activities was to avoid the risk of the increased beam intensities during Run3 leading to damage of the seals of the LHC vacuum window at the end of the connecting line.

The modifications to be implemented in LS2 address the various problems described in the sections above. The requirements for the new designs and modifications to the infrastructure can therefore be summarised as:

- Compatibility with Run 3 beam parameters
- Prevent N₂ leaks
- Prevent chain clamp fasteners coming loose (avoid transmission of vibration to vacuum sector of beam pipe)
- Avoid migration of dump (problems with remote lifting and dump integrity otherwise)

2.2 SUMMARY OF TECHNICAL CONSTRAINTS

The design modifications considered the following main technical constraints:

- Run 3 beam parameters.
- Vibrations and thermal expansion / retraction cycles.
- High radiation levels on used dump and inside shielding.
 - Remote handling of dump by crane for installation and removal from the shielding.
 - Downstream window must have metallic seals.
 - Cannot modify existing TDE supports inside the shielding.
 - Cannot modify existing TDE core assembly.

More details and estimations of such residual doses can be found in the document [3].

- Lifting and handling operations to be compatible with existing infrastructure and handling equipment.
 - existing remote handling spreader beam and custom-built trailer.
- Use spare dumps (slightly radioactive) as new operational dumps.

- Fit in LS2 schedule.
- Retain the possibility of reverting to the Run 2 configuration in the event of problems with the new designs.

2.3 SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES DURING LS2

Based on the requirements in section 2.1 and the technical constraints listed in 2.2 design and analysis work was carried out which led to a new design concept for how to support the dump block and isolate it from the LHC vacuum. To implement this concept a programme of work was defined for LS2 which included:

- Disconnection of dump from LHC machine vacuum,
- New downstream beam windows,
- New upstream beam windows,
- New dump block support frames,
- N₂ line extension.

Additional work was also proposed as part of the modifications

- New instrumentation for the dump core
- New vacuum window
- Storage of used dump and connecting line

These activities are described in more detail in the following sections. Figure 29 shows the UD cavern configuration once the modifications have been implemented (compare with Figure 7 before the modifications)

Figure 29 – Configuration of beam dump caverns after the LS2 modifications (UD 62 shown)

2.3.1 Disconnection of dump from LHC machine vacuum

In order to avoid risk of damage of seals of the LHC vacuum window at the upstream end of the connecting line it was decided to remove the connecting line completely. This had four main implications:

- The dumped beam would pass through the air of the cavern over a distance of approximately 10 m,
- A new beam window would be needed at the upstream end of the dump,
- A new nitrogen connection to the dump would be needed,
- The vacuum window would no longer be protected from inadvertent mechanical damage during interventions in the UD on the side where the connecting line had previously been.

Radiation protection confirmed that the dumped beam passing through the air of the cavern was acceptable from an RP standpoint; this was formalised in the review held in January 2020 [4].

HSE-OHS confirmed that protection of the vacuum window from accidental impact during interventions in the area could be assured by the installation of a protective steel tube of about a metre long and about 600 mm diameter. This will not be needed if a new Titanium vacuum window is installed. These operational safety aspects were formalised in the review held in January 2020.

Design and analysis work were started on a titanium beam window to be installed on the upstream end of the dump. The new dump upstream window beam window includes a connection method to allow the dump to be connected to the nitrogen supply system (as previously the N₂ injection was via the connection line).

2.3.2 New dump upstream beam window and gasket

A completely new dump upstream window was needed as a result of the decision to remove the connecting line.

The new dump upstream window is designed to be fitted to the dump core vessel without any modification to the existing flange on the upstream end of the dump vessel. The FLUKA-calculated radiation dose at the outside of the upstream dump window over the whole of Run 3 are compatible with the use of EPDM gaskets in place of the previous metallic gaskets (see Section 6.3.3 for more details). The upstream window therefore uses the chain clamp mechanism to secure the window to the dump.

The nitrogen connection to the dump, which was previously assured via the connecting line is now made via a small port at the bottom of the dump upstream window and a lightweight flexible metallic pipe.

Figure 30 - New dump upstream window design – shown installed on the dump. The window is secured by the same chain clamp arrangement used previously – but with an EPDM gasket. The nitrogen connection can be seen at the bottom of the window. Drawing LHCTDE__0109.

More details of the dump upstream window design, its sealing and the associated FLUKA and thermomechanical analysis can be found in section 4.5 and 6.3.

2.3.3 New dump downstream beam window

In response to the leaks on the downstream window and its inaccessibility inside the shielding a revised design with a bolted window to replace the previous design which used a chain clamp had already been prepared before LS2. The design is illustrated in Figure 31.

Figure 31 - New LS2 dump downstream window design. The new titanium grade 5 beam window is attached to the dump vessel via 60 studs and nuts and is sealed with "Conflat" flanges and a copper gasket. An intermediate ring is welded to the existing flange at the downstream end of the dump vessel to enable the change from the previous chain clamp sealing system to the bolted arrangement. Drawing LHCTDE__0045

Details of the new dump downstream window design and the associated FLUKA and thermo-mechanical analysis are given in sections section 4.5 and 6.2.

Figure 32 - New dump downstream window installed on the dump assembly.

2.3.4 New dump block support frames

The new support frame design aims to let the dump block expand, vibrate and contract back to its original dimensions without migrating on its supports.

Key additional constraints on the design are that it must:

- Fit in the same space inside the shielding as the original lifting support
- Be compatible with the remote spreader beam used to lift the dump block
- Be compatible with the trailers used to transport the dump block along the TD tunnel and along the LHC tunnel
- Fit in the space available under the hoists where the dump has to pass over the LHC machine in the junction galleries where the TD tunnel join the LHC (UJ62 and UJ 68)
- Be compatible with radiation doses during Run 3.

The concept finally chosen supports the dump on two loops of steel wire ropes that are suspended from a new support frame which has a structure with the same outside form as the original lifting frame (although it is hollowed out to leave space for the supporting ropes. The support frame concept is illustrated in Figure 33. More details are given in section 8.

Figure 33 - New dump block support frame concept without the dump block. The wire rope loops that support the dump core can be seen inside the cradle structures at each end of the support frame. Drawing LHCTDE__0052

2.3.5 N₂ line extension

Before LS2 the nitrogen supply connection to the dump and connecting line was made near the upstream end of the connecting line. It was therefore necessary to install a new line connecting the nitrogen supply to the dump itself. To do this a connection was foreseen in the new upstream beam window. A new supply pipe was installed along the wall of the UD cavern to the front of the shielding around the dump (see Figure 29). A flexible stainless steel tube provides the connection between the fixed pipework and the upstream window of the dump to allow for movement of the dump (see Figure 34).

Figure 34 - View of the end of the upstream end of the dump showing the Nitrogen line connection to the upstream dump window. The connection between the pipe fixed to the front face of the shielding and the dump upstream window is made with a flexible stainless-steel tube to allow for the movements of the dump.

2.3.6 Instrumentation

New instrumentation will be installed to monitor the dumps during Run 3. Details are given in Section 9.

2.3.7 Storage of used dumps and connecting lines

The two used dumps have been removed from the UD caverns and are stored side by side in a shielded enclosure built up from concrete blocks in the UX65 cavern. Inspection of the used dump graphite core elements will be carried out to check for damage due to beam impacts. The connecting lines are stored in the TD caverns in case it is decided to revert to the original configuration at some stage. The connecting line storage location can be seen in Figure 29.

2.4 FORMAL REVIEW OF PROPOSED LS2 MODIFICATIONS – AND APPROVALS

A review of the proposed LS2 modifications to the dumps and infrastructure as described above along with the supporting analysis and safety assessments (radiation protection and general safety) was held in January 2020. The presentations made at the review can be found in [5].

The reviewers endorsed the proposed LS2 modifications and made recommendations for additional analysis.

The outcome of the review was reported and the formal approval to go-ahead with the implementation of the modifications was given at the LHC Machine Committee (LMC) meeting on 5 February 2020 [6].

An Engineering Change Request covering the programme of modifications was also produced and approved [7].

3. LHC BEAM DUMPING SYSTEM AND FAILURE SCENARIOS

3.1 INTRODUCTION

A detailed description of the full LHC beam dumping system can be found in [2] while here details are only given regarding the dilution kickers. A set of four horizontal (MKBH) and six vertical (MKBV) dilution fast-pulsed kickers is used to sweep the beam on the front face of the dump and thus dilute the deposited energy. Each magnet is powered with a sinusoidal current by a pulsed generator via a low impedance transmission line. During a beam dump, pre-charged oscillating capacitors, coaxially connected to the magnets, are discharged, through solid-state closing switches, to produce an attenuated sinusoid. The MKBV current is shifted by $\sim 90^\circ$ with respect to the horizontal system for a simultaneous trigger of the two systems.

Some key parameters for the dilution kicker magnets are presented in Table 3. The same kick amplitude of approximately 0.28 mrad is required in both the horizontal and vertical plane to paint the beam according to the required shape on the dump. This means that the MKBH, being only four, have a higher magnetic field and this translates in a higher charging voltage in the generators. On the other hand, due to the larger pole gap, the voltage in the MKBV magnets is 10% higher than in the MKBH. The switches and generators of the kickers are being upgraded in LS2 to improve their reliability. Thanks to this upgrade, operation at 7 TeV for the MKBH will be possible with a lower voltage, on the generator side, than what previously used at 6.5 TeV.

Table 3 - MKB operational parameters pre (6.5 TeV) and post (7 TeV) LS2.

	Pre-LS2 (6.5 TeV)		Post-LS2 (7 TeV)	
	MKBV	MKBH	MKBV	MKBH
Magnet type				
System deflection angle [mrad]	0.277	0.278	0.278	0.277
Kick strength per magnet [Tm]	1.000	1.508	1.077	1.624
Magnet pole gap [mm]	70.9	36.9	70.9	36.9
Operating charging voltage in generator [kV]	13.7	24.7	14.8	23.5
Total SEB failure rate probability [y^{-1}]	n.a.	0.15	n.a.	0.0003

3.2 BEAM PARAMETERS & FILLING SCHEMES EXPECTED FOR RUN3

LHC operation foresees only using the so called BCMS (Batch Compression Merging and Splitting [8]) high brightness beams in Run3. The beam parameters are presented in Table 4. The number of particles per bunch and the total number of bunches circulating in the machine have to be intended as the maximum allowed when operating at top energy. Safe operation has to be guaranteed independently from how the 2748 bunches are distributed in the LHC ring. If weaknesses are identified at some dump components (windows or core) in case of a failure in the dilution system, either the number of protons per bunch and/or the total number of bunches (avoid injection of last train) will have to be reduced accordingly.

Table 4 - Main parameters for Run3 operation

Particles per bunch	1.8×10^{11}
Number of bunches	2748
Normalised emittance [μm]	1.8

3.3 FAILURE SCENARIOS TO BE CONSIDERED FOR RUN3

Two types of failures can affect the dilution kickers. A spontaneous firing in one generator or a flashover in a magnet. According to the original design assumptions, the simultaneous loss of two dilution kickers was considered as the worst possible failure scenario. Due to the smaller number of horizontal modules, their contribution in case of a failure is more critical and, for the given dilution pattern, the system is more sensitive to the loss of horizontal dilution.

3.3.1 Spontaneous MKB Firing

In case of a spontaneous firing of one MKB, a synchronous dump is performed as soon as the erratic is detected. In the original design, the total reaction time before the dump could vary between 207 μs and 1300 μs and the remaining MKBs were pulsed only at the actual moment of the beam extraction. This configuration allowed, for a perfect overlapping in anti-phase between the current of the first magnet pulsing and the remaining ones, to lose at worst two kickers. During tests without beam at 7 TeV, some parasitic electromagnetic coupling, through the re-triggering line, caused the simultaneous firing of two neighbouring MKB generators. This event, combined with anti-phase, could determine the loss of more than two MKBs, as shown in Figure 35 for the horizontal plane. As mentioned above, any loss of dilution in the horizontal plane is particularly critical. Moreover, due to the higher operational charging voltage, the likelihood of an erratic in an MKBH generator is higher than in an MKBV one. An upgrade program is being executed to make the full system more reliable already in Run3. In particular, as already mentioned, the MKBH generators will be modified to reduce their operational voltage by approximately 10% for the same kick strength (see Table 3). A new re-triggering system is put in place for the MKBs such that, after a fast detection of one erratic, all the other generators are directly triggered. The risk of phase opposition between kicker waveforms is eliminated in this way. However, since an asynchronous dump has to be avoided, this implies that the extraction kickers are fired within a certain delay (t_{delay}) after the MKBs. This time delay depends on the total reaction time and the position of the abort gap in the ring with respect to the MKDs, which can vary between 0 and 89 μs . For each delay a different pattern is produced at the dump front face and thus a different energy deposition at the dump windows and core (Figure 36).

Figure 35 - Maximum horizontal deflection for spurious firing of one (blue) or, in case of electromagnetic coupling, two (green), three (red) or all (cyan) the MKBHs as a function of the delay between the erratic and the dump execution. The effect on the dilution pattern at the front face of the dump is also shown, courtesy C. Wiesner.

Figure 36 - Ratio between the peak energy density at the different dump components during a spurious trigger of a MKBH and a nominal dump for different delays between the erratic and the actual beam extraction. The line corresponding to the originally assumed worst failure scenario (loss of two MKBH) is shown, courtesy C. Wiesner, M. Frankl.

As a consequence of the implementation of the MKB retriggering the following considerations hold concerning the possible failures during Run3.

Being the reaction time of the system of the order of a few μs , a maximum delay of 100 μs is considered. The highest energy density at the downstream window and the core is reached for a delay of 70 μs and is lower than in case of the loss of two MKBHs. The worst failure scenario for the upstream window corresponds to a delay of 14 μs where the energy density is higher than the case of two missing MKBHs. If problems occur in the synchronization process between the RF and the abort gap, an asynchronous beam dump request is triggered 120 μs after the detection of the erratic to exclude any risk of total loss of dilution. Also in this case, the energy density at the different dump components is lower than the originally considered worst failure scenario.

3.3.2 MKB Flashover

During the execution of a nominal beam dump a spark can occur between different components of a pulsing dilution kicker (see Figure 37 for reference), in particular:

- Between HV and grounded bus-bar,
- Between HV and magnet ground,
- Between HV and vacuum tank,
- On the surface of an isolator,
- On the surface of the HV feedthrough.

Figure 37 - Front and side view of vertical dilution kicker.

Two magnets share the same vacuum tank and the simultaneous loss of two dilution kickers, due to the propagation of the flashover through the plasma in the tank, was considered as the worst failure scenario. During the last year of Run 2, two MKBVs experienced a flashover while extracting 2556 bunches at 6.5 TeV. The second spark occurred 10 μs after the first one when some residual current was in the magnet. This delayed flashover in combination with the antiphase with respect to the remaining kickers resulted in the total loss of three MKBVs for the last trains of extracted bunches, as shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38 - Comparison between the sweep pattern as measured during Run 2 MKBV flashover (dark red dots), nominal dilution (green) and in case of loss of one (blue), two (orange) or three (red) MKBVs, courtesy C. Wiesner.

Despite the system is being upgraded to reduce the voltage, and thus the risk of flashover, both in the MKBV and MKBH magnets, this type of failure cannot be fully excluded. All the dump components have to withstand the energy deposition corresponding to the worst failure that was identified as the one occurring in two MKBH and assuming a delay of 16 μs (Figure 39).

Figure 39 - Comparison between measured nominal sweep pattern (dark red dots) and the simulated one when flashovers occur in two MKBHs with a relative delay of 16 μs (assumed worst case).

3.3.3 Total loss of dilution

The LHC dump system was designed to ensure a Safety Integral Level 4 (corresponding to one event every 105 years) concerning the probability of having a failure of all the dilution kickers during a beam dump. In reality, due to the overshoot of the MKD extraction kicker system, a minimum dilution is still granted but not sufficient to exclude severe damages of the dump components. Such an event is considered as catastrophic

and would require the replacement of the dump. Due to its improbability, it should not be taken into account for the design of the new dump elements. Nevertheless, the problem of a possible contamination due to the loss of radioactive material has to be addressed.

3.3.4 MKB Capacitors Upgrade

New capacitors will be installed in the dilution kickers in LS2 and will allow to reduce the voltage on the magnet side by $\sim 8\%$ for the MKBV and $\sim 3\%$ for the MKBH. This modification will reduce the risk of flashover but will affect the oscillation period and thus modify the sweep speed and the dilution pattern. The resulting bunch distribution at the dump front face for the original and the new capacitors is shown in Figure 40. First order calculations were performed to evaluate the impact of such a modification on the peak energy density at the dump both for the nominal case and for different failures of the dilution kickers. No major differences are expected but dedicated studies should be performed for the most critical cases. Different delays between an erratic and the beam extraction or between two flashovers could be identified as more critical than the original ones but the effective energy density should stay the same within the simulation accuracy.

Figure 40 - Dilution pattern at the dump front face for the original (red) and the new (blue) MKB capacitors during a nominal dump. The stars define the points corresponding to the peak energy density.

3.4 WHAT WILL BE DIFFERENT FOR HL-LHC

The LHC dilution system will undergo a major upgrade in LS3 to cope with operation with the increased intensity and brightness beams foreseen for the HL-LHC era (see Table 5). Two types of beam are considered: BCMS and standard 25 ns. Two additional MKBHs will be installed in each extraction line to be able to reduce the operational voltage and thus the risk of failures while making the system less sensitive to the loss of horizontal dilution. Moreover, the LHC beam dump design will be fully revised. Sweep patterns for nominal operation and in case of all the above-mentioned failures will be provided as an input for the design of the new dumps.

Table 5 - Main parameters for HL-LHC operation

	BCMS	Standard 25 ns
Particles per bunch	2.3×10 ¹¹	
Number of bunches	2748	2760
Normalised emittance [μm]	1.7	2.1

4. ENERGY DEPOSITION ON THE DUMP BLOCK AND DOSES – INCLUDING IN TD TUNNELS

Simulations of the energy deposited by 7 TeV LHC beams in the dump components have been carried out using the Monte Carlo code FLUKA [9] [10]. The geometry of the TDE including cavern and surrounding shielding is implemented in FLUKA via the graphical interface FLAIR [11] as shown in Figure 41.

Figure 41 - Model of TDE cavern and shielding.

In the following sections, energy deposition studies in the main dump components for regular dump and dilution kicker failure scenarios under Run 3 beam parameters (see section 4.1) are summarized, followed by a discussion of the radiation to the electronics for the dump instrumentation.

4.1 NUMERICAL MODEL AND ASSUMPTIONS

An overview of the most important beam parameters used for energy deposition studies is given in Table 6.

It has to be remarked that the emittance values reported in Table 6 refer to the injection phase and are then considered as input parameters in the analysis. The choice of not considering the emittance growth guarantees a more conservative approach on the energy deposited into the dump.

Table 6 -Overview of beam parameters. The values highlighted in red are those employed for energy deposition studies.

	LHC design (ultimate)	Run 2	Run 3	HL-LHC (BCMS)
Energy [TeV]	7	6.5	6.5-7	7
N. bunches	2808	2556	2748	2748
Bunch intensity [ppb]	1.15 · 10 ¹¹ (1.7 · 10 ¹¹)	1.2 · 10 ¹¹	1.4 · 10 ¹¹ 1.8 · 10 ¹¹	2.3 · 10 ¹¹
Emittance [μm]	3.75	1.7-2.1	1.8	1.7
Stored energy [MJ]	362 (535)	319	431 - 555	709

The Batch Compression Bunch Merging and Splitting (BCMS) filling scheme developed for HL-LHC has been assumed also for Run 3. It allows 2748 bunches with 288 bunches per injection for 12 injections.

As mentioned in Section 3, a new sweep pattern will be adopted in Run 3. Temperature increase with Run 3 sweep pattern is verified only for the dump core and compared with Run 2 sweep pattern. The other results discussed here refer to the Run 2 sweep patterns for regular dump and dilution failure scenarios.

To perform accurate energy deposition studies, a detailed (as much as possible) TDE assembly model has been implemented in FLUKA via FLAIR starting from available mechanical drawings. The properties of windows and dump core components used in energy deposition simulations are summarised in Table 7.

Table 7- Material properties of TDE core and windows used in simulation.

Component	Length [cm]	Material	Density [g/cm³]
UHW upstream window			
Disc	1.5	CfC (SIGRABOND® 1501G)	1.5
Foil	0.02	Stainless steel (SS316L)	7.8
Dump upstream window			
Disc	1	Titanium Grade 23	4.43
Core			
High density block	70	Graphite (SiGRAFINE®)	1.77
Low density section	342	Graphite (SIGRAFLEX®)	1.1 - 1.2
Plate	8	Graphite (HLM quality)	1.72
Vessel		Stainless steel (URANUS 45)	7.8
Dump downstream window			
Disc	1	Titanium Grade 5	4.43

It has to be remarked that there is some inconsistency in the low-density section length given in drawings and the number of 2 mm sheets ordered from the manufacturer. Our assumption (and used in the simulation) is specified in Table 7.

Additionally, two density values are reported for the low-density section. The higher value (1.2 g/cm³) is generally used in the simulations being more conservative for the low-density graphite core. The lower density value (1.1 g/cm³) is instead assumed only in dedicated studies, e.g. to assess effect on downstream window and vessel since a lower density would yield higher temperatures for the downstream equipment.

4.2 TOTAL ENERGY IN THE DIFFERENT ELEMENTS IN THE CAVERNS

At the beginning of Run 3 with a bunch intensity of $1.4 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb, the total energy stored by each beam will reach 431 MJ. At the highest envisaged Run 3 bunch intensity ($1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb), it will increase to 555 MJ, exceeding the LHC ultimate value (535 MJ).

It has been evaluated with FLUKA that around 96% of the total stored energy is deposited in the dump and surrounding components via electromagnetic shower (80%) and ionization losses of hadrons and muons (16%). The remaining 4% is spent in nuclear interaction and escaping neutrinos (i.e. not deposited). Taking this into account, at the highest Run 3 bunch intensity, the energy effectively deposited by each proton beam will be 530.3 MJ and distributed as reported in Table 8.

Table 8- Distribution of energy deposited in different elements of TDE cavern.

Element	Total deposited energy: 530.3 MJ	
Dump ¹	81.6 %	432.6 MJ
Shielding	18.2 %	96.7 MJ
Cavern	0.1 %	0.7 MJ
Molasse	0.06 %	0.3 MJ

In particular, the energy deposited in dump assembly is distributed between vessel, core and windows as described in Table 7.

Table 9- Distribution of energy deposited in the dump assembly.

Element	Total deposited energy: 432.6 MJ	
Dump upstream window	0.001%	0.002 MJ
High-density graphite	49.5%	214.4 MJ
Low-density graphite	42.4%	183.3 MJ
Graphite plates	2.6%	11.3 MJ
Downstream window	0.06%	0.3 MJ
Vessel	5.4 %	23.4 MJ

4.3 PEAK ENERGY DENSITIES AND TEMPERATURES IN THE GRAPHITE CORE

An estimation of the maximum temperature after a beam dump is obtained by simulating with FLUKA the energy deposited in the core by a single proton bunch and superimposing it at each bunch position along the sweep pattern. This approach allows for a faster

¹ Dump includes vessel, core and windows.

evaluation of the peak temperature (w.r.t. simulate the complete swept beam), without neglecting the contribution from all other bunches.

In case of regular beam dump, the longitudinal peak temperature profile in the core, i.e. up to the first high-density graphite block after the low-density section is shown in Figure 42 for three bunch intensities and 2748 bunches. In these calculations, the Sigraflex density is set to 1.2 g/cm³.

Figure 42 - (left) Longitudinal peak temperature profile for Run 3 and HL-LHC bunch intensity in case of regular dump. (right) Energy density variation along the Run 2 sweep pattern at the depth in the core where maximum temperature is reached.

As visible in Figure 42 (right), the maximum energy density is reached on the upper-left part of the sweep pattern, where the sweep velocity reduces (i.e. after about 15 μs when the vertical dilution changes direction). Due to the shower build-up, the maximum temperature is reached at a depth of around 2.8 m inside the low-density graphite (SIGRAFLEX®) section, with the peak values shown in Table 10.

Table 10- Peak temperature in the core in case of regular beam dump.

	Bunch intensity [ppb]	Max temperature [°C]
Run 2	1.2·10 ¹¹	1000
Run 3	1.4·10 ¹¹	1230
	1.8·10 ¹¹	1500
HL-LHC	2.3·10 ¹¹	1850

Very high temperatures are already expected for a regular beam dump with the progressive increase of the bunch intensity. Significant stress levels are induced as a consequence of absorption of such high energy and intensity beams.

The peak load on the dump core increases even more in the case of dilution kicker failures. As described in Section 3, the 4 horizontal dilution kickers (MKBH) are one of the most critical system in LBDS. Losing 50% dilution in the horizontal plane (referred as 2 MKBH

off or missing) was so far considered as the worst failure scenario. In this case, a shrink of the sweep pattern (Figure 43 right) is observed with a consequent temperature rise in the core. In Figure 43 (left), the peak temperatures in the core for regular dump and failure scenario of 2 MKBH missing are compared.

Figure 43 - (left) Longitudinal peak temperature profiles for Run 3 bunch intensities in case of 2 MKBH missing and a regular dump. (right) Energy density variation along the sweep pattern at the depth of about 280 cm in the core where the maximum temperature is reached.

For regular dump and failure scenario of 2 MKBH missing a comparison between the maximum temperatures reached in the core with Run 2 default sweep pattern and the new developed for Run 3 is made. The two sweep patterns are shown in Figure 40 where the location of the peak energy density is highlighted. Energy deposition simulations demonstrated that the maximum temperature reached with the new sweep pattern (Run 3 sweep pattern) is comparable (within 0.2%) with the Run 2 sweep pattern for regular dump and 2MKBH missing.

Table 11 provides an overview of the maximum temperature in the core with different numbers of dilution kickers missing. In case of 2 MKBH missing (i.e. 6 active MKBV and 2 active MKBH), the maximum temperature increases more than 50% w.r.t. the value obtained during a regular dump.

Table 11- Maximum temperature (in °C) in the core in case of different active dilution kickers.

Run 3 1.4·10 ¹¹ ppb		# active MKBV			Run 3 1.8·10 ¹¹ ppb		# active MKBV		
		6	5	4			6	5	4
# active MKBH	4	1230	1250	1280	# active MKBH	4	1500	1520	1570
	3	1470	1500	1520		3	1800	1830	1860
	2	1850	1880	1920		2	2280	2310	2360

Observed for the first time in 2018, the loss of two dilution kickers due to delayed flashovers inside their common vacuum tank is considered the new worst failure scenario. Although only two kickers are involved, the actual effect on the sweep pattern might be

equivalent to the loss of more than two kickers since they can partially cancel the kick of the other MKBs. Depending on time at which the flashover occurs during the beam extraction, the sweep pattern assumes different shapes with partially overlaps or hot-spots [12]. The peak temperature in the core is evaluated at possible times between 0 and 86 μs at which a flashover might occur and its variation displayed in Figure 44.

Figure 44 - (left) Peak temperature in the core for Run 3 beams with a bunch intensity of $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb as a function of the time when the first flashover occurs. Comparison with the peak temperature in case of regular dump and 2 MKBH missing (see also Table 11). (right) Energy density variation along the sweep pattern at the time (16 μs) where the maximum temperature is reached.

As visible in Figure 44 (right), the highest temperature is due to the head-tail overlap of the sweep pattern. In such a situation, the maximum temperature in the core is around 2150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with $1.4 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb while it increases up to 2660 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

Under Run 3 conditions and even more with HL-LHC bunch intensity, TDE graphite core will increasingly experience high stress levels with possible material degradation or damage. A proper SIGRAFLEX® characterization is needed to understand if the core can withstand such high temperatures and stress. For this purpose, a collaboration with NTNU/SINTEF (Norway) institute is ongoing and more details are given Section 5.2.

4.4 OVERVIEW OF ENERGY DEPOSITION IN THE STAINLESS-STEEL VESSEL

From Table 7 it is possible to observe that the energy deposited in the vessel is much smaller than in the Graphite but is still not negligible: 23.4 MJ. However, this leads to a rapid temperature increase that induces fast movements and vibrations (see Section 5.7 for a detailed analysis). The peak temperature profile in case of regular beam dump is displayed in Figure 45 with a maximum around 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 45 - Peak temperature profile in the stainless-steel vessel in case of regular dump with $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb. The dump sketch on top helps to identify at which depth the peak temperature in the vessel occurs.

4.5 OVERVIEW OF ENERGY DEPOSITION IN THE UPSTREAM AND DOWNSTREAM BEAM WINDOWS

Energy deposition studies have been also performed for two other critical components of the TDE assembly: the upstream (a new addition of the LS2 consolidation works) and downstream window. Located at the extremities of the dump core, the two windows have to withstand the thermal load and vibrations of the entire dump structure while keeping the nitrogen gas confined in the vessel. The results summarized in the following sections quantify the temperatures induced by the traversing beam protons and secondary particles. It is important to note, that the vibrations of the dump structure can, however, yield a more important contribution to the stresses in the windows than the beam-induced thermal load itself, as demonstrated in Section 6 and 7.

4.5.1 Upstream window: UHV_W and DUS_W

Until the end of Run 2 a unique upstream window was in use separating the LHC Ultra-High-Vacuum from the dump nitrogen section. This window consisted of a 15 mm CfC Sigrabond® disc and a 0.2 mm stainless-steel (SS316L) foil. In preparation for Run 3 and HL-LHC, thermo-mechanical studies have demonstrated the need to change the configuration of this upstream window, by replacing the thin stainless steel foil with a more robust material to withstand higher bunch intensity [13] [14]. Part of upgrade plan during LS2, the nitrogen section will be removed during LS2 imposing the installation of an additional window on TDE side. At LHC restart operation post-LS2, there will be an "upstream window" on LHC-UHV side (UHV_W) and one on TDE side (DUS_W). At the same time, material upgrade imposed from thermo-mechanical studies [13] [14] is applied on both UHV_W and DUS_W with the use of titanium Grade-5. Let highlight that the analysis of UHV_W window is not included in this report since it is out of this scope. In any case, the final design of such window can be found in LHCVDWB_0009. It consists in a double window with a mid-chamber configuration, using a sandwich window in the

UHV side (15 mm CfC + 1 mm Ti + 15 mm CfC), and a 10 mm titanium Grade-5 in the external.

From the point of view of the DUS_W, the FLUKA analysis suggest that the maximum temperature reached in a 10 mm thickness titanium window is slightly higher than in one with a CfC + stainless-steel foil. Nevertheless, the upgraded Ti configuration will benefit from the higher strength of titanium (see Section 6 for more details).

Energy deposition studies have been performed on UHV_W and DUS_W using the configurations and materials of Table 7. The results correspond to the configuration that was finally adopted. More accurate temperature estimations based on FE for the DUS_W (also considering more failure scenarios) can be found in the summary table of section 6.6. The thermomechanical analysis of the UHV_W is not within the scope of this document.

Table 12- Temperature increase (in °C) in the components of UHV_W and DUS_W post-LS2 with bunch intensity of $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

Type	Component	Regular dump	2 MKBH missing
UHV_W (double-window chamber)	15 mm CfC	18	31
	0.2 Ti-Gr5	28	50
	15 mm CfC	24	42
	10 mm Ti-Gr5	52	93
DUS_W	10 mm Ti-Gr5	65	67

4.5.2 Downstream window

The criticality of the downstream window arises from its exposure to the longitudinal tail of the particle shower from the dump core. The uncertainty of the SIGRAFLEX® density - between 1.1 g/cm^3 (guarantee by the manufacturer) and 1.2 g/cm^3 (nominal) - has an impact on the energy deposited in the downstream window. Energy deposition studies on the upgraded configuration of the downstream window (10 mm of titanium grade 5 – Ti6Al4V) have been performed for both SIGRAFLEX® densities and the resulting peak temperatures are displayed in Figure 46.

Figure 46 - Longitudinal peak temperature in the downstream window (Ti6Al4V) in case of regular dump (left) and 2 MKBH missing (right) for two density values of SIGRAFLEX® (bunch intensity of $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb).

As for the upstream window, the temperature reached during a beam dump is not extremely high but leads to considerable stress levels as discussed in Section 7. It is important to remark as well that these simulations are subjected to significant uncertainties induced by the interaction through more than 8 meters of graphitic materials. Such uncertainties could imply a deposition of energy of a factor up to x2 with respect the simulation predictions. One of the aims of the new temperature sensors installed in the downstream window (described in detail in section 9.1.2) is to benchmark these uncertainties.

4.6 ENERGY DEPOSITION IN THE SUPPORT FRAME AND ROPES

Introduced in section 2.3, the system for mitigating the dump movement made by two ropes and their supports has been implemented in FLUKA as sketched in Figure 47.

Figure 47 - FLUKA model of a transversal cut of the dump core, support frame and ropes.

Energy deposition studies on the movement mitigation system have been performed as shown in Figure 48 for the support frame.

Figure 48 - Energy density (in J/cm^3) in a cross-section of dump core and support frame upstream (left) and downstream (right) for a regular dump assuming a bunch intensity of $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb. In order to better illustrate the energy density gradients in the frames, only a limited energy density range is shown (hence the energy density in the core is out of scale).

Under Run 3 condition (with $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb), the energy density in the upstream cable (i.e. closer to the upstream window) varies in the range 48 – 57 J/cm³. In the downstream cable, the energy density reduces to 37 – 43 J/cm³. FLUKA energy deposition studies have been used as input for the thermo-mechanical analysis of these components (see Section 5.7).

4.7 RADIATION LEVELS OF RELEVANCE FOR THE INSTRUMENTATION

During LS2, new instrumentation is planned to be installed on the dumps to monitor their behaviour and movements. The electronics associated to the instrumentation must be installed in a low-radiation environment to not compromise its functioning.

Fluences of high-energy hadrons (HEH above 20 MeV) and thermal neutrons are the most relevant quantities in radiation-to-electronics studies. For the LHC radiation environment, the limits for electronics of distributed and interlocked systems are set as [15]:

- High energy hadrons fluence/year: $3 \cdot 10^6$;
- Thermal neutrons fluence/year: $3 \cdot 10^7$;
- 1 Gy/year or 5 Gy over the full lifetime.

4.8 DOSE TO INSTRUMENTATION ELECTRONICS IN TD TUNNELS

The TD extraction tunnel geometry has been included into the existing FLUKA model of dump and cavern. This allows to evaluate the yearly radiation level due to 150 dumps at top energy and find the more convenient location for installing the electronics.

Figure 49 Model of extraction tunnel, cavern and dump

Figure 50 - High-energy hadrons (left) and thermal neutrons (right) equivalent fluence along the extraction tunnel. As normalization factor 150 dumps/year are assumed with 2748 bunches and $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

In order to account for all radiation sources, in the FLUKA model the beam is set up upstream of the BTVDD (Beam TV Dump Detector) beam screen, which is placed 33 m

upstream of the dump and is used during operation to monitor the dilution. The screen is made of alumina and is 3 mm thick [16]. The fluence of high-energy hadrons and thermal neutrons generated from the primary beam impact against the BTVDD and the beam dump is scored along the extraction tunnel as shown in Figure 50.

The steep increase of the HEH-Eq. fluence (Figure 50-left) at 33 m upstream of the dump is due to the presence of the BTVDD screen. Two possible locations were initially considered for electronics: at 50 m and 80 m upstream of the front face of the dump. The normalized annual fluence at the two locations is reported in Table 13.

Table 13- Normalized annual high-energy hadrons and thermal neutrons fluence at two locations in the extraction tunnel. As normalization factor 150 dumps/year are assumed with 2748 bunches and $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

Fluence [cm ⁻² /year]	Distance to the dump	
	50 m	80 m
Thermal neutrons eq.	$1.7 \cdot 10^{10}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^9$
High-Energy Hadrons eq.	$1.4 \cdot 10^{10}$	$4.3 \cdot 10^9$

Based on radiation levels along the extraction tunnel folded in with the capability of the instrumentation, it has been decided to install the electronics at 80 m upstream of the dump. The values of Table 13 imposes to enclose the electronics inside a proper shielding. The optimized shielding design (Figure 51) is composed by iron to reduce high-energy hadrons components and borated (5%) polyethylene to absorb thermal neutrons.

Figure 51 - FLUKA model of the shielding for the electronics.

The FLUKA simulation has been repeated including the optimized shielding design in order to derive thermal neutrons and high-energy hadrons fluence at electronics level (i.e. inside the shielding). The results are reported in Table 14 assuming 150 dumps/year with 2748 bunches and $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

Table 14 - Normalized annual high-energy hadrons and thermal neutrons fluence inside/outside the shielding at the electronics rack position.

Quantities	Inside Fluence [cm ⁻² /year]	Outside Fluence [cm ⁻² /year]
Thermal neutrons eq.	$2.8 \cdot 10^7$	$1.6 \cdot 10^9$
High-Energy Hadrons eq.	$2.7 \cdot 10^7$	$4.3 \cdot 10^9$

Comparing Table 13 and Table 14, the effect of the shielding presence is clearly visible: high-energy hadrons and thermal neutrons annual fluence is reduced by roughly two

orders of magnitude. Even if the high-energy hadrons fluence inside the shielding exceeds the original limit ($3 \cdot 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-2}/\text{year}$), the results are considered acceptable since the electronics belongs to a non-distributed and non-interlocked system. A few failures/year might still happen depending on the electronics components. Instead, a plate of 5 cm thickness of borated-polyethylene (5%) is enough to reduce the annual thermal neutron fluence below the prescribed limit ($3 \cdot 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-2}/\text{year}$).

4.9 RADIATION LEVELS ON THE INSTRUMENTATION AND SEALS

During LS2, new instrumentation is installed on both dumps to monitor their movements as described in Section 9. FLUKA simulations have been performed to estimate annual dose levels at the location where the instrumentation is installed. For this analysis we use Run 3 sweep pattern and assume 150 dumps/year with 2748 bunches and $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

Annual dose distribution at outer flange of TDE upstream window is displayed in Figure 52. A dose of 15-20 kGy per year is expected at the location where LVDTs are mounted. The dose value found with FLUKA is in agreement with RP measurement (8 kGy in 2018) after correcting for the bunch intensity.

Figure 52- Annual dose distribution for the TDE upstream window outer flange where LVDT are installed.

5. THERMOMECHANICAL ASSESSMENT OF DUMP BLOCK: CORE AND VESSEL BEHAVIOUR

5.1 REVIEW OF DUMP CORE CALCULATIONS

As commented earlier in this report, during the last years of Run-2 operation, movement and high vibrations of both TDE dumps were detected after each beam dump, as well as other related issues, like nitrogen leaks, loosening of the fasteners, etc. As a result of the beam-matter interaction phenomenon, an elevated amount of energy is deposited on the TDE dump (and surroundings) during the beam impact ($86 \mu\text{s}$). This energy deposition leads to a sudden temperature increase and a violent dynamic response of the entire dump, which is the source of the observed issues during operation.

Initial analyses were carried out during the conception/design of the dump block in the early 2000s [17] [18] [19]. The authors were focused mainly on the thermal performance of core. Using FLUKA software for the energy deposition and ANSYS® software for the thermal phenomenon, different materials and configuration of the core were studied. Due to the computational limitations at that date, simplified numerical models were used to estimate the transient thermal behaviour after the beam impact. It is interesting to note that peaks of temperature in the order of 1150-1800°C (depending on the beam scenario) were expected in the core, with a cooling period of dump longer than 13 hrs. The authors suggested the installation of a water-cooling system to extract the heat more efficiently. During the execution phase, the envisaged cooling system was exchanged with a once-through external ventilation system with a poor efficiency in terms of heat transfer.

Additional studies were developed by Century Dynamics [20] for the case of a total dilution failure scenario. In such a case, the study concluded that sublimation of the graphite core and failure of the windows was to be expected.

During last few years new FLUKA simulations have been carried out to check the performance of the core according to the beam requirements (see [21] [22] [23] [24]). Nevertheless, thermo-mechanical assessment of the dump core is still a big challenge from the engineering point of view. The core is exposed to extremely high thermal loads and the physical and mechanical behaviour/properties of the material itself are not well known [25]. A big effort is been dedicated recently on that topic as will be shown in the next Section 5.2.

A special attention has been also paid to the windows, where the structural integrity has been checked for different beam scenarios (see [26] [27] [28] [13]). A dedicated section for the windows is included in this report.

To the knowledge of the authors of the present report, there is no previous general analysis of the dynamic behaviour of the entire dump block. This analysis is vital not only to explain the observed issues during the RUN 2 operational period, but also it is mandatory in order to ensure the safe operation for the foreseen Run 3 beam scenarios.

As will be shown, several numerical models of the full dump have been developed in order to assess the movement of the dump after the beam impact. These models have been validated by comparison with experimental measurements.

5.2 DISCUSSION ABOUT THE AVAILABLE MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Thermo-mechanical properties of SIGRAFLEX® are not well known and they are required in order to analyse the behaviour and structural integrity of the dump core. The behaviour of the SIGRAFLEX® is extremely complex for many reasons. The main sources of this complexity are discussed below:

- The material seems to be made of graphite flakes/ worms (see Figure 53), which are compressed together, producing a layered structure through the thickness of the SIGRAFLEX® sheet.

Figure 53 - SIGRAFLEX® structure. Extracted from HRMAT-43 experiment [29].

- High orthotropic behaviour
- Non-continuous material
- High porosity
- Asymmetrical behaviour in traction/compression
- Brittle behaviour (in traction).

Moreover, the SIGRAFLEX® core is exposed to high dynamic thermo-mechanical loads:

- High temperature (1500°C)
- High strain rate (around 10^4 s^{-1})

All these considerations make the characterization and numerical modelling of the SIGRAFLEX® a challenge from all engineering points of view.

In the frame of the HL-LHC-WP14 and in the context of the upgrade of the TDE for Run 3 and for its future use in other Beam Intercepting Devices (BIDs), an agreement between NTNU and CERN has been signed. The aim of this collaboration is the development of a numerical model that is able to represent the behaviour of the SIGRAFLEX® under a direct beam impact and in conditions similar to those found in the dump. More information can be found in [30]. Preliminary thermal-mechanical characterization can be found in [31].

5.3 DIFFERENT BEHAVIOUR TIMESCALES ("FAST" AND "SLOW" EFFECTS)

After the proton beam impact on the TDE dump, a significant amount of energy, $\approx 81\%$ of proton beam energy, (see Table 8) is deposited in the dump. As a result of this energy deposition, the temperature rises suddenly during the beam impact and produces a thermal expansion of the entire dump block.

As commented previously, two interferometers were installed at the upstream end of the dump block (flange dump block-connection line) and upstream of the connection line for each cavern (UD68 and UD62), called hereinafter as dump-interferometer and connection line interferometer, respectively. Both dumps and caverns are symmetrical. It is to be

recalled that the interferometers measure the displacement along the three main directions (longitudinal, vertical, transversal direction).

Figure 54 shows the displacements of the dump during several days from 2-May-2018 to 10-May-2018. It was observed that permanent displacements in the horizontal and longitudinal directions occurred after series of beam dumps, where the longitudinal one was the most significant. The amplitude of the permanent displacement seems to be related to the beam intensity and the frequency of beam dumps. The more frequent the beam impact, the larger the permanent displacement. One has to be cautious with the interpretation of the interferometers measures because some of the drift could be produced due to limitations and misalignment issues of the sensor itself. Although the trends should be right, absolute values should not be considered accurate.

Typical movement of the dump block for a single beam dump is shown in Figure 55. During the first 25 min. after the beam impact, the extremity of the dump-block, attached to the connecting line, expands longitudinally (opposite to the direction of the beam). Then, the dump block starts to shrink back to the original position asymptotically. Typical period of this process can be more than 18 hrs, depending on the beam intensity. A similar pattern is observed in vertical and horizontal directions. This phenomenon is related to the quasi-static thermal expansion of the dump and the heat transfer. Hereinafter it is referred to as slow movement/expansion of the dump block.

Focusing on the first two hundred milliseconds after the beam dump event, the dump exhibits a fast oscillatory movement (see Figure 55a). This movement is related to the natural frequencies of the dump itself. The fastest oscillations are produced along the longitudinal direction at 190 Hz approximately. Vertical and horizontal oscillations ($\approx 37\text{ Hz}$) are related to bending modes. The oscillation amplitudes depend on the beam intensity and decay rapidly after a few cycles (typical damping ratio $\xi \approx 0.25$ based on the logarithmic decrement for Run 2 era) towards a quasi-steady state. This behaviour is called as fast movement and it is the source of the most of issues found during Run 2. Therefore, it will be analyzed more in detail in Section 5.7.

Figure 54 - a) Beam intensity at the extraction from LHC ring; and b, c, d) displacements of the dump interferometer along longitudinal, horizontal and vertical direction, respectively, measured from 02-May-2018 to 10-May-2018 on UD68. (beam intensity $1.02 \cdot 10^{14}$ p and 6.5 TeV)

(a)

(b)

Figure 55 - Displacements of the dump block measured with the dump-interferometer on 16-June-2018 for UD68. a) Continuous signal at low acquisition rate (1Hz) during a period of 16 hrs and b) high acquisition frequency signal (> 200 kHz) after the beam impact.

5.4 OVERVIEW OF THE PERFORMED SIMULATIONS

As described in previous Section, two different behaviours of the dump were observed after the beam dump: a fast movement that appears during the first second; and a slow or quasi-static movement during a period of several hours. Because of the different nature of both movements and temporal scales, two different kinds of analysis were developed (see Table 15). For each kind of analysis, a series of simulations was performed considering different assumptions/boundary conditions and emphasising different components of the dump.

The slow movement is produced by a quasi-static thermal expansion of the dump. After the beam impact, the energy deposited in the dump is diffused from the core to the vessel and then it is extracted by convection and radiation to the ambient/surrounding. This phenomenon involves a change of the temperature distribution with time and a slow thermal movement of the entire dump block. An implicit thermo-mechanical Finite Element Analysis (FEA) model was developed using ANSYS® software. This technique is able to efficiently model long term simulations thanks to the implicit temporal integration scheme that allows unconditional stable (and adaptive) large time steps. More detail about this model will be explained in Section 5.5

Table 15 - Workflow of the different thermo-mechanical analyses

	Time range	Software	Details
Fast movement	25 ms	LS-DYNA®	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full dump and frame - Thermo-mechanical simulation (direct weak coupling) - Transient analysis based on an explicit scheme.
Slow movement	~12 hrs	ANSYS Mechanical®	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dump block - Transient implicit thermal analysis - Quasi-static mechanical analysis

On the other hand, the fast movement and vibrations are a consequence of the high dynamic response of the dump to the sudden energy deposition during the beam impact. Explicit codes are especially suitable for this kind of problems and efficiently treat them with complex non-linear large models. For this purpose, the LS-DYNA® code is used.

5.5 THERMAL REVIEW OF THE ENTIRE DUMP

With the aim of assessing the slow movement of the dump, thermal simulation of the entire dump block was carried out. ANSYS transient thermal software was used (ANSYS® 19.1). Then, temperature evolution with time can be imported to the transient mechanical solver in order to evaluate the quasi-static thermal expansion.

Properties of the material depending on the temperature were considered (reader is referred to 1.1.1.1A.3 for more details).

Figure 56 shows the numerical model of the dump. 2.8 million elements (first order) were used for the core and vessel. First order elements, although less accurate than second order elements, are more robust and exhibit a lower computational cost, which is required for this large model. Some features of the mesh are shown in Figure 56a and 56b. Several elements through the thickness of the vessel were used in order to capture the temperature gradient. Figure 56b shows the mesh refinement around the beam impact region. The characteristic mesh size in that region is 2 mm.

(a)

(b)

Figure 56 - (a) Numerical model of the TDE dump. (b) mesh detail of the extremity of the dump. Note the fine mesh on the beam impact region; several (three) elements through the thickness of the vessel; matching mesh between core and vessel.

An ambient temperature of 22°C was considered. Convection and radiation with the surrounding were included in the model. An emissivity $\varepsilon = 0.7$ was assumed [32]. Currently there is an external air-cooling system that blows 5000 m³/h on the vessel [33]. Heat transfer coefficient (HTC) air-vessel was estimated based on semi-empirical formulations [34] [35]. Thermal properties of the air (specific heat, density, thermal conductivity, dynamic viscosity, thermal expansion and Prandtl number) were considered depending on the temperature. Figure 58 shows the average HTC on the vessel depending on the temperature.

Figure 57 - Air cooling system/ventilation system.

The HTC was cross-checked by 2D CFX simulations considering a representative transversal section of the vessel. Table 16 shows the average HTC on the vessel assuming a homogeneous temperature distribution of 75°C (as will be shown later, this temperature is around the average temperature on the vessel at the time corresponding to the highest temperature). Numerical results are 25% higher than analytical ones. As observed on the Table, the air-cooling system has a low impact on the HTC ($\approx 40\%$ with respect to total HTC). It is assumed that the function of the air system is related to air renewal and to avoid local air stagnation.

Figure 58 - Convection heat transfer coefficient on the external surface of the vessel depending on the temperature and computed analytical [34] [35].

Table 16 - Heat transfer coefficient air-vessel considering an homogeneous temperature on the vessel (75°C) computed analytically and numerically (2D CFX).

	Natural convection [W/m²K]	Forced convection [W/m²K]
Analytical calculation	5.1 [4]	8.5 [5]
Numerical analysis	6.8	10.7

Thermal contact conductance (TCC) between the vessel and the core was computed based on semi-empirical formulations [36]. TCC depends on the material properties, surface finish (see drawing LHCTDE__0002 and LHCTDE__0003) and the contact pressure. Figure 59 shows the TCC between graphite and stainless steel depending on the contact pressure.

Figure 59 - Thermal contact conductance between isostatic polycrystalline R7300 SIGRAFINE® blocks and stainless steel Uranus-45 vessel vs contact pressure.

The isostatic Sigratine® R7300 blocks were introduced in the vessel by shrink fitting technique. Considering the manufacturing tolerances, the interference may be between [650-800] μm . This interference produces a contact pressure of [7.5-9.2] MPa (see Figure 60). The plastic index is above unity ($Y = 7.5 > 1$), which means plastic deformation in the region of the contact surface. According to the previous graph, the TCC is 12-14 kW/m²K, where the minimum value has been used from a conservative assumption.

Figure 60 - Contact pressure between vessel and high-density core due to the shrink fitting.

In case of the low density core, the Sigraflex® is just sitting on the vessel by the effect of the gravity. The external surface of the low-density core was divided in two parts: bottom and top side (see Figure 61). Based on the average pressure contact on the bottom side, a TCC= 575 W/m²K was calculated. On the top side of the SIGRAFLEX® there is a small gap with respect to the vessel, filled with gas. Convection due to the nitrogen gas and radiation to the vessel was assumed.

Figure 61 - Thermal contact between core and vessel. Orange colour means the contact is tight and the main mechanism is conduction heat transfer, whilst the yellow colour denotes a weak contact with gap where the convection and radiation phenomenon are dominant.

FLUKA energy deposition on the dump was imported as internal heat generation in the model. Figure 62 shows the energy deposition on the vessel and core. The maximum energy peak is found in the SIGRAFLEX® core and the 2nd HD block. The global error on the total imported energy in ANSYS® is 0.12%, whilst the local error at the peak is around 2.7%.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 62 - Energy density deposition in: a) the vessel; b) detail through the vessel thickness; c) detail of low density core. (Z-Axis is the beam direction)

Figure 63 shows a series of pictures of the temperature distribution in the dump: immediately after the beam impact and after 12 hrs. After the beam impact, the energy is focused around the beam sweep and the maximum temperature, $T_{max}=1300^{\circ}C$, is found in the Sigriflex® core (assuming adiabatic conditions and properties depending on temperature). One can note that the temperature peak calculated by Ansys ® is lower

than predicted by FLUKA analysis (see Section 4.3). This difference ($\sim 11\%$) is due to the relatively large dimensional resolution of the 3D FLUKA mapping imported in Ansys®. Nevertheless, the difference in total deposited energy is practically negligible.

Figure 63 - Temperature distribution on the dump after a beam impact at: a) $t = 86 \mu\text{s}$ and $t = 12 \text{ hrs}$.

Because of the high thermal gradient in the core, the energy is transferred from the core to the vessel, where it is extracted by convection and radiation. This phenomenon involves a slow temperature rise of the vessel up to a maximum temperature $T_{\text{max}} = 171^\circ\text{C}$ (at $t = 20 \text{ min}$.) and then it is followed by a progressive cooling down over several hours (see Figure 64). Note that, as expected, a faster heat transfer mechanism is found on the high density blocks due to the higher TCC provided by the shrink fitting.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 64 - Temperature distribution in the vessel (longitudinal vertical section) after a beam impact at: a) $t = 86 \mu s$, $t = 20 \text{ min}$. and $t = 12 \text{ hrs}$

Figure 65 shows the maximum and average temperature evolution of the vessel with time. The pattern of this curve is similar to the Nitrogen evolution curve observed during Run 2 operation (See Figure 171 in Section 9.4.3). Note that, Nitrogen temperature is driven by the temperature evolution of the internal surface of the vessel and external surface of the graphite. This change of temperature produces a pressure cycle representative of the temperature evolution.

Figure 65 - Temperature evolution of the vessel

The power dissipated against time due to convection and radiation is shown in Figure 66. Both mechanisms have the same order of magnitude. Even after 12 hrs, 19 % of the energy deposited on the dump remains still inside, which demonstrates the low efficiency of the current cooling/ventilation system. RUN2 and RUN3 are expected to be similar in terms of energy evolution in the TDE block with respect to deposited energy (see Figure 66b). This means that, although more energy is deposited in the TDE block for the RUN3 than for the RUN2, the thermal transfer phenomenon is more intense and the characteristic cool-down times (for a given percentage with respect to the total deposited energy) are similar. Nevertheless, the net stored energy in the TDE block for RUN3 at a given time is obviously higher than RUN2 because of the bigger amount of deposited energy. Note that results for long term simulation could be not very accurate due to several reasons: conservative and simplified assumptions, high non-linear behaviour, high sensitivity to convective/radiation parameters and the accumulation of time integration errors. Therefore, these results should be taken as qualitative.

Monitoring of the temperature on the vessel during operation would provide valuable information. This information could be used for crosschecking the simulations and provide more confidence in the numerical results, constraining some of the assumed parameters. Moreover, it could be used to set-up other future more accurate simulations and extrapolate for the design of the future HL-LHC dump. Installation of thermal sensors (PT100) is planned along the vessel and both windows. More details about the PT100 can be found in Section 9.1

(a)

(b)

Figure 66 - a) Power dissipated through the vessel via radiation and convection mechanisms for RUN 3. B) Relative extracted energy with respect to the total deposited energy in the TDE block over time.

5.6 REVIEW OF THE SLOW THERMAL EXPANSION OF THE DUMP.

The component responsible for the expansion of the dump block is the stainless steel vessel due to the relatively high thermal expansion coefficient and stiffness. As commented in the previous sections, due to the high temperature gradient in the core, the heat is transferred from the core to the vessel and then is extracted to the environment. This produces a slow cyclic expansion/shrinking process of the dump.

Temperature evolution of the dump is exported to a mechanical solver in order to analyse this phenomenon. Since it is a slow movement, a quasi-static implicit model based on linear elements is used. Bonded contact is assumed between the HD blocks and vessel whilst frictional contact is assumed for the LD core.

Gravity is assumed to play a minor role compared with the thermal forces. Nevertheless, gravity can produce a very slow swinging phenomenon due to the asymmetric expansion of the dump, it has therefore been included in the calculations.

Figure 67 shows the deformation of the dump at different time steps. After the beam impact, the dump expands longitudinally and is bent due to the non-axisymmetric distribution of the energy deposition. The bend pattern change as the energy is redistributed with time.

The longitudinal movement of the both extremities of the dump with time is plotted on Figure 68. The max. displacement of each extremity is 3.7 mm and 4.0 mm for the upstream and downstream ends, respectively. The pattern of movement is completely analogous to the movement observed on the interferometers.

Figure 67 - Total thermal deformation of the dump assuming a quasi-static movement at the time: a) $t=86e-6s$; b) $t=16.6$ min and c) $t=12hrs$.

Although the interferometer can capture the slow movement of the dump, it exhibits some limitation and it is more suitable for measuring fast short movements. A dedicated robust sensor system, based on LVDTs with large range of measurement, has been planned to be installed on the upstream window along 3 directions. More info can be found in Section 9.3.

Figure 68 - Longitudinal movement of the dump with time at the upstream and downstream ends. (Positive direction corresponds to direction of the beam)

5.7 FAST MOVEMENT BEHAVIOUR OF DUMP AND COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Although, most of the energy is deposited in the core (94.5%), a non-negligible amount is also stored in the vessel and windows (23.7 MJ). This energy is deposited in 86 μ s, which is the duration of the beam sweep. Because of the fast energy deposition, the entire dump is exposed to a violent and sudden thermal load, which produces a complex dynamic response of the dump itself, including wave propagations and rarefaction waves, where inertia plays an important role. This phenomenon is able to excite different natural frequencies of the entire dump.

Unlike the slow movement, the time scale of this phenomenon is in the order of milliseconds. The vibrations are attenuated with time due to Sommerfeld's radiation condition and dissipation mechanisms (internal material damping, friction, plasticity, etc.) and finally the entire dump tends towards a quasi-steady state. The slow movement starts from this state.

A dedicated numerical model has been developed for the analysis of this fast movement. This model allows us to estimate the dynamic load on the different components and their design as well as the identification of possible source of problems.

In the context of high dynamic and non-linear analysis, explicit numerical codes exhibit strong advantages in term of computational cost, time resolution and convergence. Ls Dyna explicit code is used [37]. Thermal and mechanical solvers are weakly coupled in the time domain.

In general, linear elements with full integration method is used. Each block in the core is modelled as a continuous material by solid elements (8 nodes). Although the vessel could be represented efficiently by shell elements, solid elements is also chosen. Several solid elements are set up through the thickness of the vessel. This configuration allows to

capture the energy/temperature gradient through it, which is needed to simulate the thermal bending of the vessel and the 3D stress state. Because the aspect ratio of these elements can be non-suitable, a special element formulation with reduce transverse shear locking is selected [38].

The steel rope introduced in the LS2 upgrades is modelled by unidimensional beam elements. LS-DYNA® offer a specific material for ropes (Mat_166). This formulation takes into account the non-linear elastic (and plastic) and asymmetric behaviour of the rope. Properties of the rope are taken from CASAR turbolift® $\phi 20\text{ mm}$ (DIEPA H40® wire rope, used in this application, has the same internal structure and construction, however it is not fully characterized).

Temperature-dependent properties of the materials can be found in 1.1.1.1A.3.

As will be explained in next Section 5.8, several models with different assumptions were analysed. Figure 69 shows the model considered for our calculation, corresponding to the as-built device. The main assumptions and boundary conditions can be summarised as follows:

- Friction contact between core and vessel: according to the literature, typical friction coefficient between graphite and st. steel is around 0.1. Nevertheless, in vacuum or N₂ environment this coefficient can be up to 1. We assume a value 0.5 and 0.35 for the static and dynamic coefficient, respectively.
- Shrink fitting between HD core and vessel is considered according to nominal interference of the drawing. The simulation of the shrink fitting follows the manufacturing process of the dump and does not produce unrealistic stresses.
- SIGRAFLEX® core is enclosed by two Sigrafine HLM disks, which are blocked by two metal rings (see picture). Frictional contact is applied between these parts (see Figure 69d).
- Preload of the structure due to the gravity is considered.
- Beam energy deposition is applied to the vessel, frame, ropes, supports and all the surrounding elements (not applied to the core).
- Ambient temperature = 22°C

The time step is set up to 90% with respect to the Courant number, i.e. $t=1.37*10^{-7}$ s. The end time of the simulation is 25 ms. No damping, except the intrinsic numerical one is considered.

Figure 69 – (a) Numerical model of the full dump including the frame and ropes (>1M elements). (b) and (c) details of the cradle and rope. (d) Detail of the core inside the vessel.

In order to gain confidence with the numerical model, the simulation has been cross-checked with the measurements of the interferometer at the upstream end of the dump (identified as the the "downstream" interferometer). For this comparison, the numerical model was adapted to the previous configuration of the dump, which is supported on two rigid supports and connected to the connecting line. The real measures of the intensity of the proton beam ($1.06 \cdot 10^{14}$ p at 6.5 TeV) were used for setting up the simulation. Figure 70 shows the longitudinal displacement as a function of time. Numerical and experimental results show good agreement. The difference of the main oscillation frequency is lower than 3% (see Figure 70b). An amplitude difference is noticeable between the experimental data and the numerical model: this is due to the fact that the reference point for the simulation and for the measurement are not exactly at the same location. The interferometer reads the movement of a plate, which is bolted on the downstream flange of the connecting line. The flexibility and inertia of this plate could be one of reasons for this difference.

(a)

(b)

Figure 70 - Comparison of the longitudinal displacement between numerical simulation and real measured date on 16-August-2018: a) on the time and b) frequency domain.

Figure 71 shows a series of plots of the dynamic behaviour of the full TDE for the nominal RUN-3 standard scenario ([Here](#) you can find a video). The clear advantage of this new support system (based on ropes) is that the dump can move freely as it is unconstrained. Moreover, the dump vibrations are well insulated with respect to the frame support thanks to the high flexibility of the rope. One should observe that the frame support exhibits an inherent thermal expansion due to the particle shower and energy deposition on it, which is uncoupled from the TDE block. This phenomenon has been considered and analysed during the design phase (see Section 8).

Figure 71 - Displacement [m] of the dump at different time steps ($t=1.25$ ms, $t=2.5$ ms and $t=11$ ms). Longitudinal expansion is dominant and the windows are strongly excited.

Figure 72 shows the movement at different points along the dump: upstream window, downstream window and central point. It can be observed that three main natural frequencies are apparently excited, which correspond with the longitudinal, the bending and breathing (radial) mode. The longitudinal mode has a higher contribution to the displacements, compared to the other modes (let us refer to it as dominant), and it violently shakes the windows (see Figure 71). This phenomenon will be studied more in

detail in a dedicated Section (See Section 5.9 for modal analysis and Section 6.4 and 7.4 for the movement of the windows).

Figure 72 - a) position of the measured points. b) Longitudinal and c) lateral movement of a point at the upstream, central and downstream side of the dump along the time during the fast movement.

Because of the asymmetric longitudinal expansion of the dump, a swinging phenomenon can be produced (see [video](#)). The entire dump, suspended by the two ropes, moves as a solid rigid body along the longitudinal direction by action of the gravity. According to simulations, the maximum amplitude of this oscillation is around 0.2 mm. The swinging was studied on a real mock-up. The dump was moved by 1 mm in the longitudinal direction. Movement was measured by a gauge. The oscillation was damped very fast and it was imperceptible after 1 s.

Vibrations are observed as well on the frame and cradle. These vibrations are induced due to the rapid heating induced by the particle showers induced by the beam impacting on the core. The lateral longitudinal bars expand with the temperature and push both cradles which support the dump. This phenomenon will be discussed in detail in Section 8.2.1.

Regarding the steel ropes, which are critical component for the new Upgrade, the present full model allows us study the dynamic force/deformation along the rope. Dynamic oscillations of the rope are found due to not only the energy deposition on it, but also due to the movement of the frame/cradle and the breathing vibration mode of the dump itself. Actually, this last one seems to be the dominant behaviour. Section 8.2.1.3 will provide extensive details.

5.8 SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Several simplification and assumptions were assumed in the present simulations in order to reduce the complexity of the problem and make it feasible in term of computational cost. The impact of these assumptions on the results is not known a priori. The aim of this study is to assess the influence of different boundary conditions/assumptions. This analysis is focused on following ones:

- Gravity. Differences on the dump behaviour considering or not gravity.
- Pre-stress of the vessel-core (shrink-fitting) and friction coefficients. There are some uncertainties about the friction coefficient between graphite materials and stainless steel in N₂ environment.
- Energy deposition. Difference in the dump behaviour applying the energy deposition on vessel and core and only on the vessel.

The results are summarised in Table 17. As observed, the fast movement of the dump is dominated by the expansion of the vessel. Gravity exhibits a low influence on the general behaviour of the dump. Nevertheless, it is important to take it into account in order to reliably assess the stress on the rope and cradle. The shrink fitting of the HD core should be considered to compute the stress on the vessel and fatigue phenomenon, but the friction coefficient seems to have a low influence on the results. Therefore, all dynamic analysis performed along this document, at least other consideration was specified, includes the shrink fitting of the core-vessel (FC=0.5) and gravity in order to assess the stress levels on the different components of the TDE system.

Table 17: Sensitivity analysis on the behaviour of the dump for different boundary conditions/assumptions. ** Friction coefficient: this value is not well known.

Model		Difference*	Comments
Gravity	with/without	< 0.3%	
Shrink fitting HD core-vessel	FC**=0.1	10%	With respect to perfect bonded contact (lower displacements but same behaviour)
	FC=0.5	<1%	With respect to previous model FC=0.1
	FC=1	<1%	With respect to previous model FC=0.5
Energy deposition	vessel/ vessel+core	<1%	Apply only on the vessel/ apply on vessel + core

5.9 MODAL ANALYSIS AND COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION

An experimental modal characterization has been carried out on the Run 3 dump configuration. This method determines some useful dynamic characteristic of the structure such as: natural frequencies, damping and modes. This characterization was required to assess several points:

- Pre-characterization of the dump system before operation. Movements of the dump are driven mainly for the modal modes. Modal characterization allows to assess the behaviour of the dump.
- Extraction of damping ratio. Vibration period can be estimated based on the damping. Damping ratio is critical for fatigue analysis.
- Cross-check of numerical simulation.

Three accelerometers were installed along the dump: upstream, central section and downstream. The dump block was excited using a calibrated hammer. 38 points of impact were selected along the dump in order to excite different modes. The accelerometer signals were acquired and post-processed by a special specific Software ME'Scope VES. The system was calibrated to capture frequencies up to 200 Hz. A special set-up was used for measuring high frequencies around 2 kHz. More details about the modal characterization can be found in Ref. [39].

Figure 73 - Set-up of the modal characterization of the dump. Picture extract from report [39].

Table 18 summarises the results of the modal test. The table includes a comparison between simulation and experimental test results. It is worth noticing the good agreement between them, especially for the dynamic simulations.

Complex modal analysis was computed on the dump. This technique estimates the relative relevance of the modes and it showed that the longitudinal and 1st bending mode are the dominant ones. This finding is fully coherent with the dynamic simulations.

Table 18 - Experimental and numerical modal characterization of the dump

Simulation [Hz]		Measurement [Hz]	Diff [%]	Mode shape	Damping [%]
Linear Modal analysis	Dynamic analysis				(respect to critical)
32.0		27	18.5%	1st vertical bending	0.20%
36.9	35.4	37	0.3%	1st horizontal bending	0.20%
95.3		102	6.6%	Horizontal bending	4.20%
125.1		134	6.6%	Vertical bending	1.70%
172.3		183	5.8%	Horizontal bending	1.40%
174.4	199.4	197	1.2%	Longitudinal	1.80%
186.4		205	9.1%	Vertical bending	0.30%
-	2353	2360	0.3%	Breathing	0.20%

Type: Total Deformation
Frequency: 32.034 Hz
Unit: mm
17/07/2020 11:31

Type: Total Deformation
Frequency: 36.909 Hz
Unit: mm
17/07/2020 11:30

Type: Total Deformation
Frequency: 174.44 Hz
Unit: mm
17/07/2020 11:39

Figure 74 - Numerical modal shape for (a) and b) first two bending, c) longitudinal and d) breathing modes. Last mode has been extracted directly from the dynamic simulation.

5.10 FATIGUE ASPECTS FOR THE VESSEL

Because of the fast movements of the dump, the dump itself and all the components are exposed to strong vibrations. This phenomenon should be taken into account for the estimation of the fatigue life. This section is focused on the vessel. Other components will be treated in the following sections.

The shrink fitting of the core into the vessel already produces a high initial stress on the vessel (see Figure 75). After the beam impact, the vessel expands longitudinally and radially exhibiting both modes at different natural frequencies at 200 Hz and 2.3 kHz, respectively (see Figure 76). As results the vessel exhibits a multiaxial stress state.

Figure 75 - Static stress on the vessel mainly due to gravity and shrink fitting of the core.

Regarding multiaxial fatigue, a wide variety of criteria and models can be found in the literature. Each model has been proposed for a particular purpose and/or condition. A valuable review of different methods can be found in [40]. Nevertheless, there is not a common consensus on this subject, and there are still some doubts as to which method should be used.

Figure 76 - Von Mises stress compute on two points on the vessel: corresponding with the position of the SIGRAFLEX® core and 2nd HD block.

Based on the literature review, multiaxial fatigue criteria could be roughly classified in four categories:

- Stress based models: Applicable for High Cycle Fatigue (HCF) where plastic deformation is negligible. See Sines, Crossland and modified Dang Van criteria [41] [42] [43]
- Strain-based models: Used for both Applicable for High Cycle Fatigue (HCL) and Applicable for High Cycle Fatigue (LCF) conditions. This method is non-applicable for non-proportional loadings cases (see Brown and Miller [44]).
- Energy approach: Fatigue damage is initialized and driven by continuous accumulation of plastic strain energy. (see [45])
- Critical plane models: The fatigue is initialized and dominated for a critical plane usually related to the maximum shear. These models are used commonly for non-proportional loading. Nevertheless, this is computationally intensive and requires of many fatigue properties. Used for HCL. See Fatemi-Socie, Dang-Van [46] [43]

The loading type, proportional or non-proportional, is important to select the criteria. Moreover, in most of the cases the amplitude is variable and it changes with time. Linear cumulative rules based on Rainflow decomposition and Miner's rule [47] are usually applied. More advanced models based on continuum damage mechanics have been as well proposed [48], but it is out of this scope.

In the framework of this study, a dedicated python code was developed for the assessment of the multiaxial fatigue. This code includes several criteria: Sines, Crossland, Dang Van, Fatemi-Socie. The approach is based on computer aided analysis where the stress and strain history inputs are obtained via FEM, such that these variables as well as the mesh are imported into the Python code. The code post-processes the information and generates a new fatigue output for all the nodes/elements. Two methods have been implemented:

- Variable amplitude: Cumulative linear damage based on Miner's and Rainflow analysis. Output: amount of damage.

- Constant amplitude: The code looks for worst cycle along the history it returns the number of cycles up to failure and equivalent amplitude fatigue stress.

Table 19 summarises fatigue information on Duplex 2205 (Uranus 45) and reference. Note that because of the lack of data, some extrapolations need to be done based on literature/authors' proposals. In general, Basquin-Manoson-Coffin equations are assumed:

$$\epsilon_{eq} = \frac{\sigma'_f}{E} (2Nf)^b + \epsilon'_f (2Nf)^c \quad \text{For strain life fatigue}$$

$$\sigma_{eq} = \sigma'_f (2Nf)^b \quad \text{For stress life fatigue}$$

where $2Nf$ is the number of reversal cycles, σ'_f is the fatigue strength coefficient, b is the fatigue strength exponent, E is the elastic modulus, ϵ'_f is the fatigue ductility and c is the fatigue ductility exponent.

Table 19 - Fatigue properties for Uranus 45. Note: * Estimated from bending test according to literature.

Test	Coefficients	Endurance limit (at 1e7 cycles)	Reference
Bending stress (R-1)	$\sigma'_f = 1835 \text{ Mpa}, b = -0.12$	265 Mpa	[49]
Axial stress (R=-1)	$\sigma'_f = 696 \text{ Mpa}, b = -0.03$	411 Mpa	[50]
Axial stress (R=-1)	$\sigma'_f = 1330 \text{ Mpa}, b = -0.09$	311 Mpa	[51]
Axial Strain (R=-1)	$\sigma'_f = 924 \text{ Mpa}, b = -0.049, \epsilon'_f = 0.086, c = -0.4381$	0.21%	[50]
Torsional stress (R=-1)*	$\tau'_f = 1060 \text{ Mpa}, b = -0.12$	153	[52]

From a conservative point of view, a constant amplitude fatigue analysis is considered in this study. The number of cycles per each beam dump is computed based on the modal characterization, and particularly on the minimum damping ratio (0.2%). Assuming an 80% of attenuation of the oscillations, 123 cycles/beam dump is considered. Several criteria are evaluated in order to estimate the possible uncertainty. Because there is no data beyond 10^7 cycles, the maximum number of cycles is limited to that value. Table 20 shows the results.

Table 20: Fatigue assessment for different criteria assuming the worst cycle along the load history.

Criteria	Min. # cycles to the failure	Max Eq stress/strain	# dumps
Crossland	5.20E+06	Eq Stress= 165 Mpa	4.06E+04
Sines	5.22E+06	Eq Stress = 166 MPa	4.08E+04
Modified Dang Van	1.11E+05	Eq. Stress =260 Mpa	8.67E+02
Fatemi-Socie	1.00E+07	Max. Shear= 0.13%, Normal Stress= 170 Mpa	7.81E+04

As observed, all the criteria provide similar results in term of number of cycles, except the modified Dang Van criteria (based on stresses). This last one penalised more strongly the hydrostatic component and it is based on the Von-Mises equivalent stress, unlike other stress criteria, which use the deviatoric stress tensor. Because the load is out-phase, Fatemi-Socie criteria should be the most reliable/suitable. Figure 77 and Figure 78 show the results for Crossland and Fatemi-Socie, respectively.

In conclusion, according to different fatigue criteria and in particular to Fatemi-Socie's one, no fatigue issue should be expected for the vessel. Nevertheless, this calculation does not consider the welds of the different sections of vessel, which could be a weak point (this particular analysis is outside the scope of this work).

(a)

(b)

Figure 77 - Assessment of the Crossland criteria: a) Number of cycles up to failure and b) Equivalent fatigue stress.

(a)

Figure 78 - Assessment of the Fatemi-Socie criteria: a) Number of cycles up to failure and b) shear strain on critical plane and c) normal stress on critical plane.

5.11 SUMMARY

In this section, the thermo-mechanical behaviour of the TDE exposed to the beam impact has been analysed with the aim of finding some clues regarding the past issues during RUN2 and getting a better understanding and providing a solid support for the present upgrading.

Two different responses of the TDE block have been identified: a fast response and slow response.

The fast movement is related to the suddenly energy deposition in the TDE block, which induces a violent thermal-expansion. Vibrations are in the order of $\sim 1000g$ and excite several natural modes of the TDE. Although these vibrations are expected to be dissipated in the first seconds, it can produce high reaction forces when the TDE movement is constrained (as it was during RUN2, where the TDE was connected to the connection line). Actually, the source of the most of the issues observed during RUN2 are likely to be derived from these vibrations.

Concerning the slow movement, it is produced by a quasi-static thermal expansion of the TDE. After the beam impact, the energy deposited in the TDE diffuses slowly from the core to the vessel and then it is extracted by convection and radiation to the ambient/surroundings. This phenomenon involves a change of the temperature distribution along the time and a slow thermal movement of the entire TDE block. This response is likely to be responsible of the observed permanent displacement of the TDE during RUN2.

Numerical calculations have been crosschecked with experimental measurements and they exhibit a good agreement (which provides reasonable confidence). As shown in this

document, and based on this analysis, the present upgrade is focused on reducing the effect/consequences of these vibrations by setting the TDE free from the connection line, and also on reducing permanent displacements.

Moreover, the TDE has been dynamically characterised (modal characterization) experimental and numerically. This characterization can be set as a reference point previous to operation. The evolution of the behaviour of the TDE can be tracked via the instrumentation system, which can provide a valuable information during operation.

6. DUMP UPSTREAM WINDOW: DESIGN & FINITE ELEMENT ASSESSMENT

6.1 INTRODUCTION

The main function of the TDE windows is to provide a robust closure at the extremities of the stainless steel TDE vessel to contain the internal nitrogen atmosphere while withstanding the beam-induced thermomechanical and dynamic loads.

In view of the beam-induced dump vibrations described in section 5.7 and subsequent undesired dump displacements, it was decided to completely disconnect the dump's vessel from the vacuum beam line. This change involves the replacement of the previous upstream window, placed between the vacuum line and the N₂ line reservoir, by two new independent windows. One of these windows is placed at the end of the vacuum line - separating the vacuum from the atmosphere - and we refer to it as the Upstream Vacuum Window (UHV_W). The second window is placed upstream the TDE vessel - separating the atmosphere from the N₂- and we refer to it as TDE Dump Upstream Window (DUS_W).

Information about the original vacuum-nitrogen windows can be found in references [53] [14] [25]. This window consisted of 15 mm thick CfC plate together with a 0.2 mm stainless steel foil and such design was not suitable for the new DUS_W since, among other reasons, the DUS_W has to provide tightness when submitted to bidirectional loads. This requirement comes from the fact that the interior of the TDE vessel is subjected to vacuum before injecting nitrogen until reaching an over atmospheric pressure of 0.2 bars. The current section is devoted to the description of only the new DUS_W. Information about the new UHV_W (also to be replaced in order to be compliant with Run 3 beam parameters) is not within the scope of this document.

6.2 REQUIREMENTS OF THE DUS_W

The new DUS_W must fulfil the following requirements, which can be classified in two types; (i) To withstand the different operational loads. (ii) To be compatible with the TDE vessel interface and integration requirements.

6.2.1 Operational loads induced in the DUS_W

The new DUS_W must withstand three different types of loads, which take place in different time regimes and are induced by various operational aspects:

- 1) Withstand the thermal stresses directly induced by the deposition of energy of the beam during each beam dump. This deposition of energy takes place in $\sim 85 \mu\text{s}$ consistently with the sweeping path arising from the beam dilution system (described in Section 3). The window must withstand not only the nominal operation path, but any likely impacting path arising from the dilution kickers failure scenarios introduced in Section 3.3.
- 2) Withstand the load induced by the N_2 atmosphere at 0.15-0.16 bars of over-pressure inside the TDE vessel, as well as the one induced by the internal vacuum before the nitrogen filling procedure. In this report we consider, in any case 0.2 bars as design internal pressure.
- 3) Withstand the mechanical loads arising from the TDE longitudinal vibrations induced by the energy deposition of the beam shower in the vessel (estimated at 200 Hz). This phenomenon is described in detail in section 5.7. This dynamic load, coming from the vessel, will induce additional vibrations in the window. It will take place in a time scale from 5 ms up to 250 ms, depending on the damping time of the vibrations. For this reason, the natural frequency of vibrations of the window shall be far from 200 Hz, so any possible resonance phenomena is prevented.

The compliance of the new window design with the above loads for Run 3 operation is described in detail in the section 6.2. In addition, a fatigue analysis to ensure the compliance of the design during the operational life is provided in section 6.5.

6.2.2 TDE vessel interface and integration requirements

The new DUS_W shall be compatible with:

- 1) TDE vessel flange: This flange, at the vessel's side, remains the same as in the previous configuration. The method of connection of the window shall be then through a KF-flange and a clamping chain. Previous issues related to N_2 leaks during Run 2 operation (most probably induced by seal displacements consequence of the vessel's vibration) shall be minimized. Previous reports assessing this issue and proposals of an exchange of the types of seals can be found in refs. [54] [55] [56].
- 2) Integrate a N_2 pipe connector DN25: This requirement comes from the fact that the N_2 connector in the previous configuration was present in the N_2 reservoir, which is currently removed. Therefore, the only option to include this connection without modifying the dump's vessel is through the new window. The connector shall be integrated in such a way that no additional mechanical load is induced in the window because of its inertia contribution during the dump vibrations.
- 3) Integrate TDE instrumentation: The new installed dumps will be instrumented, including its windows, as described in section 9. Therefore, the design shall be compatible with the integration of the following instrumentation:
 - a. Strain gauges (x3)
 - b. PT100s (x1)
 - c. LVDT (x3)
 - d. A flat surface of at least 4x4 mm to which the LDV will point at.

6.3 DESIGN DESCRIPTION OF THE UPSTREAM WINDOW

6.3.1 Geometry of the Upstream Window (DUS_W)

Figure 79 shows the front and transversal view of the new DUS_W. The official drawing number is LHCTDE__0067 and its Smart-team Catia-3D model is ST1235195.

As can be seen in the Figure 79 (a), the nitrogen connection is integrated in the front face. A DN-25 flange is bolted directly into the window by 6x M5 screws. This front-face attachment solution was selected after several design iterations. Simulations showed that a perpendicular attachment through a radial side would lead to unacceptable stresses due to the inertia of the pipe during the dump longitudinal vibrations.

As can be seen Figure 79 (b), the window has a variable thickness. At the central zones, the selected thickness is 10 mm. This is the thickness that is directly impacted by the proton beam. On the other hand, close to the radially external zones, the thickness is increased up to 39.7 mm. This zone of increased thickness – placed at a distance from the beam path of at least 20 mm – is added to insert the N₂ connector and to bolt instrumentation accessories. Furthermore, this increased thickness is very important to provide additional stiffness to the window, to avoid resonant frequencies of the dump longitudinal vibration, and to minimize the induced dynamic stresses. Finally, a very large transition radius is added between the different thicknesses to minimize as well the dynamic stresses. More details on the calculated beam impacting paths on the front surface and dynamic response on the windows are shown in section 6.4.1.

Figure 79 - (a) Front view of the new TDE upstream window. (b) Detail of a cross-section of the window. Official drawing LHCTDE__0067. Smart-team no ST1235195.

6.3.2 Titanium Alloy and Manufacturing Process

The titanium alloy Grade 5 - also known as Ti-6Al-4V is selected as material for the DUS_W. This alloy combines low density (necessary to minimize the beam deposited energy) with exceptionally high yield strength even at high temperatures.

The geometry of the window is machined at CERN by CNC out of a multidirectional forged disk of 690 mm in diameter by 50 mm thickness. This raw material was manufactured by the company IMBACH & CIE AG. according to SAE AMS 4928 W. This material was subjected to ultrasonic inspections according to EN 10228-4. In addition, mechanical tests of representative material were carried out according to EN ISO 6892, showing a yield and ultimate strength of 935 and 986 MPa respectively, with associated longitudinal and transversal strain to rupture of 14% and 39%. These values are above the indication of the norm. Figure 80 shows results of such mechanical testing as well as a picture during the CNC machining at CERN’s main workshop.

EN ISO 6892-1

Probenbezeichnung Specimen designation	Probenlage Spec. location	Abmessungen Dimensions [mm]		m _E	R _{eH}	R _{p0.2}	R _{p1.0}	R _m	A ₅	A _{50mm}	A ₄	Z
						N/mm ²		N/mm ²	%			%
		<input type="checkbox"/> d ₀	Min.			862		931	10			25
Soil Nominal value:	T	<input type="checkbox"/> a*b	L ₀ Max.									
C741	T	10	50			935		986	14.3			39

Figure 80 - Table of results of mechanical testing from the supplier as well as a picture during the CNC machining at CERN’s main workshop.

6.3.3 Attachment to the Dump and Sealing Solution

The method to attach the window to the dump block had to be changed from the approach used during Run 2. Previously a metallic Helicoflex® seal was used. However, this method led to numerous leaks and was demonstrated not to be reliable. More information about the system used during Run 2, the leaks, and the failure modes can be found in references [54] [55] [56].

In the new design, the interface on the dump block side will remain unchanged. The new DUS_W window will have a similar interface compared to the old nitrogen reservoir, so that the same chain clamp can be used. The seal will be changed to an O-ring seal, made of EPDM.

Additionally, a small O-ring will be placed in the DN25 connection used to supply the nitrogen.

Figure 81 - Sections through dump upstream window taken from the TDE assembly drawing. Left view shows the whole window mounted on the upstream end of the dump. Right view shows detail of the O-ring and groove (Note that the O-ring is shown at its nominal major diameter and nominal cross section in the drawing; this makes it appear out of position because the O-ring major diameter is slightly smaller than the groove diameter so that the O-ring is under a slight tension when fitted to the groove to aid installation)

The following operational conditions were taken into account for the selection of the O-rings:

- Pressure differential: the dump will be put under a rough vacuum, and later filled with nitrogen at an overpressure of 0.2 bar.
- Temperature: the temperature in the hours after a beam dump will increase as the heat dissipates from the core into the vessel. More information can be found in section 5.5.
- Sizing: regarding the "big" O-ring, the groove in the dump side was not initially designed to hold an O-ring. For this reason, a slightly smaller diameter of O-ring was selected (ID 628.5X4 mm), and the fitting was tested on a prototype. The fitting of the O-ring is possible if a small amount of vacuum grease is applied to it first (Dow Corning® High-Vacuum Grease [57]). The size of the DN25 connection O-ring was selected based on the manufacturer's recommendation and the standard ISO 3601.
- Radiation: The total dose in the O-ring for 8 years of operation is estimated to be 0.24 MGy. This estimation is based on the FLUKA simulations reported in section 4.9, which conservatively consider that the 400 dumps per year (reported in Table 1) are at the maximum intensity, $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

Nord-Lock washers will be added to the chain clamp, in order to avoid them loosening with the vibrations. The torque on the chain clamp was chosen to i) achieve metal to metal contact, fully compressing the O-ring and ii) create the necessary conditions for the Nord-Lock washer to work properly. In order to fully compress the O-ring, a torque below 100

Nm was enough, based on empirical tests. In order for the Nord-Lock washers to work properly, a torque of 300 Nm was needed, as advised by the supplier. This torque was selected taking into account the use of Molykote D-321R® [58] as lubricant on the threads. More details and parameters of the final installation can be found in the EDMS report [59].

Note that, as shown in Figure 81, and following the inheritance of the previous window design, there is a groove between the window itself and the TDE flange. The aim of this grooves attends to easy the installation of the seals. After a series of experimental tests and some FEM analysis, it was observed an unwanted pre-bending phenomenon of the window during the clamping, which may introduce some pre-stress. This phenomenon is avoided by inserting a “washer”.

6.3.3.1 Selection of a radiation resistant O-ring material

At the dose levels cumulated in operation, radiation-induced effects can induce relevant modifications of the O-ring mechanical properties. Depending on the synergic action of several ageing factors (radiation, oxygen diffusion, thermomechanical stress...) the O-ring can become harder or softer, possibly experiencing structural failure (as fragmentation) or functional failure (leak) [60].

To minimize the risk of radiation-induced O-ring failure, a radiation tolerant commercial material is required. EPDM is generally known to be more radiation resistant than VITON. However, large differences in the radiation tolerance of different EPDM-based commercial products are reported [60] [61]. Specific radiation resistant products need to be identified and experimentally tested.

James Walker^{Co.} is one of the very few manufacturers producing radiation resistant O-rings materials. In particular, its *Shieldseal 663*® is an EPDM-based material declared by the producer as radiation resistant up to 1.6 MGy of gamma radiation, after irradiation and test [62]. *Shieldseal 663*® has been irradiated in a mixed neutron and gamma radiation field [61], demonstrating a satisfactory radiation resistance in comparison with other commercial EPDMs. Moderate damage is reported at 0.7 MGy, severe damage at 1.5 MGy [60]. *Shieldseal 663*® is therefore selected for these applications.

James Walker^{Co.} also provided proposals for the dimensions of the smaller O-ring and for its groove (see Figure 82) and produced the O-rings in custom dimension for both O-rings.

As already introduced, the large O-rings were installed using a fine layer of Dow Corning® High-Vacuum Grease [57] at 8 points around the circumference so that they did not fall out of the groove during assembly. Installation trials with EPDM O-rings on a mock-up of the upstream window indicated that it was not possible to reliably install the upstream window without applying such grease.

The compatibility of *Shieldseal 663* with greases was therefore discussed with the seal producer. *Shieldseal 663* is claimed to be compatible with silicone based greases, while the use of hydrocarbon lubricants must be avoided. Dow Corning® High-Vacuum Grease is a silicon based grease.

EDMS [63] provides an estimate of radiation damage to Dow Corning® High-Vacuum Grease in this application, as well as arguments why a small quantity of this product is not expected to compromise seal functionality.

Figure 82 - Proposal for O-ring dimensions and groove from James Walker^{Co.} for the N₂ connector in the upstream window.

6.4 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF THE UPSTREAM WINDOW UNDER OPERATIONAL LOADS

The dump windows are subjected to three types of loads: (i) Beam induced thermo-mechanical response, (ii) Vacuum/N₂ pressure differentials, (iii) Dynamic load induced by the vibration of the dump vessel.

6.4.1 Beam Induced Thermomechanical Response

The interaction of the proton beam with the material of the window leads to a fast deposition of energy and the subsequent temperature rise and thermo-mechanical stresses. This deposition takes place in approximately 85 μs, which is the duration of the beam dilution path. Such path is composed by the impact of 2748 proton bunches, leading to a single bunch impact duration of 30 ns (including the bunch-to-bunch temporal spacing). The maximum estimated rise of temperature per bunch – which 1σ radius at windows location is around 1 mm - is in the order of 4.2 °C (considering 1.8·10¹¹ ppb). This peak takes place at the downstream part of the 10 mm thickness window as shown in Figure 83. Nevertheless, the superposition of locations of consecutive bunch impacts leads to much higher effective temperature rises, in the order of 100 °C for some failure scenarios as shown in detail in Table 22.

Figure 83 - Temperature rise per bunch (from RT) long the 10 mm thickness of the upstream window.

The calculation of the real induced temperatures and peak of stresses requires a simulation considering the whole impact of the dilution-path and its time structure, since stress waves will appear due to the fast energy deposition. This calculation is provided in the next subsection.

6.4.1.1 Calculation of beam induced stress waves on the window

The explicit FE code LS-DYNA® has been used to for this type of simulations. The computational procedure is the same as the one previously applied and described in [14]. This procedure uses a Python script to create a set of time-dependant internal energy load curves, one per each relevant element of the FE mesh. This script uses as input:

- i. The energy deposition map in the 10 mm thick window for a single bunch estimated by FLUKA.
- ii. A table with the location and time of impact of each bunch onto the window, consistent with the beam dilution structure. This table is provided by TE-ABT. A different table is provided for each beam dilution scenario in order to consider, in addition to the nominal path, other potential dilution failures which change the beam impacting path.

The different beam dilution paths considered for the upstream windows are summarized in Figure 84. The failure scenarios have been selected based on event likelihood as well as criticality in terms of build-up of energy deposition in a particular location due to bunch impact superposition of the distorted dilution path. The simulation of each beam dilution scenario requires the implementation of a different computational model since the mesh must be refined according to the dilution path to ensure a correct energy interpolation. The selected mesh size along the dilution path is 0.25 mm.

Figure 84 - Summary of the beam dilution path scenarios considered in the analysis of the upstream window.

The selected LS-DYNA® solver is thermal-structurally coupled, i.e., in a single simulation the temperature and stresses are calculated using as input the internal heat deposited in the window. The thermal solver uses an implicit time integration scheme (with time steps in the order of 20 ns) while the structural is explicit (with time steps imposed by the Courant condition and the min mesh size of 0.25 mm). The considered simulation time is 150 μs.

Figure 85 - LS-DYNA® contour plots of temperature (left) and Von Mises stresses (right) for the dilution failure scenario “flashover” at 89 μs after the start of the beam impact.

Figure 85 shows the contour plots for the temperature (left) and Von Mises equivalent stress (right) obtained by such analysis at 89 μs after the start of pulse impact for the dilution failure scenario “flashover”, which is the worst failure scenario considered.

As shown by the left image, the maximum temperature rise for such Run 3 scenario ($1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb) is in the order 113 °C, and takes place at a position where, due to the distorted dilution path, the trajectory of the beam is superimposed with itself. The image on the right shows the Von Mises stress at this time. A maximum stress of 74 MPa is

reached in the same location as the maximum temperature. In addition, the image shows the stress wave propagation fronts following the dilution path, with an amplitude in the order of 20 MPa. The maximum stress reached obtained from this sort of analysis takes into account, in addition to the inertia effects, the potential constructive interference of such stress waves fronts. The row 2 for Table 22 summarizes the results for the nominal dilution path and all the considered dilution failure scenarios.

6.4.1.2 Quasi-static stress induced by the beam impact

Observing the stress contour image of Figure 85-right, it is easy to see that residual stresses in the order of 40 MPa remain along the dilution path after the beam impact. This is a consequence of the temperature gradient that remains along the path until the heat diffusion relax such gradient (taking place in the order of tens of milliseconds). This residual stress, which corresponds to the quasi-static component of the thermal load, is relevant since it is the one that will remain when the dynamic loading of the window, consequence of the dump's vibrations, takes place (analysed in detail in section 6.4.3). For this reason, a quasi-static structural analysis has been executed considering the static thermal state arising from the interaction of the full beam dilution path with the window. Figure 86 shows a detail of the stresses appearing from such analysis for the nominal case and the "flashover" failure. In such models, only the geometry close to the beam path has been implemented. The expansion on the boundaries of such region has been constrained. This is a conservative boundary condition with respect the reality, in which the surrounding material could deform. The maximum quasi-static stress of the nominal beam is 36 MPa and 66 MPa for the "flashover" failure scenario.

Figure 86 - Contour plots of the quasi-static Von Mises stresses (Pa) as a consequence of the thermal gradients in some specific zones of the dilution path for the nominal scenario (left) and "flashover" scenario (right).

This analysis is substantially faster and simpler than the dynamic one shown in the previous section. Results of this analysis are summarized in row 3 of Table 22. It is interesting to remark that the ratio between the maximum dynamic and quasi-static stress is in the order of 1.83. This ratio could be used if future case studies of new dilution failure path are required. A simple quasi-static analysis and posterior multiplication of such factor could be a good approximation to obtain the dynamic stresses while significantly reducing the complexity of performing LS-DYNA® analysis for each failure scenario.

6.4.2 Structural analysis vacuum/N₂ pressure loads

Figure 87 shows the results of an axisymmetric structural analysis considering a simplified geometry of the 10 mm thickness window for the pressure loads from vacuum and the 0.2 bars of N₂ overpressure, respectively. Maximum stress for the first case (only present when the dump vessel is subjected to vacuum prior to N₂ filling) is 60 MPa. This maximum stress takes place close to the sealing surface. Maximum displacement is 1.3 mm.

The right figure shows the results when considering the 0.2 bars overpressure of the N₂. Maximum deformation in this structure is 0.26 mm. Maximum Von Mises stress at the central regions (in which the beam will pass through) is 10 MPa. The 0.2 bars overpressure is the one considered in the design, nevertheless, the real overpressure in the dumps at room temperature is in the order of 0.15-0.16 bars, as can be seen by the pressure sensor readings 'VGMA.629594.R.PR' (UD62) and 'VGMA.689594.B.PR' (UD68). Rough estimations suggest that, after a dump at $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb, this overpressure could reach up to 0.3 bars due to the increase of temperature of the N₂. This is not considered an issue in any case, since simulations show that even with an overpressure of 0.5 bars, the maximum Von Mises stress at the central regions of the window would be only 22 MPa.

Figure 87 - Contour plots of the stresses and deformation induced in the upstream window as consequence of vacuum (left) and N₂ overpressure (right) loads.

6.4.3 Dynamic Load Induced by the Vibration of the Dump's Vessel

As explained in section 5.7, the excitation of a longitudinal mode of vibration induced by the deposition of energy of the beam shower in the vessel imposes high velocity displacements on the contact surface between the windows and the vessel. Such displacement will propagate to the window's face, inducing a "membrane-shape" vibration with its subsequent deformation and dynamic stresses. In order to evaluate the compliance of the upstream window design to such loads, a sub-modelling approach has been applied. This approach consists in performing transient structural simulations by applying the velocity field from the windows contact flange obtained from the dynamic

simulations of the whole vessel vibrations calculated section 5.7. Figure 88 illustrates this approach, including the velocity field applied and its oscillatory nature corresponding to the longitudinal mode of vibration of the dump. The dominant period of the velocity load is around 5 ms, matching the 197 Hz vibration frequency corresponding to such longitudinal mode. The maximum reached velocity at such contact is proportional to the energy deposition in the vessel and hence the impacted intensity. For the case of study ($1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb), the maximum applied velocity at the upstream flange is 2.25 m/s.

Figure 88 - Schematics showing the velocity profile applied at the contact face between the upstream window and the dump's vessel.

It is important that the natural vibration frequencies of the window are far from the 197 Hz frequency to avoid resonances. The geometry of the upstream window has been selected seeking this purpose. A model analysis showed that the 1st vibrating frequency is 430 Hz. This value considers a potential mass of the N₂ connection line, assumed to be up to 1 kg. This mass is also considered in the dynamic simulations.

The dynamic simulations performed consider the thermal gradients induced by the beam impact. Because this gradient remains almost constant during the vibrations (i.e. 15 ms), an initial quasi-static structural step without time integration is applied. In this way, the remaining thermal stresses are already present during the vibration induced dynamic response.

Figure 89-left shows that the expected maximum Von Mises stress reached in the centre of the window are in the order of 110 MPa. This maximum is reached 2.8 ms after the beam impact. The second critical region is the connection radius with the thicker part of the windows, where the stresses are also in the same order of magnitude. Figure 89-right shows the associated displacement of the centre of the window as a function of time. The centre of the windows moves up to 4.8 mm towards the upstream as consequence of this vibration.

It is worth noting that stresses associated to this dynamic load are the highest ones in the window, substantially higher than the ones directly induced by the beam. This type of load, not considered in previous design studies of the dump, is found to be the dominant one in the fatigue analysis of section 6.5. The goal of the strain gauges attached to some position of the windows (described in section 9.2.1.1) is to measure and characterize these vibrations and loads, with its corresponding damping times, so the life times are properly set.

Figure 89 - Left- Contour plots of Von Mises stresses (Pa) at 2.8 ms, when the maximum is reached. Right: Displacement of the centre of the window over 14 ms.

6.5 FATIGUE ANALYSIS OF THE UPSTREAM WINDOW

In order to characterize the fatigue lifetime of the window, the same procedure and scripts as the ones described in section 5.10 have been applied.

This procedure consists in a multi-axial analysis based on Crossland criteria. This method is applied to all the points/nodes of the window for the worst cycle in the time history.

In order to apply such script, the fatigue material data for Ti-Gr 5 for torsion and flexural loading is required. Most of this data is not available in the literature at high temperature. For this reason, it has been extrapolated to high temperatures by scaling it with respect to the temperature dependent fatigue data found for axial loading in ref. [64]. In addition, the N-S curve for axial loading from ref. [65] instead of flexural has been applied (which is conservative).

Curves from Ti-Gr 5 in axial loading at 20 °C and 300 °C have been obtained from Majidi et al. in ref [64]. Analysing these curves, gives an estimated a ratio of 0.79 between the fatigue strength at 20 °C and 300 °C. This ratio is applied to the axial and torsion fatigue parameters obtained from F. Berto et al. in ref. [65]. Table 21 shows the employed data fitted values according to the inverse logarithmic relation for the fatigue strength as a function of number of cycles (N); $\sigma_{fatigue\ Strength} = \sigma_f N^b$.

Table 21 - Values assumed for the fatigue analysis of the window, obtained from extrapolating values at room temperature From ref. [65], scaled down to 300 °C using ref. [64]

Test	Coefficients	Endurance limit (at 2e6 cycles)
<i>Fatigue Curve data at Room Temperature obtained from data fitting of ref. [65]</i>		
Axial stress (R=-1)	$\sigma_f = 2213 \text{ MPa}, b = -0.109$	471 MPa
Torsional stress (R=-1)	$\tau_f = 722 \text{ MPa}, b = -0.0411$	398 MPa
<i>Fatigue Curve data at 300 °C used in the analysis, obtained from scaling down data of ref. [65] by a 0.79 ratio according to RT vs 300 °C comparison of ref. [64]</i>		
Axial stress (R=-1)	$\sigma_f = 1748 \text{ MPa}, b = -0.109$	373 MPa
Torsional stress (R=-1)	$\tau_f = 570 \text{ MPa}, b = -0.0411$	314 MPa

The following analysis conservatively assumes that the Ti-Gr 5 in the windows is at 300 °C, which is certainly not the case for the upstream window where $T_{\max} = 65 \text{ °C}$ in the nominal scenario.

Figure 90 shows the contour plot of the distribution of the Fatigue Equivalent Stress in the upstream window according to the multi-axial fatigue analysis described in section 5.10. According to this analysis, the ~5 ms longitudinal oscillations of the dump induce a maximum fatigue equivalent stress of 140 MPa. This is well below the fatigue endurance limit in torsion for $2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles of Ti-Grade 5 at 300 °C, estimated to be 314 MPa. According to the modal characterization measurements of section 5.9, the longitudinal vibrations would be damped within 120 ms. This leads to ~20 oscillations per beam dump, and therefore $8 \cdot 10^4$ cycles are expected over 10 years of operation. Hence, we can conclude that fatigue is not an issue for the upstream window.

Figure 90 - Contour plot of the distribution of the Crossland's fatigue Equivalent Stress according to the multi-axial fatigue analysis described in section 5.10.

6.6 SUMMARY OF STRUCTURAL ANALYSES AND CONCLUSIONS FOR THE UPSTREAM WINDOW

Table 22 all the results of the analysis made in all the subsection 6.4, for the nominal beam and the x3 dilution failure scenarios considered.

As can be seen in the table, the maximum load corresponds to the dynamic load induced by the dump's vibrations. This load is 110 MPa, which it turns in a 6.3 safety factor against yielding.

Animations of all the simulations performed on the upstream window can be found in the links of Annex A.3.

Table 22 - Summary table of loads in the Upstream Window from the analysis performed in sections 6.4.1.2, 6.4.2 and 6.4.3.

Scenario	Max T (°C)	Max VM Stress (MPa) induced by the beam Quasi-static	Max VM Stress (MPa) induced by the beam Dynamic	Max VM Stress (MPa) induced by Dump vibration	Maximum Von Mises (MPa) due to N ₂ pressure	Max VM stress from simulations taking into account all the loads	Safety Factor against Yielding <small>$\sigma_{yield_100C} = 700 \text{ MPa}$</small>
Nominal	65	37	46	110	10	110 MPa	6.3
Flashover	113	66	73	110	10	Not relevant for fatigue	~6.3
Retrigger (14 μs)	112	48	50	110	10	Not relevant for fatigue	~6.3
2MKBH_ missing	61	36	65*	110	10	Not relevant for fatigue	~6.3

7. DUMP DOWNSTREAM WINDOW: DESIGN & FINITE ELEMENT ASSESSMENT

7.1 INTRODUCTION

Differently from the upstream window, whose inclusion in this upgrade was motivated by the removal of the N₂ reservoir, the upgrade of the downstream was directly motivated by compliance with Run 3 beam parameters. Before this upgrade, the downstream window consisted of a 10 mm thick blank KF-flange made in Ti-Grade 2 (unalloyed titanium). The strength of this material at room temperature is in the order of 380 MPa and drops down to 130 MPa at 250 °C. Simulations showed in ref. [14] indicated that in some Run 3 beam dilution failure scenarios, maximum temperature and stresses reached were 203 °C and 209 MPa respectively, leading to yielding in this material. These simulations were not considering yet the additional dynamic load induced by the dump's vibrations. In addition, the uncertainties related to the N₂ leaks and problems with the seals in the KF-flange motivated the shift in the design towards a bolted window (CF-flange) instead of clamped, as it is considered to be more robust. It shall be remarked that the access and maintenance for the downstream window is considerably more

complex than for the upstream window due to the presence of the shielding and high residual doses.

7.2 REQUIREMENTS OF THE DDS_W

Similarly to the upstream window, the downstream window (DUS_W) has to fulfil the requirements in terms of operational loads and integration compatibility with the TDE vessel.

7.2.1 Operational loads induced in the DDS_W

The DDS_W is essentially subjected to the same type of loads as the upstream one, i.e, the three types of loads described in section 6.2.1. The main difference with respect the upstream window is that, in the downstream one, the deposition of energy by the proton beam is consequence of the full-developed particle shower, which leads to a less focused but more transversally spread profile.

7.2.2 TDE vessel interface and integration requirements

The new downstream window has different integration requirements with respect to the upstream one. The new DDS_W shall be compatible with:

- 1) Bolted flange (CF-flange): As already introduced, it is decided to shift from the past clamped window to a bolted one in the upgraded design. This is considered more robust in terms of N₂ leaks. A Cu seal instead of EPDM can be used then, being more resistant to radiation damage.
- 2) Modification of the vessel's end to be compatible with the bolted flange of the window. This upgrade involves welding an extension on the end of the current dump's vessel (corresponding to a KF-flange). Description of the extension is given in section 7.3.3.1 as well as in document [EDMS 1888408](#) (ref. [66]).
- 3) Integrate TDE instrumentation: The design of the new downstream window shall be compatible with the following instrumentation:
 - a. Strain gauges (x3)
 - b. PT100s (x5)

The main purpose of the x5 PT100s is to measure the rise of temperature associated to each dumped pulse. The goal is to use these recordings to cross-check the FLUKA energy deposition simulations. These simulations are subjected to many uncertainties induced by the interaction through more than 8 meters of graphitic materials. Such uncertainties could imply a deposition of energy of a factor up to x2 with respect the simulation predictions. Comparison with predictions using Geant4 code could help to evaluate these uncertainties, in addition to the bench mark using temperature sensors.

7.3 DESIGN DESCRIPTION OF THE DOWNSTREAM WINDOW

7.3.1 Geometry of the Downstream Window (DDS_W)

Figure 91 shows new configuration of the welded extension and DDS_W. The official drawing number of the new bolted window is LHCTDE__0045, and Smart Team no. ST1235195.

As can be seen in the Figure 91 (b), the selected thickness of the window is 10 mm, as the upstream one. However, this window does not follow a variable thickness as the upstream one. This is due to the broader beam footprint in the window, induced by the particle shower, which prevents having an increased thickness to make it more robust against the dump's longitudinal vibrations. The natural vibration frequencies of this geometry in this configuration are around 300 Hz, 615 Hz and 1 kHz.

Figure 91 - (a) Downstream part of new TDE assembly (LHCTDE__0051, ST1225471_02) with the welded extension (LHCTDE__0044). (b) New bolted downstream window (LHCTDE__0045, ST1235195).

7.3.2 Titanium alloy and Manufacturing Process

Similarly to the upstream window (DUS_W), the material used is Ti-Grade 5. The geometry of the window was machined from a forged disk \varnothing 640 mm by 35 mm thick manufactured according to AMS4928V, which was provided by the company "Jacquet Osiro AG". The reported yield strength at room temperature is 835 MPa. The corresponding DAI is [67].

Material certificate as well as ultrasonic inspections can be found respectively in the following documents [68]and [69].

7.3.3 Attachment to the Dump and Sealing Solution

7.3.3.1 Additional welded extension

As introduced in Figure 91 (a), a new welded extension to the dump vessel is required in order to bolt on the new window. This extension is made in the same material as the vessel (stainless steel 318LN, also known as URANUS 45, UNS S31803, EN 10088-2, 1.4462).

A MIG (Metal Inert Gas) welding technique has been used, adopting as filler metal CN 22/9 N-IG from Bohler. During the tests on a mock-up of the weld, a minimum and maximum welding throat of 4 mm and 5 mm were achieved.

A welding assessment following the European standard code NF EN 1993- Design of steel structure- has been carried out. In the assessment, two values of the effective throat thicknesses were adopted, evaluating both the minimum value required by the Eurocode 3 (equal to 3 mm) and the minimum value obtained during experimental trials (equal to 4 mm). More information can be found in ref. [66]. The compliance of this weld with the operation loads is provided in section 7.7.

7.3.3.2 New Sealing Solution

Figure 92 shows the bolted solution for the downstream window. The seal is made of Cu OFS + 0.1% Ag (LHCTDI__0311). Nord-Lock washers are used to prevent bolt loosening due to vibrations.

Figure 92 - Detail showing the clamping solution of the downstream window, with a copper seal and Nord-Lock washer (LHCTDE__0051).

7.4 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF THE DOWNSTREAM WINDOW UNDER OPERATIONAL LOADS

Similarly to the upstream window, the downstream one is subjected to three types of loads: (i) Beam induced thermo-mechanical response, (ii) Vacuum/N₂ pressure differentials, (iii) Dynamic load induced by the vibration of the dump's vessel.

7.4.1 Beam Induced Thermomechanical Response

The profile of interaction of the proton beam with the material of the downstream window is considerably different from the one of the upstream one due to the developed particle shower occurring along the dump core. Figure 93 shows the profile of temperature along the thickness for a local region of the sweep path where the maximum temperature is reached. As can be seen in the figure, there is a gradient of the order of 40 °C within the thickness of the window, while for the upstream window is in the order of 20 °C. Higher temperatures are also reached in the downstream window (in the order of 150 °C).

Figure 93 - Temperature rise (from RT) along the 10 mm thickness of the downstream window, for a 15 mm region where the maximum temperature is reached.

It is important to mention that the simulations presented in this section consider that the density of the expanded graphite Sigraflex® in the dump is 1.1 g/cm^3 . This is different from previous studies in ref. [14], which considered this density to be 1.2 gr/cm^3 . This is due to the fact that recent discussions with the manufacturer suggested that the minimum guaranteed density of the material is 1.1 g/cm^3 . This implies that more energy may be deposited in the downstream window and therefore this density has been considered, applying a more conservative approach.

7.4.1.1 Calculation beam induced stress waves on the window

Following a similar procedure as in section 6.4.1.1, the dynamic stresses induced by the beam impact in the window have been evaluated using LS-DYNA®. The main difference in the modelling is in refined zones of the mesh, which, due to the less focused profile of the energy deposition, have to be considerably broader. In addition, the minimum mesh in such areas is consistently increased up to 0.5 mm.

Another difference in the modelling has to do with the beam dilution failure scenarios considered for the downstream window analysis, which are summarized in Figure 94. The main difference is that the "Retrigger scenario" considered is slightly different ("Retrigger-70 μs " vs the "Retrigger-14 μs " of the upstream one) as described in section 3.3. The reason is that the maximum energy density in the downstream window is higher with this scenario - as reported previously in ref. [14].

Figure 94 - Summary of the beam dilution path scenarios considered in the analysis of the downstream window.

Figure 95 - LS-DYNA® contour plots of temperature (left) and Von Mises stresses (right) for the dilution failure scenario "Retrigger-70 μs" at 89 μs after the start of the beam impact.

Figure 95 shows the contour plots for the temperature (left) and Von Mises equivalent stress (right) obtained by at 89 μs after the start of pulse impact for the dilution failure scenario "Retrigger-70", which is the worst failure scenario considered. A maximum temperature of 240 °C and dynamic stresses of 185 MPa are reached.

Row 3 of Table 23 summarizes the results for the nominal dilution path and all the considered the dilution failure scenarios.

7.4.1.2 Quasi-static stress induced by the beam impact

Several structural analyses considering the static thermal gradient arising from the interaction of the full beam dilution shower have been performed for the downstream window.

Figure 96 shows the temperature profile and quasi-static stresses for the failure scenario "retrigger -70 μ s". As anticipated, the temperatures are considerably higher than in the upstream window. For this failure scenario, maximum temperatures and associated stresses are 240 °C and 144 MPa respectively.

Figure 96: Contour plots of the thermal gradient and associated quasi-static stresses (Pa) for the dilution failure "retrigger -70 μ s".

Results of this analysis for the four-scenario considered are summarized in to row 2 of Figure 96.

7.4.2 Structural Analysis Vacuum/N₂ Pressure Loads

This analysis is equivalent to the one performed for the upstream window, since the windows thickness and material is the same. The results presented in section 6.4.2, predicting a maximum stress of 10 MPa due to the N₂ overpressure, are therefore applicable to the downstream window.

7.4.3 Dynamic Load Induced by the Vibration of the Dump's Vessel

Similarly to section 6.4.3, a transient structural simulation by applying the velocity field induced by the vessel's sudden expansion to the contact flange of the downstream window has been performed. Figure 97 illustrates this approach, including the velocity field applied and its oscillatory nature corresponding to the 200 Hz longitudinal mode of vibration of the dump. The maximum velocity reached at such contact is proportional to the energy deposition in the vessel and hence the impacted intensity. For the case of study ($1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb), the maximum applied velocity at the downstream flange is 2.2 m/s.

Figure 97 - Schematics showing the velocity profile applied at the contact face between the downstream window and the dump's vessel.

The dynamic simulation considers the thermal gradients induced by the beam impact as well, since this gradient will remain during the vibrations as there is little time for heat transfer during 15 ms. This is carried out by applying the temperature in an initial quasi-static structural step without time integration. In this way, the remaining thermal stresses are already present during the vibration induced dynamic response.

Figure 98 - Maximum VM stress reached in the window and displacement of the centre of the window during 25 ms as a consequence of the longitudinal vibration of the dump.

Figure 98-left shows that the expected maximum Von Mises stress reached in the centre of the window is in the order of 226 MPa. This maximum is reached 14.5 ms after the beam impact. The other critical region is the connection edge with the windows flange, which is a stress concentrator where stresses up to 255 MPa can be reached. Figure 98-right shows the associated displacement of the centre of the window as a function of time. The centre of the windows moves up to 5.4 mm towards the upstream as a consequence of this vibration. Maximum stresses and displacements under this load are considerably higher in the downstream window in comparison to the upstream one (even if the load is

similar) since the geometry of the downstream one is not optimized with the region of increased thickness, which makes the upstream one stiffer.

The stresses associated with this dynamic load are the dominating ones in the window, substantially higher than the ones directly induced by the beam.

7.5 FATIGUE ANALYSIS OF THE DOWNSTREAM WINDOW

The same material models and methods as described in the section 6.5 are applied to the downstream window. Figure 99 shows that the fatigue equivalent stress according to the Crossland criteria is 230 MPa, still below the endurance limit at 300 °C of 314 MPa ($2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles). Therefore, no fatigue issues in the downstream windows are expected over the operational life of the dump.

Figure 99 - Contour plot of the distribution of the Crossland's fatigue equivalent stress within the downstream window according to the multi-axial fatigue analysis described in section 5.10.

7.6 SUMMARY OF STRUCTURAL ANALYSES AND CONCLUSIONS FOR THE DOWNSTREAM WINDOW

Table 23 summarizes all the results of the analysis made in all the subsection 7.4, for the nominal beam and the x3 dilution failure scenarios considered.

As can be seen in the table, the maximum load corresponds to the one imposed by the longitudinal mode excitation of the dump. This load is 226 MPa, which gives a 2.3 safety factor against yielding for the "Flashover" failure in which the highest temperatures are reached (244 °C).

Animations of all the simulations performed on the downstream window can be found in the links of Annex A.3.

Table 23 - Summary table of loads in the Downstream Window from the analysis performed in sections 7.4

Scenario	Max T (°C)	Max VM Stress (MPa) induced by the beam Quasi-static	Max VM Stress (MPa) induced by the beam Dynamic	Max VM Stress (MPa) induced by Dump vibration	Maximum Von Mises (MPa) due to N ₂ pressure	Max VM stress from simulations taking into account all the loads	Safety Factor against Yielding <small>$\sigma_{yield_150C} = 630$ MPa $\sigma_{yield_250C} = 530$ MPa</small>
Nominal	155	103	150	226	10	226 MPa	2.79
Flashover	244	126	175	226	10	Not relevant for fatigue	~2.3
Retrigger (70 μ s)	240	144	185	226	10	Not relevant for fatigue	~2.3
2MKBH_missing	221	130	178	226	10	Not relevant for fatigue	~2.3

7.7 WELD ASSESSMENT OF THE NEW EXTENSION FOR THE DOWNSTREAM WINDOW

The upgrade of the TDE downstream window segment involves the replacement of the Ti (grade2) window, which featured a Helicoflex gasket, by an additional welded flange and a new bolted Ti (grade 5) window. The objective of the calculations was the verification of the weld connection located on the border between the new and the old parts, as shown in Figure 100.

Figure 100 - Location of the weld in the LHC-TDE downstream segment.

Two scenarios were verified by the FE analysis: 1) commissioning and 2) nominal beam operation. The first one regards the N₂ filling, where vacuum is previously created inside the vessel to extract the air. As a load, the deadweight is also considered. Static structural and buckling analyses were done to assess the component under this scenario. For the second scenario, transient thermal and transient structural analyses were performed to simulate the TDE subjected to thermomechanical loads resulting from the dumped particle beam. High-Frequency Vibrations (HFV) coming directly from the local window and Low-Frequency Vibrations (LFV) coming from the global dynamics of the structure were distinguished. Nominal thermal loads were obtained with the use of a multi-particle

transport code FLUKA for the most critical HL-LHC scenario and used in calculations of single beam impact (SBI) and fatigue. Results were also later scaled to Run 3 intensity.

Weld assessment for a single beam impact and cyclic loading was based on Eurocode 3 standard [70]. A 4 mm effective welding throat thicknesses was adopted for calculations, which corresponds to the minimum value obtained during experimental tests.

Only the most recent and selected results are presented herein. More technical details might be found in the documentation of the computational campaign [66] [71] [72] [73]. The broad summary was also presented in the LHC beam dump block (TDE) review on LS2 upgrades for Run3 operation [74].

Single beam impact results in Figure 100 and Figure 102 are presented in the form of circumferential stress distributions on the weld. From calculated equivalent and normal stresses in time, the worst possible instants during the run were chosen. Next, peak equivalent and normal stresses were compared to limits imposed by the Eurocode 3, evaluated including the safety factors imposed by the norm. Therefore, an additional utilisation ratio R_σ between calculated stresses and limit stresses was introduced to easily interpret results. Failure criterion is defined as follows: calculated stresses have to be lower than limits established by the norm, i.e., utilization factor cannot be lower than unity.

One can observe that the despite non- axisymmetric load distribution on the downstream window, results exhibit very small stress fluctuation along the circumference. Utilization ratios for HL-LHC and LHC Run 3 conditions are well above failure criteria in all considered cases. For the most severe HFV case, they equal 4.29 and 5.48 respectively.

In terms of fatigue loads, the total number of cycles before failure was calculated – see Figure 103. Assuming 16 Low frequency cycles per dump and 160 High frequency cycles for each dump (based of the modes damping measurements of section 5.9), one can infer the total number of dumps before failure. It equals $13.7 \cdot 10^3$ dumps for LHC Run 3 conditions.

Figure 101 - High-Frequency Vibrations (HFV) case for a single beam impact.

Figure 102 - Low-Frequency Vibrations (LFV) case for single beam impact.

Figure 103 - Fatigue evaluation for a) High-Frequency Vibrations (HFV) and Low-Frequency Vibrations (LFV) cases

Table 24 — Summary of results.

Scenario	Case	Beam	Figure	Calculated	Minimum allowable
S1	LC1 – Vacuum	-	R_{σ}	62	1
	LC2 – Buckling	-	LM	111	15
S2	LC1 – HFV	LHC RUN3	R_{σ}	5.5	1
		HL-LHC	R_{σ}	4.3	1
	LC2 – LFV	LHC RUN3	R_{σ}	5.5	1
		HL-LHC	R_{σ}	4.3	1
	Fatigue	LHC RUN3	N	13.7k	1600 (10 years operation)
		HL-LHC	N	6.6k	4000 (10 years operation)

In conclusion, the weld connection foreseen in the TDE upgraded end segment was studied under the commissioning and nominal operation scenarios under vacuum and the HL-LHC and Run 3 beam loads. The phenomenon of thermomechanical fatigue was addressed among the failure assessments. The utilization factors of the admissible and calculated stresses in the weld according to Eurocode 3 [EC 3] are above the minimum required by the standard. The number of calculated dumps is much higher than the expected 10k dumps during Run 3 and HL-LHC lifetime.

8. THERMOMECHANICAL ASSESSMENT AND DESIGN OF NEW DUMP BLOCK SUPPORT FRAMES

8.1 DESIGN DESCRIPTION

The requirements and main constraints for the new dump block support frame are given in section 2.3 along with a brief description of the initial design.

8.1.1 Support frame final design

The final support frame design is very similar to the initial design shown described in section 2.3; it supports the dump by means of two steel wire rope loops that are longitudinally approximately 4 m apart. The wire ropes are supported at each end by steel cradle structures that fit around the dump block. The cradles are separated by rigid side members. Each cradle has a foot which sits on the shielding underneath the dump block in its installed position. Due to tight space constraints the cradles and side members are designed to fit in the same space as the lifting frame fitted to the dump cores before LS2.

The final design of the frame is shown in Figure 104 .

Figure 104 - Final design of dump block support frame. Left image shows whole frame, right image shows the cradle equipped with support rope assembly (the drawing numbers for UD 62 and UD 68 are LHCTDE__52 and LHCTDE__58, respectively)

The main differences with respect to the initial design were prompted by the analysis work reported in section 8.2:

- Stiffer side members – closed rectangular sections instead of open U sections (see section 8.2.1.1)
- Modified feet (see section 8.2.1.2).
- Addition of locking nuts combined with “Nordlock” locking washers and anti-rotation devices at the extremities of the support rope assemblies (see section 8.2.2.5)

Details of the cradles at each end of the dump block support frame are shown in Figure 105 and Figure 106.

In order to ensure that the dump block does not migrate with respect to the support frame with successive dumps, rope (or cable) guides are welded on to the dump outer vessel. The support ropes pass through circumferential slots included in the lower portion of the rope guides; this ensures that the dump will always return (due to gravity) to the same longitudinal position after each thermal heating and cooling cycle. In addition, a steel ring clamped on each rope assembly locates in an opening in the centre of the circumferential slots in order to prevent rotational migration of the dump over repeated beam dumping cycles.

Figure 105 - New dump block support frame – cut-away view of the cradle structure at one end of the support frame. The wire rope loops that support the dump block are suspended from shafts that locate in the cradle structure. Cable guides are welded to the dump block – these cable guides have a U-shaped groove at the bottom of the dump block circumference to prevent the rope slipping longitudinally with respect to the dump block during the rapid expansion and vibration of the dump block. The cable guides have a central gap – a ring clamped on the rope engages in this gap to prevent rotation of the dump around its longitudinal axis.

Figure 106 - Details of the new dump block support frame. The support frame is equipped with bolted-on feet that stand on the shielding below the dump block. The feet need to be removed to allow the dump to be lifted over the LHC machine in the junction caverns UJ62 and 68 because of the limited clearance between the LHC machine/dump beam lines and the hoists. The feet are attached to the frame with bolts designed to be accessible for removal by a robot once the dump is radioactive.

8.1.2 Steel wire rope (Rope assemblies, rope anti-rotation fittings lubrication)

The ropes used to support the dump core are proprietary lifting ropes with swaged end fittings manufactured and fitted by a steel wire rope manufacturer (see Figure 107). DAI order can be found in the EDH document [75].

Figure 107 - Rope assembly. (Drawing LHCTDE__0117)

The selection of the appropriate steel rope is vital for the reliability of the new support configuration. A concentrated effort has been made on the topic, contacting several companies and experts. Moreover, as part of the wire rope design/calculation and check, a contract with TensionTech laboratory, in the U.K, was agreed for fatigue testing and technical support (see DAI [76]).

The key points of a suitable selection of the rope are: Strength of the rope, flexibility, wear resistance and fatigue resistance. According with these parameters, Diepa H40 \varnothing 21 mm was selected as the most appropriate one. The general properties of this rope are:

- 8 external strands
- Independent core rope
- Compacted outer and inner strands
- Parallel wire configuration
- Non-rotational resistant
- High strength: 1960 N/mm²
- Galvanized

- Very flexible on bending
- High relative strength for a given diameter
- High resistant to wear
- High resistant to fatigue

Technical properties of the rope can be found on the technical data sheet [77] and are summarised in Table 25.

Table 25 - Technical data of wire rope Diepa H40 \varnothing 21 mm. * Note that because the assembly includes end fittings and central ring, the MBF of the assembly is $0.9 \cdot MBF_{rope} = 387 \text{ kN}$

rope	DIEPA H40
construction	8xK26WS-IWRC
diameter	21 mm
surface finished	Galvanized
tensile strength	(EIPS) 1960 N/mm ²
lay direction	(sZ) right-handed
Min. breaking forece	430 kN*
fill factor	0.7403
spinning loss	0.84
torque factor	0.076
Elastic modulus	128000 N/mm ²

Note that the strength or performance of the full assembly can be different with respect to theoretical properties of the rope itself. According to the EN-13411-8 [78] [79], the swaged fitting could produce a reduction up to 10% with respect to the nominal minimum breaking force (MBF). The performance of the assembly was tested by the supplier DIEPA. The measured breaking force of the assembly is 435.6 kN, which is superior to the required MBF of the assembly 387kN (see report [80] for more details).

8.1.2.1 Rope anti-rotation fittings

As the rope is "non-rotation resistant"; it is therefore necessary to prevent the ends from rotating under load. To do this anti-rotation levers are attached to the rope ends. See Figure 108.

Figure 108 View of the end of the rope assembly where it mounts on to the dump support frame. The load on the rope is transmitted to the frame by a nut screwed on to the threaded end of the rope assembly. To lock the position of the nut on the rope assembly, a second lock nut is used in conjunction with a Nordlock washer between the two nuts to prevent loosening under severe vibration conditions. The blue component above the two nuts fits on a rectangular section machined in the end of the rope assembly and is used to prevent rotation of the end of the rope assembly relative to the frame over the life of the dump. (Drawing LHCTDE_0111 and 3D mode ST1313148)

8.1.2.2 Ropes – radiation environment considerations

In view of the levels of radiation next to the dump block, the selected ropes do not contain any inner plastic sheathing.

Standard practice in the production of steel wire ropes of lifting appliances is to introduce lubricant between the strands during manufacture. This product then lubricates the rope as it bends during operation of the lifting appliance. As part of the design and build process for the frame, the implications of radiation dose to the lubricant in the rope and the options for replacing it with a more radiation tolerant alternative were studied. This work is reported in section 8.1.2.3.

8.1.2.3 Lubrication of the ropes

The choice of lubrication for supporting ropes must take into account two main challenges: temperature and radiation.

Based on simulations of vessel temperature illustrated in Figure 64, the expected rope temperature is computed and presented in Figure 109. It should be noted that 70°C might be exceeded in ropes during 1-4 hours after each dump event.

Based on FLUKA simulations mentioned in Section 4.6, the TDE supporting structure is expected to be exposed to approximately 5 MGy per year of standard operation, which might result in more than 15 MGy over the equipment lifetime during Run 3. Such a dose is extremely challenging for polymeric materials, even most radiation-tolerant lubricants are expected to undergo critical structural modifications. As a consequence, the supporting structure, and in particular the rope assemblies, have been thoroughly designed and tested in order to ensure safe operation even without lubrication (see Section 8.2.2). Lubrication should nevertheless be present in components subject to friction in order to limit fretting wear and corrosion, and therefore further increase safety factors. The components to be lubricated are:

- Interface between rope terminations and support frame;
- Rope core and surface
- Rope guides on dump vessel.

Figure 109 - Estimated temperature evolution in the supporting wire ropes after a single dump event with intensity $1.2 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb (blue), $1.5 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb (orange) and $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb (grey).

Extensive studies, documented in [81], have been carried out to evaluate different lubrication possibilities.

Ideally, a single lubricant, both temperature and radiation resistant, should be used in order to avoid any potential incompatibility issues. The grease Lubrilog LX AGFA 2 is selected for this application based on a literature review and a wide market survey. As a polyphenyl ether-based grease, it is very promising in terms of radiation resistance [82] despite the current lack of results on the finished product. However, a complete irradiation

study on the product in question is ongoing in the scope of collaboration agreement KN4751, with results expected in spring 2021. Moreover, it resists without melting to temperatures up to 350°C.

The selected Diepa H40 cables are sold pre-lubricated with Elaskon SK-DL and cannot be purchased dry. The product in question is expected to melt above 70°C and partially drop out from cables, as can be seen in Figure 110 (more details in EDMS [83]). Moreover, Elaskon SK-DL will likely degrade due to radiation after the first couple of years [82]. A deep cleaning of finished cables is possible [84] [85], but unfortunately reduces the thickness of galvanised layer on steel wires [86]. In addition, an efficient method of thorough re-greasing has not yet been developed [87]. Therefore, a hybrid lubrication solution is selected, combining both aforementioned products and a heat pre-treatment. The aspect of this lubrication can be observed in Figure 111, and its main features are presented in Table 26. The greasing operation of TDE support rope and fixation parts is documented in [88].

Figure 110 - Left: Wire rope with original lubricant after undergoing the temperature evolution expected in mid-Run 3. Right: Wire rope with double lubrication after 18 hours at 100°C. The change of colour indicates a mixing between the two lubricants.

Figure 111- TDE steel wire rope with a double lubrication: Elaskon SK-DL between strands and individual wires and Lubrilog LX AGFA 2 on the outer surface

Table 26 - Main features of lubrication of TDE support ropes

Selected solution	lubrication	Role	Remarks
Core lubricant	Elaskon SK-DL, initially about 21 g per rope	Reduce internal friction during initial stages of operation (ca. 1-2 years)	Unknown radiation resistance of the two lubricants and their mixtures
Surface lubricant	Lubrilog LX-AGFA 2, about 200 g per rope	Reduce friction at the dump-rope interface during initial stages of operation (ca. 3-4 years) Reduce risk of fretting corrosion by limiting access of oxygen to steel ropes	Must achieve a ca. 90:10 mixing ratio of Lubrilog/ Elaskon in order to maintain drop point above operating temperature
Pre-treatment	2 heating cycles of 24 h at 90°C	Remove the excess of Elaskon SK-DL that would drop out during operation (about 50%) Limit risk of area contamination Limit mixing ratio of Lubrilog/Elaskon to ca. 90:10 Should not have impact on thickness of galvanised layer	Additional operation step

It should be noted that, based on laboratory tests illustrated in Figure 110, the two products would likely mix as a result of gravity and diffusion. Prior to the validation of this hybrid lubrication, different mixtures of the two lubricants in question have therefore been characterized. The progressive evolution of apparent viscosity (Figure 112) and drop point (Table 27) of these mixtures indicates a satisfactory compatibility between the lubricants. As mixtures mainly composed of Lubrilog grease are the best compatible with expected operating temperatures [89], a heat pre-treatment has been carried out on ropes in order to optimise the quantity of Elaskon inside [90].

Figure 112 - Apparent viscosity of mixtures of Lubrilog LX AGFA 2 and Elaskon SK-DL.

Table 27 - Drop point of mixtures of Lubrilog LX AGFA 2 and Elaskon SK-DL. The first three values are within the uncertainty of the measurement technique.

Référence	Résultat
ELASKON SK-DL	77.5°C
Ratio 10 (LUBRILOG LX AGFA 2)/90 (ELASKON SK-DL)	76.8°C
Ratio 50 (LUBRILOG LX AGFA 2)/50 (ELASKON SK-DL)	77.9°C
Ratio 90 (LUBRILOG LX AGFA 2)/10 (ELASKON SK -DL)	242.2°C
LUBRILOG LX AGFA 2	SANS

The study detailed in n [81] is still ongoing and aims to develop a re-lubrication technique that will allow the use of a single lubricant for all the lubricated parts of the next generation of dumps.

8.2 ANALYSIS

This Section is aimed for providing an exhaustive thermo-mechanical analysis of the new dump support system in order to ensure its compliance according to the design requirements.

The design requirement is the survival of the new supporting system for at least the RUN 3 period (4 years) without significant damage that can compromise the structural integrity or operational functionality of the TDE and at the same time reducing the maintenance interventions.

As general baseline design criterion, 400 dumps/years at full RUN 3 intensity ($1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb) is assumed for the calculations, which is a conservative assumption considering previous experience during RUN 2 (around ~ 150 dumps/year in average).

From a conservative point of view, yield strength of the materials is set up as ultimate design criterion, although steel alloys exhibit a very ductile behaviour even beyond the yield strength.

8.2.1 Support Frame

This section is focused on the analysis of the support frame, excluding the steel wire rope and rope guides, which are considered in dedicated sections.

The assessment of the global behaviour of the frame has been studied via full dynamic analysis explained in Section 5.7. Additionally, some specific analysis on particular components of the support frame have been carried out in order to provide more accurate results.

8.2.1.1 Dynamic assessment

Two different configurations of the frame were studied during the design phase. As described previously in Section 8.1, the initial (original) version of the frame was made of two cradles (U structure, which support the dump) linked by two longitudinal side bars with a standard open U profile. This version was modified for a closed rectangular 200x80x7 mm profile. This subsection explains the reasons for this modification and the dynamics of the support frame.

Material properties of the different components of the frame support (see Figure 113) are summarized in Table 28. As generally considered in this document, an elasto-plastic model (with linear kinematic hardening) is applied for metal-base materials.

Figure 113- Materials used for the new supporting system

Table 28 - Material properties of the steel grades used in the TDE frame

Material	Density (kg/m ³)	Poisson's ratio (-)	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Yield stress (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Fatigue limit 1E6 cycles (MPa)	A (%)	Ref
S235JR (1.0038)	7850	0.3	200	235	340-470	185-215	>24	[91]
S460ML (1.8838)	"	"	"	460	540-720	140-265	>17	[92]
C60 (1.0601)	"	"	"	450	750-900	185-415	>14	[93]

At the steady state, the frame is loaded by the gravity effect. After the beam impact, energy is deposited on the TDE block and produces a dynamic response of the block itself. Forces are transferred from the TDE block to the frame through the ropes, although these forces are relatively low, because of the high flexibility. This flexibility is actually the key of the new supporting system and it allows the free movement of the TDE block.

Due to the particle shower phenomenon, a non-negligible amount of energy is deposited in the frame and particularly in the side bars. These bars suddenly expand with the temperature and violently push the cradles. This phenomenon excites some bending/torsional frequencies of the side bars and results in high levels of deformation.

Figure 114 shows a comparison between both frames (with the open profile and the rectangular one). The higher torsional/bending stiffness of the closed side bars helps to reduce the movements and stresses considerably with respect to the original design (you can see both videos by clicking on: [first-version](#) and [last-design](#) or in EDMS folder [94]). Equivalent Von-Mises stress are kept lower than 200 MPa (< yield stress) for the closed profile.

Figure 114 - Equivalent stress (Von-Mises) during the fast movement of the frame for: a) first version made of lateral bars with open U profiles and b) last design with a close rectangular profiles.

Regarding the cradles, they also experience a sudden thermal expansion. Since the movement of the cradle is not strongly constrained and the rope is relatively flexible, the thermal load does not imply high levels of stress. The dynamic behaviour of the cradle and stresses are mainly dominated by the expansion of the side bars.

Figure 115 shows a sequence of pictures, representative of the behaviour of the cradle (note that the displacement has been amplified by a factor of x 100 in order to clearly show the deformation). The transversal stiffeners, which connect both U plates of the cradle, help to absorb these longitudinal forces. The highest stresses are found during the initial expansion of the frame (first 2 ms) and in general are lower than 400 MPa (and lower than yield stress), except in local areas where plastic deformation may happen. A more refined model is required to analysis in detail the stresses in cradle and foot (see 8.2.1.2).

Figure 115 - Sequence of picture of the dynamic behaviour of the cradle and foot during the initial expansion of the frame.

8.2.1.2 Cradle and foot

Although the general behaviour of the full TDE and frame can be analysed by the full dynamic model (see previous section), this model is not well optimized to study the stresses in the cradle and foot at high level of detail.

This Section shows a dedicated sub-analysis of the cradle and foot. Sub-modelling technique was employed. The foot is joined to the cradle via screws. Friction contact is considered between the contact surfaces. The shielding is also included and friction contact is applied between the feet and shielding. Screw/bolts are considered via beam elements.

A dynamic simulation up to first 15 ms was carried out in order to capture several cycles of the expansion of the frame (See Figure 116). The cradle was initially preloaded by the rope forces. Then, displacements were imposed on the side bars, which represents the thermal expansion of the frame. The particle shower and sub-sequent energy deposition was as well applied to the model.

ANSYS® software was used with a characteristic element size of 0.5mm (first order elements). Schematic illustration of the model is shown in Figure 116.

AE: Transient Structural

A Displacement
B Force

Figure 116 - Numerical model of the new foot and cradle

Figure 117a shows the equivalent Von-Mises stress on the cradle and foot after the preload of the rope. Stresses at the steady state are lower than 35 MPa.

Obviously, during the expansion of the frame, stresses increase significantly. Figure 117b and c show the maximum Von-Mises equivalent stress over the time (i.e. this is an artificial plot with the maximum value at each node over the time) for both parts, respectively.

In general, **the stresses on the cradle are lower than 300 MPa (YS= 460MPa)**. As expected, maximum stresses are found around the welds between the stiffeners and U plates; this is probably related to the singularities of the corners (note that the welds are not directly represented in the model which may change locally the stress distribution). Plastic deformations may happen in these areas but should not compromise the structural integrity because they remain very local and low, and would produce a hardening phenomenon (moving the yield surface) followed by reconfiguration of the stress state.

Concerning the foot (see Figure 117c), the stresses are lower than 180 MPa in general (YS=235 MPa) during most of the simulation. Small jumps are observed in the foot and the full support due to fast vibrations. Peaks of stresses appear at the impact moment with the ground and it may produce some minor plastic deformation on some local corners. No issues are expected.

Y: Cradle foot
static stress
Type: Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress
Unit: MPa
Time: 1.e-006

(a)

V: Cradle_foot

Type: Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress (averaged)
Unit: MPa
Maximum Over Time

(b)

Y: Cradle_foot
Foot
Type: Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress
Unit: MPa
Maximum Over Time

(c)

Figure 117 – (a) Von-Mises stress after the preload of the cradle due to the rope force; (b) and (c) maximum Von-Mises stress over time in the cradle and foot. Note that small plastic deformations are found on the cradle around the welds, which produce a hardening phenomenon. Results are shown at the integration points.

Screw forces were tracked as well over time. Table 29 summarises the maximum force and utilization factor for each screw. These screws are Bumax M16 quality A4 109 (high strength) [95].

Table 29 - Maximum forces on the foot screws during the dynamic movement. *Utilization factor according to Eurocode (including Eurocode safety factors). ** Assuming frictional contact between bolted faces.

	TYPE	AXIAL [KN]	SHEAR [KN]	UTILIZATION FACTOR* (NO PRELOAD)	UTILIZATION FACTOR** (PRELOAD)
SCREW 1	Bumax M16 A4 109	16.8	40.4	75%	91.7%
SCREW 2	Bumax M16 A4 109	13.6	22.9	45%	70%
SCREW 3	M24 A4-70	16.1	61.0	48%	71%

Because the cradle is exposed to high dynamic forces, a fatigue analysis is believed to be convenient in order to assess the fatigue service life. The same procedure and scripts as described in section 5.10 have been followed in this section. Crossland’s criterion was selected and the analysis was based on non-constant amplitude evolution.

The main inputs for this analysis are the fatigue properties (see Figure 118) and the stress evolution over time. It should be notice that no attenuation or damping phenomenon was considered in the simulation, promoting conservative results.

Figure 118 - S-N curves for S 460 ML steel, different loading conditions [92]

Figure 119 shows the fatigue damage on the cradle for each beam dump. It is assumed that vibrations are attenuated after ~120-150 ms, which is coherent with previous experimental observation (see Figure 55) and modal analysis (see Section 5.9).

As has been considered throughout this document, 400 dumps/year x 4 years=1600 dumps is set as baseline for the fatigue check. According to Crossland’s criterion, no fatigue issue is expected during the entire service life of the cradle. Based on an accumulative damage evolution, macro cracks could appear around the welds of the

stiffeners (where the highest level of equivalent stresses are found) after 37000 dumps, this is, after 23 years.

Figure 119 - a) Crossland fatigue damage on the cradle (values equal or higher than 1 mean failure by fatigue). b) Maximum Crossland equivalent stress on the cradle.

Note that Crossland's equation is a multiaxial fatigue criterion based on the stress state. This criterion is suitable for structures with low or negligible plastic deformation. Although this assumption is well fulfilled, other criterion as Fatemi-Socie's one should be more advisable because it relies on the shear strain at the critical plane. Aiming to provide an additional comparative fatigue result, this criterion has also been studied.

Fatemi-Socie's criterion requires additional fatigue properties: fatigue ductility (ϵ_f) and fatigue ductility exponent (c). These parameters have been estimated by Rossle and Fatemi's formula [51]. Considering a Brinell hardness 180 MPa for S460ML material (see [96]), these parameters are given as follows:

$$\epsilon_f = \frac{1}{E} [0.32 HB^2 - 487HB + 191] = 947 \text{ MPa}; c = -0.56$$

Figure 120 shows the Fatemi-Socie damage per beam dump and the equivalent shear deformation. This criterion exhibits lower damage values than Crossland's one, which is in agreement with previous findings for the vessel (see Section 5.10). According to Fatemi-Socie's criterion, failure could be expected after 770k dumps.

Figure 120 – (a) Fatemi-Socie’s fatigue damage on the cradle (values equal o mayor than 1 means failure by fatigue). b) Maximum Fatemi-Socie’s equivalent shear strain at the critical plane on the cradle.

8.2.1.3 Pins

The pin is a crucial component of the support frame. Part of the dynamic load is transferred from the TDE block to the cradle via the rope. Dynamic analysis of the steel rope shows up oscillations of the axial force around the steady state by a factor around 100% (see Figure 127). The pin, which connects the rope to the cradle, has been designed to withstand these force oscillations. A sub-analysis, focused on the pins has been made in order to study the stresses in detail.

Figure 121 shows the FEM model. Only the pins, saddle and a portion of the cradle is represented. Friction contact has been defined between pin-saddle and pin-cradle (other contacts, which are welded, are assumed as bonded).

Figure 121 - FEM of the pin

LS-DYNA® code has been used for this analysis. Mesh size of the pins is 2 mm (linear element), in order to capture the stresses with high resolution. The simulation is run during the first 10 ms, when maximum forces and oscillations are expected.

This simulation was divided into two steps. Initially, the saddle, which transmits the force from the rope to the pin, was preloaded by the weight of the TDE block. Then, the dynamic forces of the rope due to the expansion of the full TDE, was applied to the saddle.

Figure 122 shows the stress at steady state when TDE is at rest. The maximum stress in the shaft is 68 MPa.

Figure 122 - Von Mises Stress (in Pa) on the (a) cradle and (b) pin at the steady state (gravity is considered)

The Von-Mises stress in the pin at the worst time during the dynamic simulation is shown in Figure 123. The maximum stress, 190 MPa ($\sigma_y = 450$ MPa), appears around the central hole, where the rope passes through, and it is mainly driven by bending/shear phenomenon.

Figure 123 - Von-Mises stress [Pa] on the pin at the worst time (t=8.94ms) during the dynamic simulation considering the dynamic force oscillation of the rope.

In addition to the previous dynamic analysis, a multiaxial fatigue study has been developed on the pin, aimed at estimating the fatigue performance. In line with other previous fatigue analysis, Crossland’s criterion has been used. More details of this criterion and procedure can be found in Section 5.10.

In the literature, different fatigue curves can be found for C60 steel depending on the grade. Figure 124 and Figure 125 show the main fatigue properties for grade σ_y (yield strength)= 580 MPa and $\sigma_y = 380$. The most conservative curves are assumed in this section.

Figure 124 - S-N curves for C60 steel with $\sigma_y \geq 580$ MPa, different loading conditions [93]

Figure 125 - S-N curves for C60 steel with $\sigma_y=380$ MPa, different loading conditions [93]

Figure 126 shows the Crossland’s equivalent fatigue stress in the pin. The maximum equivalent fatigue stress found, 114 MPa, is below the endurance limit at $1e6$ cycles $\tau_{\text{torsion}_f} = 205$ MPa and $\tau_{\text{shear}_f} = 185$ MPa at $1e6$ cycles; and at $1e7$ cycles : $\tau_{\text{torsion}_f} \approx 140$ MPa and $\tau_{\text{shear}_f} \approx 122$ MPa at $1e7$ cycles (extrapolated data). According to the modal analysis and the simulations (see Section 8.2.2), oscillations of the rope force are expected to be attenuated after ~ 100 ms, which is equivalent to ~ 300 oscillations per beam dump. This provides an expected service life > 33000 beam dumps; this is longer than 20 years.

Figure 126 - Crossland’s equivalent fatigue stress in Pa.

8.2.2 Steel wire rope & anti-rotation system

8.2.2.1 Steel wire rope

The steel rope allows the TDE block to move freely, accommodate its thermal expansion and at the same time it avoids any permanent displacement/rotation. Figure 107 shows

the assembly of the wire rope. Basically it is defined by the wire rope itself, the swaged terminal and the anti-rotation central ring.

Loads on the rope are produced basically by the fast movement of the entire dump and the energy deposition on it. Figure 127 shows the axial force in the rope over time extracted from the full dynamic simulation (Section 5.7). The main phenomenon responsible for this force is the breathing vibration mode of the dump at 2.3kHz, which produces a sudden expansion/contraction of the rope. [Here](#) (or in EDMS folder [94]) you can see an animation of the rope movement.

The mean value of the axial force is 17 kN (corresponding with weight of the dump block itself) and the range of the oscillation is between [30 - 7] kN. Considering a quasi-static analysis and the properties of the rope (see Table 25), the theoretical safety factors are summarized in Table 30.

Figure 127 - Axial force on the steel rope after the beam impact. Simulation includes the damping ratio of the breathing mode. Real simulation is up to 25 ms. An artificial extension of the curve up to 100ms was made in order to capture the damping attenuation with time.

Table 30 - Static and Quasi-dynamic safety factor of the rope.

Static Safety factor (weight of the dump)	$0.9 \text{ 430kN} / 17 \text{ kN} = \mathbf{23}$
Quasi-dynamic safety factor (Max. force)	$0.9 \text{ 430kN} / 30 \text{ kN} = \mathbf{13}$

8.2.2.2 Fatigue analysis of the rope

A special attention has been dedicated to the fatigue aspect of the rope. The ropes are exposed to a severe oscillatory load and could potentially compromise the structural integrity of the new support system.

Simulations shows that the main load of the rope is Tensile-Tensile (TT), and the bending phenomenon is practically negligible.

According to the literature, fatigue properties of the rope are mainly driven by the mechanical properties of the steel, the structure of the wire rope and the grease. Müller found that de-lubricated wire ropes have an endurance of about 75 % with respect to lubricated ones for TT-fatigue. Moreover, a parallel lay strand configuration has always a better fatigue performance compared to ordinary cross lay (see [97]).

Numerous TT fatigue tests on different ropes can be found in the literature. This test provides basically the typical force amplitude-Number of cycles up to failure (S-N curve). The regression equation proposed by Fryer [97] is the most commonly accepted among the scientific community to represent the TT-fatigue behaviour:

$$\lg N = a_0 + a_1 \cdot \lg \frac{2 \cdot S_a \cdot d_e^2}{d^2 \cdot S_e} + a_2 \cdot \frac{S_{\text{lower}} \cdot d_e^2}{d^2 \cdot S_e} + a_3 \cdot \left(\frac{S_{\text{lower}} \cdot d_e^2}{d^2 \cdot S_e} \right)^2 + a_4 \cdot \lg \frac{d}{d_e}$$

where N is the number of cycles up to the failure, S is the tensile force (see Figure 128), d is the rope diameter, $S_e=1$ is the dimensionless force, d_e is the dimensionless diameter and a_i are the fatigue parameter to be determined.

Figure 128 - Nomenclature of TT-fatigue test for a wire rope

Given that a priori no-fatigue characterization is provided by the manufacturer and a S-N curve is required to perform the fatigue analysis, fatigue parameter is extracted from the literature for a first estimation. After a deep review of the literature, the fatigue properties reported by [98] seem to be the most representative according to the wire structure, diameter and type of steel. Parameters of this S-N curve can be found in Table 31.

Table 31: fatigue parameters of steel wire rope (see [98])

a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4
13.524	-3.76	4.45e-3	-1.17e-5	0

As commonly used in the literature, Rainflow algorithm and linear accumulative damage based on Miner's rule is applied here. Figure 129 shows the rainflow spectrum, i.e. number of cycles for each force amplitude and mean. 300 cycles is found in total for a period of 100 ms where most of the cycles are at low amplitude.

Figure 129 - Rainflow decomposition applied to the axial rope force for a beam dump.

The distribution of damage can be seen in Figure 130. The total damage is around 3.23×10^{-7} /beam dump. Considering 400 dumps/year and 4 years (RUN-3), **the total damage is 0.05%**, where 100% means fatigue failure.

Damage; total damage = 3.2306×10^{-7}

Figure 130 - Fatigue damage decomposition of the rope for a beam dump. Significant damage is only produced for force amplitude higher than 2kN.

8.2.2.3 Tensile Fatigue testing of the rope

In the context of the contract signed with TTI Testing laboratory (see [76]), a series of tensile fatigue tests was carried out to confirm the fatigue performance of the rope.

The fatigue test is carried out on the final rope assembly, including the swaged end central ring. As proposed by the experts, a constant amplitude Tensile-Tensile test at worst load conditions is tested. Because the radiation environment in the cavern can affect the performance of the rope grease, a degreased rope assembly has been chosen for the test. This simulates the worst condition.

TTI testing's 250 kN tension-torsion machine is used. Set up parameters can be found in Table 32. Figure 131 shows the test assembly. Temperature of the rope is monitored during the test.

Table 32 - Fatigue test parameters

Mean load	17 kN
Amplitude	13kN
Constant Ampl. At freq.	2Hz

Figure 131 - Tensile fatigue testing of the rope assembly. (a) General view and (b) view of the end fitting.

Two tests were performed on two de-greased wire rope samples: up to 1.12 M of cycles and up to 2.24 M of cycles, respectively. Report of the testing can be found in [80].

The first test was successfully completed for 1,120,000 cycles without apparent symptoms of damage on the wires (some small wear marks).

The second sample successfully completed 2,240,000 cycles without failure. Inspection of the sample showed a greater level of internal fretting fatigue, as might be expected, but it was still at an acceptable level.

Inspection of the end fitting and fixation system indicated they are in good conditions after more than 5M cycles. Some minor wear is observed on the pin and swaged end fitting (see Figure 132).

In order to assess the fatigue damage, a tensile breaking test was carried out on the second sample that had been cycled up to 2.24 M cycles. The test was unexpectedly interrupted during the cycling at 1.62 M cycles and then re-started from the beginning. The Ultimate breaking force after fatigue test (3.86 million of cycles) is 413.7 kN, this is a reduction of 5% with respect to the initial breaking force, 435.6 kN (see Section 8.1.2). This new breaking force is still 5% above the required MBF of the assembly (as per code EN13411-8 [78]). It should be noted that the relationship of strength reduction-fatigue damage is highly non-linear and it cannot be extrapolated. Therefore, we can conclude that even after the fatigue test, which is more severe than the expected real service conditions, the rope retains good performance in term of strength.

a

b

c

d

Figure 132 - a) Sample completed 1,120,000 cycles without failure b) Sampled completed 2,240,000 cycles. Fretting observed between core-strands producing red rust. c) Fretting damage between pin and swaged end-fitting after 5.4M cycles. d) Detail of the pin and swaged end-fitting. e) Spherical bearing with some minor wear marks. F) Saddle with some wear on the pin side. g) Swaged end-fitting with some fretting damage on the edges. h) Surface of M30 nut and NordLock washer.

8.2.2.4 Fatigue safety value

Based on previous fatigue test, a minimum fatigue safety factor can be estimated. It is important to note that the experimental fatigue test is performed at a constant amplitude whilst the real axial rope force amplitude decays with the time due to the damping.

As shown in Figure 130, only the cycles at higher amplitude (>2 kN) produce significant damage (this is, 140 cycles/beam dump out of 300 cycles, where only a few cycles are above 10kN). Assuming that these 140 cycles are at the testing amplitude (13kN), the **minimum safety factor based on no-failure before 2.24 Million cycles is**

$$\frac{2120000 \text{ cycles}}{140 \text{ cycles/dump} \cdot 400 \text{ dump/year} \cdot 4 \text{ year}} = 10.$$

Nevertheless the previous assumption is quite conservative. More accurate calculation can be done assuming a linear damage method. Applying the Miner's rule, the equivalent number of cycles at testing amplitude and mean is only 5 cycles/beam dump. **Fatigue safety factor is** $\frac{2240000}{5 \cdot 400 \cdot 4} = 280.$

8.2.2.5 Anti-rotation system

The rope is non-rotation resistant. That means that if an axial force is applied, the rope will tend to rotate around its axis and unravel. Some preliminary calculations reveal that the rope could twist almost 1 turn due to the static force and this twist angle could oscillate due to the axial force variations after the beam impact.

A priori the system was design to absorb this movement. Nevertheless, TTI testing experts recommendeds the installation of an anti-rotation system at both extremities of

the rope. According to their experience and the literature [99], the unravelling of the rope could reduce the fatigue and strength performance.

The full dynamic model of the dump does not include the detail of the anti-rotation system. A separate simulation of the anti-rotation system has been carried out. The simulation is based on a Quasi-static analysis assuming the worst dynamic conditions. Force and torques were estimated based on dynamic simulations and the rope torque-based axial force.

Figure 133 shows the model and summary of boundary conditions. Note that forces and torques are far overestimated because the flexibility of the rope is not considered (and it includes a safety factor 1.5.).

Figure 133 - Model and boundary condition of the anti-rotation system

Note that the anti-rotation system is made of Uranus 45 and the rope termination is made of a high strength carbon steel 1.6580+QT. Main properties are summarised in Table 33. Elastoplastic model with kinematic hardening are assumed for both materials.

Table 33 - Main properties of the anti-rotation system and rope termination. Note: Fully reversed *tensile/**bending fatigue test for infinite life.

Rope Materials	Yield strength [MPa]	Ultimate strength [MPa]	Endurance limit [MPa]
Uranus 45	460-480	640	265**/311*
1.6580+QT	990	1170	550*

ANSYS® software was used for this analysis. Second order elements with a characteristic mesh size of 1 mm for the lever and 0.75 mm for the rope termination were set-up. Frictional contact was assumed between both bodies. Mesh refinement around the contact areas with a characteristic size of 0.2 mm was applied.

Figure 134a shows the equivalent Von-Mises stress on the anti-rotation system. **Maximum tensile stress** on the anti-rotation lever is around **320 Mpa**. This stress is lower than the fatigue strength (362 MPa), considering the correction by Goodman

diagram [100], and yield strength. There may be some local high compression stresses on the contact regions that should not compromise its performance.

As it can be observed in Figure 134b, the stress in the termination is high around the contact region with the anti-rotation lever and it decreases rapidly with distance from the contract region. This stress is mainly in compression. Tensile stresses are lower than endurance limit and yield strength (<**550 MPa**).

Local plastic deformation can be found around the contact edge of the rope termination (see Figure 134d). This plastic deformation remains very local and low. Some fretting phenomena could be expected on the edges with the time but are not relevant for the functionality of the system. Actually, this phenomenon has been observed on the termination during the fatigue test of the rope assembly without any apparent issue (see Figure 132).

(a)

(b)

Figure 134 - Equivalent Von-Mises stress on (a) the anti-rotation lever, (b) rope termination and (c) assembly. (d) Accumulative plastic deformation of the termination.

8.2.3 Rope guides on dump core

The function of the rope guide is to spread the rope force on the vessel and to guide the rope. The rope guide is made of two separate pieces of Uranus 45 and they are welded to the vessel (see Figure 135).

Figure 135 - Drawing of the rope guide welded on the vessel. (Drawing LHCTDE_0048)

The general behaviour of the rope guide was studied with the full dynamic model. The major stress contribution is produced by the fast vibrations of the vessel, which are transmitted to the rope guide through the welds. Note that because the same material is used as the vessel, the differential thermal expansion vessel-rope guide is reduced.

This Section is focused on the welds, which are a critical point.

A dynamic FEM simulation has been carried out in order to extract the forces on the welds. A sub-modelling technique has been implemented for the present analysis. As can be

seen in Figure 136 the model only considers a section of the vessel and the rope-guide. Explicit LS-DYNA® software was used with a characteristic element size of 5mm (first order elements).

Figure 136 – (a) Sub-FEM model of the rope guide and (b) detail of the mesh

As habitual in sub-modelling, displacements on the vessel are imposed as boundary conditions. These displacements are imported from the full dynamic analysis of the dump (see Section 5.7). Energy density deposition due to beam-matter interaction is also applied in the model.

The welds are represented by linear bonded contacts between rope guide and vessel. No welded contact surfaces are considered to be frictional.

As commented elsewhere in this document, there are two main modes of vibrations: at 200 Hz (longitudinal mode) and 2000 Hz (radial mode). The simulation has been performed during first 12 ms in order to capture several longitudinal cycles and provide representative results.

The same procedure as used for the calculation of welds in Section 7.7 is applied here. Contact forces, that represent the welding forces, are extracted from the simulation. A uniform distribution of the stress is assumed on the throat section of the weld, leading to the normal stresses and shear stresses. The welds are checked according to the Eurocode 3 [70] for static and fatigue.

Figure 140 shows the equivalent welding stress considering the maximum forces over the time. **Minimum safety margin is 1.33.**

Figure 137 - Maximum equivalent weld stress over the time for the rope-guide according to Eurocode 3 [70].

Figure 138 shows the non-dimensional fatigue damage depending on the stress type. For the fatigue calculation, 400 dumps/year and 4 years of RUN3 at maximum intensity is considered. **The minimum safety factor 3.8** is found for the normal stress. In addition to previous criteria, Eurocode 3 recommends an additional check of the stresses related to the yield stress of the material (see Eq 8.1 EC 3 [70]), providing **minimum safety margin is 2.3**.

Figure 138 - Fatigue damage criteria according to Eurocode 3.

Note that the safety margins are evaluated according to the Eurocode [70], which includes partial safety factors that penalize the material properties.

8.3 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

An exhaustive review of the different components of the new supporting system has been shown in this Section.

In general, the stresses of all components are below the yield strength and no issue is expected during the full RUN 3. Let's highlight that yield strength has been set up as ultimate design criterion, when it is well known that steel alloys exhibit a very ductile behaviour even beyond the yield strength.

Fatigue analysis has been studied on some critical components and they show good performance. Welds and bolts have been checked and they fulfil the Eurocode design requirements.

Table 34 summarises the main results.

Table 34 - Summary of the results for the dump support frame

	EQ. STRESS [MPa]/ YIELD STRESS [MPa]	MIN. SAFETY FACTOR	FATIGUE # DUMPS
SUPPORT FRAME (GENERAL)	<200 Mpa / Min yield= 235 Mpa	1.18	-
CRADLE (U-SUPPORT)	300 Mpa / 460 Mpa	1.53	>37000
PIN/SHAFT	190 Mpa/ 450	2.37	>33000
FOOT	180 Mpa/ 235 Mpa	1.31	-
STEEL WIRE ROPE	30 kN / MBF 430 kN	12.90	>15000
ANTI-ROTATION SYSTEM	320 MPa/ 460 MPa	1.50	No-issue
ROPE GUIDE (WELDINGS)	276 MPa/ 460 MPa	1.33	No-issue

9. LHC BEAM DUMP INSTRUMENTATION PACKAGE FOR RUN 3

Taking into account the dynamic behaviour of the dump during beam impact, it has been decided that the dump shall be extensively instrumented for Run 3, in order to cross-check the extended simulations and to provide input for the HL-LHC dump. In this way, its performance and the effectiveness of the implemented changes could be assessed.

The instrumentation is selected in order to monitor essentially 4 types of features:

- 1) Temperatures on the vessel and windows surface: Measuring temperatures in key locations would help to cross-check the temperature peak reached due to the sudden deposition of energy predicted by simulations. In addition, it will bring key information regarding the heat diffusion from the core to the vessel as well as subsequent cooling. Knowing these temperature trends is important as they are driving the slow movements of the dump.
- 2) Dynamic behaviour of the dump (fast movement): As shown in this report, the most demanding loads on the dump (both on the vessel and windows) are induced

by the longitudinal mode excitation. For this reason, good monitoring of such vibrations (at ~ 200 Hz) to know their amplitude and damping time is paramount to cross-check simulations. These measurements will be triggered by each dump event.

- 3) Slow movement: Monitoring this movement would allow to better understand the slow heat-up/cooling displacements of the dump and potential permanent displacements.
- 4) General monitoring: Additional instrumentation such as a camera, microphone and N_2 pressure gauges are also added or modified as means to detect abnormal or unexpected events.

The acquisition system for each dump is based on a National Instruments PXI [101] allowing:

- All instruments to be acquired synchronously, with the exception of the strain-gauges, which are directly acquired by the conditioning electronics.
- Data to be logged over network to the NXCALS logging database [102].

Two different types of acquisitions have been set-up:

- Continuous acquisition (slow acquisition): The data is published with their timestamp in NXCALS. In general, the data is saved at 1 Hz although it can be modified according to future needs. The variables name of each sensor can be found in [94].
- Trigger acquisition (fast acquisition): The data will be acquired continuously and maintained in a circular buffer (2 s buffer) according to the fastest sampling rate specified for each instrument. Once the beam trigger is received, the system should continue with the fast acquisition for 8 s additional after the reception of the trigger. The acquisition for each sensor type should be saved in **.csv** format, including a timestamp column, and in separated files at a predefined server location. The folder where these files are stored can be found in [94]. In addition this data will be dumped on Post-Mortem data base.

Table 35 summarizes all the installed instrumentation and their specifications. All the instrumentation is selected based on its compatibility with the expected radiation levels in the area (see Figure 139 and Section 4.7 more details). Figure 139 shows FLUKA estimations of such levels at the vicinity of the dump. The values in the figure correspond to the dose evaluation for 1 year with ultimate Run 3 parameters (200 dumps/year, 2748 bunches, $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb). It is important to note in any case that, during the first operational year, the expected doses are in the order of 65 % of the ones of the figure, since the intensity will be lower during the commissioning ramp-up. As shown in the plot, the maximum expected dose in the vicinity of the dump is in the order of 15 MGy. In addition, all the active electronics of these devices are placed in a shielded rack in TD tunnel at 80 m from the UD cavern, where doses are below 1 Gy/year and thermal neutron fluence below $3 \cdot 10^7$ cm^{-2} /year, as has been shown in the FLUKA analysis of section 4.8.

Table 35 - Summary of all the instrumentation installed for post LS2 Operation.

Feature	Instrument	Positions and no. of measuring points		Acquisition rate		Range	Accuracy
				Fast	Slow		
Thermal Response	PT100s	Upstream Window	1	10 Hz	1 Hz	20°C-250°C	±1°C
		Dump's Vessel	10				
		Downstream Window	5				
Dynamic Response	Strain Gauges	Upstream Window	3	1 kHz	1 Hz	+/- 2000 µm/m	5-10 µm/m
		Dump's Vessel	6				
		Downstream Window	4				
	LDV	Upstream Window	1	10 kHz	-	+/- 4 m/s (up to 24 m/s)	0.01 m/s
	Accelerometers	Upstream Window	3	240 kHz	1 Hz	0-2000g	--
Slow Movement	LVDT	Upstream Window Horizontal	1	1 Hz	1 Hz	+/- 20 mm	+/- 0.1mm
		Upstream Window Vertical	2				
General Monitoring	N ₂ Pressure	N ₂ Injection Line	1	100 kHz	1 Hz	Release valve will open at 1.3 bars	~1 mbars
	Camera	Cavern	1	24 fps		FOV = 500 x 1000 mm	N/A
	Microphone	Cavern	1	96 kHz		N/A	N/A

Figure 139 - Radiation dose evaluation (1 year). Considerations: Dumps per year: 400, Number of bunches: 2748, Intensity: Run3 $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb, Standard scenario: 6V4H.

The next subsections describe in detail the particularities of implementation of each type of instrumentation. The instrumentation selection has been made taking into account the return of experience of the instruments installed during Run 2 (described in section 1.5). The interferometer installed at that time was very useful to detect some of the vibrations and permanent displacements on the dump. However, the high accelerations present in the reflective mirror and high velocities reached, which were not clearly known and understood at that time, led to the fracture of the reflective mirror. In addition, this instrument had a speed limitation of 2.5 m/s (much lower than the expected value from the latest simulations), leading to frequent loss of the signal and, consequently, loss of the reference to monitor the long term displacements.

9.1 TEMPERATURE SENSORS (PT100S)

As summarized in Table 36, 11 PT100s, with continuous acquisition at 10 Hz have been installed. The model Omega PT100 RTDCAP-100A-1-A086-060-K-40 has used for this purpose. Figure 140 shows a picture and datasheet details of this model. It consists on a ceramic (alumina) measuring cylindrical body of \varnothing 2.18 mm x 15.24 mm.

Model No.	Description
RTDCAP-100A-1-A086-060-K-40	100 Ω RTD, 0.086" diameter x 0.6" long alumina with 28 AWG polyimide leads, 350°C (660°F), 2-wire only

Figure 140 - Picture of an Omega PT100 RTDCAP-100A-1-A086-060-K-40 as installed on the dump.

These devices have a thermal response time $T_{63\%} < 1s$. This means that they cannot measure the exact peak temperatures reached due to the sudden deposition of energy by the beam shower in the vessel or windows, but the temperature present after $\sim 1 s$ of heat transfer to the ceramic probe. These measurements are in any case very useful to crosscheck the deposition of energy (though they will require FE simulations of heat transfer during this period) as well as to monitor the long term thermal inertia of the dump. The probes are resistant to radiation up to 10 MGy and are compatible with cable lengths above 80 m (enough to reach the shielded rack in the TD tunnel).

The type of sensor installation differs depending on the location. These differences and the expected temperatures are described in the next subsections. In any case, all the PT100s are inserted in orifices filled with thermal glue of the type Loctite Stycast 2850 + CAT 9, which are radiation-hard qualified. Information on the glue can be found in [103] [104].

9.1.1 PT100s in the Upstream Window

Only x1 PT100 sensor is installed in the upstream window. This sensor is installed in a M8 drilled hole on the upper part on the window, as shown in Figure 141, and filled with thermal paste. No relevant temperature measurement above room temperature is expected right after a beam dump since, as shown in the figure, the sensor is very far from the beam trajectory. Nevertheless, this sensor could measure an eventual slight increase of temperature some hours after the beam impact due to the heat transfer from the dump block.

Figure 141 - Image of the upstream window highlighting the hole in which the PT100 is installed. The image includes as well a superposition of the beam pattern on the upstream window. Nomenclature of the PT100 is T_X_US_i, where US refers to upstream; X corresponds to the TDE reference, such that A - Dump A - HCTDE_002-CR000002 - UD68; and B - Dump B - HCTDE_002-CR000001 - UD62; and i is the position on the window

9.1.2 PT100s in the Downstream Window

Four PT100s are installed in the dump downstream window. Differently from the ones of the upstream window, these sensors will measure an important temperature increase after each beam dump due to the particle shower. The purpose of these sensors is twofold:

- 1) Monitor temperatures in the downstream window to make sure that no overheating which could reduce the mechanical properties of Ti-Gr 5 of the window does take place.
- 2) Crosscheck the accuracy of the FLUKA simulations regarding the predicted energy deposition in the downstream window, which is subjected to certain uncertainties regarding the complexity of modelling the beam interaction along 8.5 m of graphite. This uncertainty can be up to a factor of x2 as reported in section 4.5.

The difficulty in fulfilling these purposes comes from the fact that a direct attachment of the PT100s sensors to achieve a reliable measurement on the face of the window would imply drilling a penetration in which they could be inserted. This is not an option for structural robustness. In addition, other alternative solutions such as clamping the sensors with a plates that keep contact pressure between them and the window's face were also abandoned since FE simulations showed that the window vibrations (described in section 7.4.3) and the associated accelerations would lead to loss of the sensor contact or even fracture of the supporting plate. For this reason, the implemented solution consists in attaching a plates made of Ti-Grade 5 (same material as the window) to the peripheral bolts, keeping it separated by 13 mm from the window's surface so there is no risk of plate-window collision during the beam induced vibrations. The PT100s are then inserted in these plates (see Figure 142 for more details).

Figure 142 - Drawing of the plates, which support the PT100s of the downstream window. (See LHCTDE__0129)

Therefore, the measured temperatures will correspond to the ones induced by the deposition of beam energy in the plates themselves instead of the window. FLUKA simulations show that the deposition of energy in the downstream surface of the window is very similar to that in the plate (9-10 % higher in the plate).

Figure 143 shows two pictures of the downstream window with the plates for the PT100s attached. The exact position of the plates and the PT100s can be found in LHCTDE__0051. Similarly, Figure 144 shows the distribution of the deposited energy in the plates by the particle shower.

Figure 143 - Pictures of the PT100s inserted in the Ti-Gr5 plates attached to the downstream window. More details of the exact position of the plates can be found in LHCTDE__0051. Nomenclature of the PT100 is T_X_DS_i, where DS refers to downstream; X corresponds with the TDE reference, such that A - Dump A- HCTDE_002-CR000002 - UD68; and B - Dump B - HCTDE_002-CR000001 - UD62; and i is the position on the window.

Figure 144 - Footprint of the deposited energy by the beam shower in the downstream window, and the PT100 plates, superimposed with a picture of the installation.

According to the FLUKA and thermo-mechanical simulations, the maximum difference in the temperature recordings at the end of the pulse between the real window's surface and measured in the plates would be in the order of 6 °C for $1.2 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb and 9 °C for $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb. Note that, the PT100s are always surrounded by the same thickness of material (5 mm). This estimated difference does not consider the fact that the PT100 material (Alumina) is slightly less dense than titanium (3.9 g/cm^3 vs 4.5 g/cm^3), therefore in reality this difference may be lower.

Figure 145 shows the estimated temperature trends expected in the PT100s inserted in the plates, as well as in the corresponding position projected on the window's surface. As seen in the plot, the T_X_DS_1 should record something close to the maximum temperature expected in the downstream window ($\sim 150 \text{ °C}$ $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb). In any case, the measured temperature in the points from T_X_DS_1 to T_X_DS_4 would be subjected to the variability and accuracy of the real beam sweeping path on the dump with respect to the position of the plates, therefore, discrepancies between these measurements with respect the temperatures shown in Figure 145 may be possible. The T_X_DS_5, on the other hand, is placed close to the centre of the window, where there is little gradient in the deposition of energy (as shown in Figure 144). The temperature measurement of this sensor may be used then to cross-check the overall absorbing efficiency of the dump. Regarding the time trend of temperature in plots of Figure 138, it should be noted that the temperature is expected to drop faster in the window than in the plate, due to the less available surrounding mass in the latter. Finally, it is also important to mention that the current temperature estimations are conservatively assuming a density of SIGRAFLEX® of 1.1 g/cm^3 (while it may be within $1.1\text{-}1.2 \text{ g/cm}^3$). This may be an additional source of discrepancy to be considered when comparing simulated data with simulations.

Figure 145 - Estimated temperature trends expected in the PT100s inserted in the plates, as well as in the corresponding position projected on the window's surface. Temperatures plotted from $1.2 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb and for $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

From the point of view of structural robustness of the supporting plates, dynamic simulations of the plates' vibrations have been performed (similarly as in section 6.4.3) taking into account the imposed velocities due to the excitation of the vessel's longitudinal mode. The design of plate was optimized for reducing the dynamic oscillations. As can be observed in Figure 146b the maximum expected displacement with time is lower than 4 mm, which is well below the 15 mm distance from the windows surface. Moreover, the stresses in the plate are in general below 250 MPa, except in some local areas where it is observed non-realistic stress concentration due to washer-nut boundary condition (see in Figure 146a). Therefore, no structural issue and no impact with the window's surface are expected.

Figure 146 -a) Von-Mises stress of the PT100 plate at the worst time. b) Movement of the plate tip vs time excited by the dynamic movement of the dump. Simulation done for RUN3 $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

9.1.3 PT100s on the Vessel

Similarly, Figure 137 shows the position of the 10x PT100s installed on the vessel. They are installed by inserting them in ten supports welded on the vessel and filled with thermal glue. These sensors will measure the sudden temperature rise due to the energy deposition on the welded supports as well as the subsequent temperature increase due to the diffusion heat transfer from the dump's core.

Figure 147 - Scheme of the positions of the x10 PT100 installed on the dump's vessel. Nomenclature of the PT100 is T_Xij, where i and j is the position on the vessel and X is

TDE reference according to the following convention: A – Dump A, corresponding to HCTDE_002-CR000002 - UD68; and B – Dump B corresponding to HCTDE_002-CR000001 - UD62. The PT100s are inserted in supports that are welded on the vessel at +/-45° with respect the horizontal, on the left side, where maximum energy deposition is expected. Bolted plates on these supports are also used as guides for instrumentation cables.

It is important to highlight that, as previously mentioned in Section 9.1.2, sensors are not directly in contact with the vessel itself but there is 2.5 mm distance between centre of the sensor and external vessel surface. Therefore, temperatures in the sensors are expected to have a small shift/deviation with respect to the vessel during the beam impact due to the gradient of the energy density deposition (see Figure 148). Based on FLUKA trends, this difference should be around 4.5 °C/ mm.

Figure 148 - Energy density deposition through the vessel according to FLUKA calculations.

Regarding the long-term heat transfer phenomenon, this temperature difference should be rather small (~1-2 °C) and it comes from the extra thermal resistance of the stainless steel support.

Figure 149a and b show the temperature evolution of each PT100 with time for the beam intensities $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb and $1.2 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb, respectively. This temperature evolution does not consider the above-mentioned shifts. Moreover it should be considered as an estimation and one needs to be conscious of the multiple uncertainties coming from: material properties, manufacturing process, FLUKA calculations, cooling system: convective and radiative parameters, FEM calculations, contact pressure vessel-core, etc.

a

b

Figure 149 - Temperature evolution of the PT100 installed on the vessel for intensity a) $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb and b) $1.2 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb

9.1.4 Summary and Estimations of expected Temperatures in all the PT100s

As a summary of sections 9.1.2 and 9.1.3,

Table 37 shows estimations of expected measurements for all the installed PT100s.

Table 37 - Summary table of temperature sensors and estimations of expected measurements.

Sensor Name	Position	Expected Temperature EOP		Max Expected Temperature	
		1.2·10 ¹¹ ppb	1.8·10 ¹¹ ppb	1.2·10 ¹¹ ppb	1.8·10 ¹¹ ppb
T_X_US_01	Upstream window	RT	RT	slight increase	slight increase
T_X11	Vessel	30.0	35	52	66
T_X12	Vessel	40	50	72	94
T_X13	Vessel	53	68	96	127
T_X14	Vessel	39	47	61	75
T_X15	Vessel	26	28	32	37
T_X21	Vessel	27	30	49	61
T_X22	Vessel	34	40	67	87
T_X23	Vessel	43	53	127	168
T_X24	Vessel	32	37	76.	97
T_X25	Vessel	24	26	30	33
T_X_DS_01	Downstream window	107	150	110	154
T_X_DS_02	Downstream window	102	142	102	142
T_X_DS_03	Downstream window	85	121	89	122
T_X_DS_04	Downstream window	97	134	98	137
T_X_DS_05	Downstream window	55	72	55	72

9.2 MONITORING OF THE DYNAMIC RESPONSE

The three methods employed to monitor the dump's vibrations are described in the next subsections. These systems aim to record mainly the longitudinal mode of vibration (~200 Hz), although bending modes such as the ones described in section 5.9 may be also detected.

9.2.1 Strain Gauge Measurements

16 strain gauges are installed in both dump vessel and windows. The gauges have the following characteristics:

- Polyimide electrical strain gauges bonded using Vishay M-Bond 610 a 2-component epoxy-phenolic adhesive [105].
- Readout at 1 kHz using carrier signal conditioning electronics to minimise EMI effects.
- High temperature solder to cope with expected maximum temperature.
- Lightweight cabling to minimise forces on gauges due to high acceleration.
- Continuous acquisition at 1 Hz. High speed acquisition at 1kHz trigger by beam (10s [-2s , + 8s])

The thermally induced strain that may be measured due to the local temperature rise can be compensated (or interpreted) with the temperature recordings of the PT100s, which are installed along the dump vessel close to the strain gauges. In any case, no

temperature changes due to heat diffusion are expected during the ~ 500 ms of dump vibrations after the beam impact. Therefore, the temperature should not be relevant in the amplitude of the measured waves.

In order to reduce the risk of gauge detachment due to the accelerations and inertia, all the gauge cables are attached by a plate (already introduced in Figure 147) close to the gluing positions. All the cables are also routed through tubes attached to the dump vessel.

Strain-gauges are used to monitor the general dynamic behaviour of the TDE block and windows. One can distinguish between two different dynamics: the beam-induced dynamics and the response of the full TDE to the beam impact excitation. The time scale of both phenomena are different. Beam-induced dynamics are related to the wave propagation (pressure wave ~ 5000 m/s in steel). This kind of dynamics is complex to capture because the strain-gauges are not immune to the EMI and a random signal during at least the first ms after the beam impact is generated. Moreover, the level of deformation is relatively small and it is expected to be almost dissipated during that blind period. Therefore, the main objective of the strain-gauges is the monitoring the post-excitation response of the TDE block and windows, which are related to the modal response. Actually, the movement of the TDE will be a combination of different modes, and depending of the mode it can even persist for several seconds (case of the bending mode).

The position of the strain-gauges has been selected in order to capture the different possible modes of the TDE and they are shown in the next subsections along with their nomenclature. It is important to point out that the acquisition frequency of the strain-gauges has been set-up at 1 kHz a priori. Although faster acquisition rate can be specified, according to previous experience, this could introduce higher level of noise in the signal, masking real signal and in detriment of the quality and accuracy of the results. In any case, the acquisition system has been designed to be flexible and it allows adjustment according to future needs.

9.2.1.1 Strain Gauges in the Windows

Figure 150 shows two images with the positions of the strain gauges in the upstream and downstream window respectively, together with the beam footprint. As shown, all the strain-gauges have been aligned in the radial direction, aimed at catching the radial bending.

Note that the temperature should not significantly affect the measurements in the upstream window as the strain gauge positions are at least 55 mm from the beam impact location. On the downstream window, on the other hand, the strain gauges will be partially hit by the beam shower. Temperatures in the order of 54 °C, 72 °C and 50 °C are expected at positions of the S_X_DS15, S_X_DS45 and S_X_DS225 respectively for operation at $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

Figure 151-Figure 153 show the expected strains to be measured by the sensors in the windows for operations at $1.2 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb, $1.4 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb and $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb respectively. As can be seen in the plots, the maximum expected amplitude in the strain would be in the order of 200-1000 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$. The periods of the measured oscillations would be, according to the simulations, in the order of 1-2.2 ms for the upstream window and 1.2 ms for the downstream one. This is consistent with the 1st natural frequency of the upstream window

reported to be 430 Hz in section 6.4.3, and the 2nd and 3rd natural frequencies for the downstream one, 615 Hz and 1 kHz, reported in section 7.4.3.

The simulations presented in the Figure 151-Figure 153 are taking into account the initial temperature distribution (for this reason the strain in the plots does not start from 0).

It is worth noticing that in any case, since the acquisition frequency of the strain gauge is 1 kHz, it may be complex to have a smooth plot of the strains in the time domain. Nevertheless, according to Nyquist's principle the first mode should be detected in the frequency domain. Potential increases of acquisition frequency of the system to 2-3 kHz, should be evaluated during operation and it could help to detect these modes with better resolution.

Figure 150 - Images showing the positions of the strain gauges in the upstream and downstream windows. The beam footprint is superimposed on the windows.

Figure 151 - Expected strain based on simulations in the x3 strain gauges placed in the upstream and downstream window for $1.2 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb. Estimated temperatures in the strain-gauges of the downstream windows during the measurements are 43 °C, 55 °C and 40 °C.

Figure 152 - Expected strain based on simulations in the three strain gauges placed in the upstream and downstream window for $1.4 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb. Estimated temperatures in the strain-gauges of the downstream windows during the measurements are 56 °C, 65 °C and 53 °C

Figure 153 - Expected strain based on simulations in the x3 strain gauges placed in the upstream and downstream window for $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb. Estimated temperatures in the SGs of the downstream windows during the measurements are 54 °C, 72 °C and 50 °C.

9.2.1.2 Strain Gauges along the Vessel

Up to 10 strain gauges are attached along the vessel of the dump. They are placed approximately at the same positions as the PT100s, which have been shown in Figure 154. As an example, Figure 155 shows a strain gauge attached at approximately 25 mm from the support in which the PT100 is inserted. Distribution and nomenclature of the strain-gauges can be found in Figure 155.

One can find two longitudinal rows with five strain-gauges in each one. The upper row has been installed at 45° with respect to the vertical plane, whilst the lower row has a

90° phase difference with respect to the upper row. All the strain-gauges were aligned in the longitudinal direction.

As shown in Figure 144 and Figure 149, the beam swept pattern is a kind of ellipse, where the main axes are de-phased with respect the vertical plane by $\sim 45^\circ$. The positions of both rows were set-up according to these axes. The idea is to detect the different modes, which are related to the energy disposition (excitation source) and hence the swept pattern. Information about the different modes can be found in Section 5.9. The main one is the longitudinal mode at ~ 200 Hz, whilst the rest of the modes are different kinds of local/global bending deformations, and they should be detected by the strain-gauges. Radial or breathing mode happens at very high frequency and it is not expected to be recorded with the strain-gauges.

Moreover, the strain-gauges could provide indirect information/estimations regarding the stress level on the vessel. Thermal and mechanical deformations could be uncoupled using the temperature sensors next to each stain-gauge. Nevertheless, it is expected to find a shift in the measurements due to radiation-induced phenomena. The values of the stress should be understood as relative changes in a cycle instead of absolute values.

Figure 155 - Picture of a strain gauge attached to the vessel, close to the support for its neighbouring PT100. Nomenclature of the strain-gauges is S_Xij, where i and j is the position on the vessel and X is TDE reference according to the following convention: A – Dump A, corresponding to HCTDE_002-CR000002 - UD68; and B – Dump B corresponding to HCTDE_002-CR000001 - UD62

Figure 156 and shows the expected strains to be measured by the sensors in the windows for operations at $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb. The maximum expected amplitude in the strain would be in the order of $1250 \mu\text{m/m}$. As shown in Figure 157, the main longitudinal mode at 200 Hz is well detected by the sensors. Note that although the figure does not show the bending modes because it requires much longer simulations over time, the sensors should also be able to detect them. Nevertheless, due to limitations on the acquisition rate, breathing mode may not be detected, but it should be observed with the accelerometers.

Figure 156 - Plots of the expected strain in the strain-gauges along the vessel for beam intensity $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

Figure 157 - Plot of the expected strain in the strain-gauges of the vessel in the frequency domain for beam intensity of $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

9.2.1.3 Summary of Strain Gauges

Table 38 - Summary table of strain gauges and estimations of expected measurements. * Estimated values by applying reduction factor proportional to beam intensity.

Sensor Name	Position	Max Expected Strain [$\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$]	
		$1.2 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb	$1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb
S_US_15	Upstream window	220*	400*
S_US_45	Upstream window	180*	220*
S_US_225	Upstream window	600*	900*
S_11	Vessel	315*	475
S_12	Vessel	661*	993
S_13	Vessel	830*	1247
S_14	Vessel	541*	812
S_15	Vessel	254*	382
S_21	Vessel	338*	507
S_22	Vessel	665*	990
S_23	Vessel	813*	1220
S_24	Vessel	493*	740
S_25	Vessel	272*	408
S_DS_15	Downstream window	600*	900
S_DS_45	Downstream window	600*	900
S_DS_225	Downstream window	600*	900

9.2.2 Laser Doppler Vibrometer (LDV)

In addition to the high acquisition rate strain gauges, it has been decided to add an LDV in order to measure accurately the velocities and displacements reached during the longitudinal vibrations of the dump.

The Digital SWIR Laser Doppler Vibrometer from the manufacturer Optomet GmbH [106] has proven to be a very reliable instrument under radiation environments, extensively used already at CERN in several HiRadMat experiments (see [107] [108]). It consists of a passive optical head connected to an acquisition system through an optical fibre. A laser is sent from the optical head to a localized point in a surface. The instrument measures the velocity of the surface by Doppler effect (in the perpendicular direction of the laser) and estimates the displacement as well by an internal integration. This equipment can measure even on black, glowing or extremely rough surfaces.

In order to measure the dump's vibration, the contactless optical head is placed at 189 mm from the upstream window as shown in Figure 158, in a support independent from the dump and attached to the floor of the dump cavern. The support is described in detail in section 9.5. The acquisition system of the device is placed in the shielded bunker, placed around 80 m upstream in the TD tunnel as described in Section 4.8.

Figure 158 – 3D model showing the position of the LDV head and the point of velocity measurement in the upstream window. The nomenclature of the LDV is $V_X_US_i$, where V means vibrometer, X is TDE reference according to the following convention: A – Dump A, corresponding to HCTDE_002-CR000002 - UD68; and B – Dump B corresponding to HCTDE_002-CR000001 - UD62, US refers to the upstream side, and 01 to the position.

The LDV will measure at 10 kHz for 8 s after each dump (saving as well a 2 s buffer before the trigger). The device is self-triggered by the surface movement. The range of measurement is ± 4 m/s with an accuracy of 0.01 m/s. This range can be increased up to ± 24 m/s if necessary, with a proportional reduction in accuracy. This is a mayor advantage with respect to the interferometer system used during Run 2, which was subjected to signal loss when velocity was above 2.5 m/s.

Figure 159 shows the expected LDV measurement for an intensity of $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb. The response will be dominated by longitudinal mode (at ~ 200 Hz). The LDV measurement will be able to accurately characterize the amplitude of vibration without being subjected to the uncertainties of the strain gauges (temperature dependence, damage to the glue, etc.).

Figure 159 - Expected velocity at the LDV a) in the time and b) frequency domain for beam intensity of $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

9.2.3 Accelerometers

Three uniaxial accelerometers are attached to the vessel of the TDE block. The function of these sensors is to provide additional monitoring of the high frequency vibrations of the TDE block.

The sensors are installed close to the upstream windows and are accessible for maintenance purposes. They are installed at $A_US_01=45^\circ$, $A_US_02=135^\circ$ and $A_US_03=180^\circ$. A_US_01 and 03 are aligned with respect to the radial direction of the TDE block, whilst the A_US_03 is aligned with the longitudinal direction.

This accelerometer has been developed at CERN, using an interferometer pointing to a membrane inserted inside a hollow box as shown in Figure 160.

Location of the three accelerometers in the dump surface.

Cross section of the accelerometer with lateral attachment.

Cross section of the accelerometer with longitudinal attachment.

Figure 160 - In-house developed accelerometer. The nomenclature of the accelerometer is A_X_US_i, where A means accelerometer, X is TDE reference according to the following convention: A – Dump A, corresponding to HCTDE_002-CR000002 - UD68; and B – Dump B corresponding to HCTDE_002-CR000001 - UD62, US refers to the upstream side, and i to the position of each sensor.

The main characteristics of the system are the following:

- Interferometer-based measuring system: Similarly as with the LDV, the optical heads of the interferometers are passive, and are connected to the acquisition system through optical fibres. For this reason, this system is not affected by radiation (in short/medium term), nor by EMI. The acquisition system is placed a large distance away (80 m) from the optical head, in the bunker situated upstream the TD tunnel (described in section 4.8).
- Support of the accelerometer allows for different alignment in the three Cartesian directions. An illustration can be found in Figure 160. These supports are welded to the vessel in order to transmit the vibration to the sensors.
- Acceleration range: 2000g. Although it can survive to higher acceleration levels.
- Bandwidth: up to 240 kHz (acquisition rate).
- Continuous acquisition at 1Hz. High speed acquisition at 2 kHz trigger by the beam dump during 10 s, (-2 s before the trigger + 8 s after the trigger).

Figure 161 shows the expected accelerations in the time and frequency domain at the position of the accelerometers. Most of the expected signal should be in the range of [-2000, 2000] g, but some peaks above 4000g could appear and the sensors should withstand them. The accelerometers should confirm the main natural frequency at ~200 Hz as well other bending modes, and be able to show the breathing mode at ~2.3 kHz.

The proposed system is to be considered “experimental” and of potential applications to future devices, such as the HL-LHC beam dumps or other similar systems.

Figure 161 - Expected accelerations at the points of the accelerometer a) in the time and b) frequency domain for beam intensity of $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

9.3 MONITORING OF THE SLOW RESPONSE

The innovative feature of the new frame supporting system is that it allows the free expansion and slow movement of the TDE block, but at the same time it preserves the nominal position of the TDE with respect to the supporting system. This slow movement, produced as result of the slow thermal expansion/contraction cycle of the TDE, is tracked by a series of LVDTs installed on the upstream window of the TDE.

It is very important to highlight that the supporting system is not constrained or fixed to the shielding in order to avoid high reaction forces produce by the vibration of the TDE. According to the drawings, and assuming the nominal position as reference, the frame support is allowed to move +/-15 mm in the beam direction and +/-2mm in horizontal one. Moreover, although the TDE block should come back to original/nominal position with respect to the supporting system, possible relative movements could appear due to the friction phenomena and manufacturing tolerances. The instrumentation has been designed to accommodate all these possible movements.

Therefore, the LVDTs are installed with the aim of measuring the slow movement of the TDE block and also for monitoring the possible migration of the supporting system.

9.3.1 Linear variable differential transformer (LVDT)

Three LVDT assemblies per dump are used to measure displacements of the TDE in three orthogonal directions: vertical, horizontal and longitudinal (see Figure 162). All of them are installed on the upstream window, so they are accessible for any possible maintenance operation, and fixed to the shielding or ground by an auxiliary supporting structure. The main characteristic of the LVDTs can be summarised as follows:

- Displacement range: +/- 20 mm with an accuracy of +/-0.02mm. Note that displacement range can be above the nominal up to +/-50 mm but in detriment of the accuracy.
- Radiation resistant (tested up to 10MGy)
- Continuous acquisition at 1Hz

Figure 162 - LVDT system on the upstream window: version rod-spring for vertical and horizontal LVDTs and version wire-spring for longitudinal LVDT. Contact plate for LVDTs are made large enough to accommodate possible permanent displacements. Fixation point of the wire rope to the window uses a free to rotate pin. The nomenclature of the LVDTs is D_X_US_i, where D means displacement, X is TDE reference according to the following convention: A – Dump A, corresponding to HCTDE_002-CR000002 - UD68; and B – Dump B corresponding to HCTDE_002-CR000001 - UD62, US refers to the upstream side, and i to the position of each sensor

The design of the LVDTs are based on on the ones used in LHC collimators and other beam intercepting devices at CERN, but it includes some modifications in order to adapt them to the specific and more challenging TDE requirements. The design principle of the LVDT assembly is illustrated in Figure 163.

Figure 163 - TDE LVDT assembly for a) lateral and vertical movement measurements and b) longitudinal movement. The central magnet is guided as it moves inside the outer body by PEEK endcaps fitted to the outer body. The central rod is spring-loaded. Drawing LHCTDE__0094 and LHCTDE__0104.

As shown Figure 163 there are two versions: The vertical and lateral LVDTs (rod-spring version) act on plates bolted to the dump upstream window via a preloaded spring; whilst the longitudinal LVDT (rope-spring) is connected to the dump block via a thin, flexible steel wire rope which is tensioned by a spring fitted at the opposite end of the LVDT assembly. Note that the size of the bolted plated has been dimensioned to accommodate the maximum displacement of the frame support.

It is worth emphasising that, although the LVDTs measure the slow movement of the TDE, they are also exposed to strong vibrations coming from the TDE block during regular dumps. Several simulations have been carried out to assess the behaviour of the LVDTs during the fast movement. They demonstrate that the rod-spring LVDTs version could withstand relatively small dynamic movements (lateral/vertical movements), but they may suffer damages in case of relative large dynamic movement as found in the beam direction.

This is illustrated in Figure 164. The relatively high longitudinal expansion of the dump after the beam impacts displaced out the rod of the LVDT at high speed and it violently impacts the body. Video can be found [here](#).

Figure 164 - Behaviour of the longitudinal LVDT after the beam impact in case of spring-rod version. Sequence of picture of the movement of the rod up to impact with the body

Because of the rope-spring version is based on an indirect contact of the LVDT rod with the measured surface via a wire rope, the flexibility of the wire rope helps to absorb the vibration of the TDE. The working principle of this version is illustrated in Figure 165.

Figure 165 - wire rope version of LVDT. Parameters of the system can be found in Table 39

Several analytical studies were performed on the rope-spring version aiming at optimising the LVDT behaviour and survival life during the fast movement of the TDE and looking for the characteristic of wire-spring system.

Equation of the movement is given by:

$$m \cdot \ddot{y} + c \cdot \dot{y} + k_{spring} \cdot y - k_{wire} \cdot (window(t) - y) = 0$$

Where m is the mass of the system, k is the stiffness, c is the damping and y is the displacement of the rod.

Figure 166 shows the longitudinal movement of the rod and window along the time during the fast movement. The positive direction is assumed to be along the beam direction. As observed, the wire accommodates and absorbs the displacement of the window during the expansion of the TDE, producing a small movement of the rod. Then, when the window returns back (contraction of the TDE), it pulls the wire and moves the rod of the LVDT (along the beam direction). Maximum displacements of the rod is in the range of [30-15] mm depending on preload and damping. Maximum force on the wire is lower than 300 N (see Figure 166b). This configuration shows a better performance respect to spring-rod version for fast large movements. Main characteristic and properties of the system is summarised in Table 39.

Table 39- LVDT behaviour: assumptions

Spring

- Free length 170 mm.
- Maximum travel 124.7 mm.
- Spring rate: 0.0814 N/mm.
- Internal diameter 6.5 mm
- Pre-load = 62.5 mm

Wire

- Diameter = 1 mm diameter (Steel)
- MBL = 100 Kg
- L= 300 mm

Mass= 0.064 (rod, ends, spring, wire)

Damping ratio= 1%

Both configurations have been tested in laboratory, confirming that they work well according to the requirements. Moreover, the study confirms the better performance of the wire-spring configuration for fast movements.

(a)

(b)

Figure 166 - a) movement of the LVDT and window during the fast expansion of the dump and b) forces on the wire rope.

Regarding the expected measurements of the LVDT, the Figure 167 shows an estimation of the slow movement of the TDE produced due to the thermal expansion/contraction cycle during 12 hrs after a beam dump for intensity of $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb and $1.2 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb. The potential displacements of the frame support due to the vibration are unpredictable a priori.

Figure 167 - Expected displacements of the TDE block at the LVDTs points for beam intensity a) $1.2 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb and b) $1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$ ppb.

9.4 ADDITIONAL INSTRUMENTATION

In addition to the previous instrumentation for monitoring fast and slow movement of the TDE, other different instruments have been placed in the cavern to record the status of the TDE in any moment. These instruments are:

9.4.1 Monitoring Audio

Audio sensor Eta250 Ultra SCU Membrane-free Optical Microphone. The characteristics of the audio sensor are the following:

- Immune to beam impact induced EMI.
- Unaffected by large fiber lengths to conditioning electronics.
- Full audible range.
- Optic fiber-based, membrane free microphone (same as used prior to LS2 and shown in Figure 153).

Figure 168 - Eta250 Ultra SCU Membrane-free Optical Microphone (Xarion Laser Acoustic).

9.4.2 Camera

A commercial DSLR camera is placed next to the bunker in the TD tunnel (section 4.8) and shielded in an ad-hoc container with borated polyethylene. The camera is focused on the front face of the upstream window. The Field of View (FOV) is ~ 500 mm (width) \times 1000 mm (height), which is achieved by routing the camera view with mirrors. Currently,

the camera view is restricted to one half of the upstream TDE window because the other half is obstructed by the beam pipe and the UHV window protection. Further analysis is being carried out in order to improve the FOV size with an additional convex mirror. Figure 169 shows the current expected FOV.

Figure 169 - Expected FOV for the camera focused on one half of the upstream TDE window placed in the UD62. UD68 shows similar configuration with a symmetrical disposition (left half visible).

9.4.3 Monitoring N₂ Pressure inside the dump

Finally, the pressure of the N₂ in the dump is a key parameter to be monitored in order to detect the presence of leaks that may lead to graphite oxidation, as well as pressure variation due to the temperature increase after the beam impact and energy diffusion. The pressure sensor is a Piezo-resistive gauge Balzers APR017 0-2000 mbar, with an accuracy of 1 mbar. The signal from the sensor is conditioned before it is sent to the common acquisition system NI 6143 card. Note that this sensor is not installed on the TDE directly, but in the N₂ injection line that feed up the TDE block at the entrance of the cavern (see Figure 170).

Figure 170: Pressure sensor installed in the N₂ injection line.

Two acquisition rates have been defined: fast acquisition during [-2s,+8s] with respect to the beam impact at 100 kHz aiming to capture the fast dynamic phenomenon after the beam pulse (fast acquisition rate should be re-assessed during commissioning according to observations); and a continuous acquisition at 1Hz published on NXCALS. The name of the variables are:

- 'VGMA.629594.R.PR' (UD62)
- 'VGMA.689594.B.PR' (UD68)

As reference, Figure 171 shows the pressure evolution on both TDEs after one beam impact during RUN2 (date 16 August 2018). An increase of pressure is detected on both devices due to the thermal expansion of the Nitrogen followed by a slow pressure reduction. This trend is representative of the thermal evolution of the contact surfaces with the gas: vessel and external surface of the graphite cores. In this particular case, the increase of pressure was around 30 mbar when impacted with $1.2050 \cdot 10^{14}$ proton beam.

Figure 171 - Pressure evolution with time in both TDE UD62 and UD68 after one beam dump on 16-08-2018.

9.5 SUPPORTS FOR INSTRUMENTATION

The Laser Doppler Vibrometer (LDV) is a very sensitive and accurate device. Small induced perturbations or vibrations can disturb the measurements. A dedicated supporting system, separated from the dump and frame, has been designed accordingly. Figure 172 shows the assembly of the supporting system.

Figure 172 - LVD and LVDT supporting system. Drawing LHCTDE__0150

Due to the space-constraints, the support accommodates as well two LVDT sensors, which in principle should not perturb the quality of the LDV signal. Nevertheless, although the characteristic time response (working time) of the LVDT is completely different to the one of the LDV, some vibrations could be transmitted to the support via the LVDT rod movement as shown in Section 9.3.1. Aiming to avoid any possible noise, a harmonic analysis on the support has been carried out in order to ensure correct operation of the LDV.

Figure 173 shows the numerical model and boundary condition. Harmonic analysis is focused on the range [0 – 250 Hz], which covers the dominant natural frequencies of the TDE block.

Figure 173 - Numerical model of the support. LVDT and LDV are represented by equivalent mass. Forces at different freq. are applied to the LVDT, which represents the movement of the rod. Displacement of the rod is assumed to be +/-30 mm.

The response of the structure depending on the frequencies of the vibrations is shown in Figure 174. No significant peaks are found around the dominant longitudinal natural frequency of the dump (197 Hz) and there is a valley in the range [150-250] Hz. Therefore, the risk to get resonance in the structure is low.

Figure 174 - Behaviour of the LVDT and LDV support in the domain of the frequency.

Logically, other designs were also checked previously during the design phase before converging to this last optimised one. As a reference of a non-optimum design, Figure 175 shows some previous results. It can be observed that there is a peak close to the longitudinal natural frequency of the TDE, which is a potential source of vibrations.

Figure 175 - previous support designs: longitudinal movement of the LDV support.

10. CONCLUSIONS

10.1 CONCLUSIONS ON THE DUMP HARDWARE MODIFICATIONS VS LHC RUN3

An ambitious and innovative set of hardware modifications has been carried out on the LHC beam dumps during LS2. The work was initiated in order to address nitrogen leaks from the dumps which had started during the course of LHC Run2.

The program of work initially proposed was relatively conservative with a minimum number of modifications in view of the difficulties of working in the beam dump caverns as a result of residual radiation levels. The main focus was on repairing the leaks by improving the sealing solutions at the downstream end of the dump and at the junctions

between the beam line vacuum window, the connecting line and the dump itself. It was realized however that it would also be necessary to do something to reduce the forces on the beam line junctions in order to minimize the risk of leaks in the future as beam intensity increases.

In parallel with design and test work to improve sealing and also look into potential ways of restraining the dumps, thermo-mechanical dynamic analysis studies on the dump block outer vessel were launched. The initial findings of these dynamic studies indicated that the shower created by the interaction of the dumped beam with the graphite core of the dump caused virtually instantaneous heating and large expansion of the dump vessel. This in turn led to violent forces, accelerations and vibrations. This "fast" reaction was accompanied by "slow" dump movements - expansion induced by the heat release from the graphite, followed by retraction on cooling lasting up to several hours.

At this point, once these new and unexpected results came out of the dynamic analysis, it was realized that restraining the dump would give rise to unmanageable forces so the approach chosen was to separate the dump from the connecting line and to support it in a way that would allow it to expand and contract freely but return to its original position rather than migrate with each dump cycle. Separating the dumps from the connecting lines led to the requirement for new beam windows at the upstream end of the dump blocks and the need for a new way of pressurizing the dumps with nitrogen.

The resulting designs are described and the analysis which steered the design work at all stages is reported in detail in this report. The analysis and design progressed in a highly iterative way - design ideas were analysed and then the results were fed back into the design and so on.

It is the first time that this kind of thermo-mechanical dynamic analysis has been made on the vessel containing the LHC dump core. Many of the findings were unexpected - for example the stresses in the upstream beam window due to the impact of the beam are dwarfed by the stresses in the window due to the vibrations of the dump vessel induced by the shower. Fatigue aspects have needed to be carefully analysed and results have been fed back into the designs.

The final versions of the thermo-mechanical analysis confirmed that the as-built designs are suitable for operation with the beam parameters of Run3.

10.2 CONCLUSIONS ON THE INSTRUMENTATION

Instrumentation of the dumps was an important part of the work program. The instrumentation will monitor temperatures, strains, accelerations and displacements of the dumps during Run 3 and this will allow checking and validation of the assumptions and models used in the analysis. This will be a key input into the design of the dumps for HL-LHC. A lot of effort has been put into the selection of sensors to cope with the radiation levels and violent vibrations they will experience - in addition the supports for the sensors and their cables have also been designed to minimize the risk of damage due to the vibrations they will be exposed to. In order to optimize performance of the instrumentation by minimizing the length of cables connecting the sensors to their electronics, the electronics have been installed inside shielded enclosures at 80m from the dumps in the TD tunnels leading to the dump caverns. Cameras inside shielded

enclosures next to the instrumentation shielding will also provide a view of the front of the dumps via mirrors.

10.3 CONCLUSIONS ON HL-LHC ASPECTS

In addition to addressing the immediate problems associated with ensuring the dumps are fit for operation during LHC Run3, the decision to undertake an aggressive program of innovative hardware modifications was influenced by the potential benefits for HL-LHC:

The analysis methods and findings described in this report will obviously be key inputs into the design of the HL-LHC dumps.

In addition, there is the chance to gain operational experience with the new hardware which will be valuable when designing the HL-LHC dumps, their beam windows and their supports.

Operational experience with the instrumentation sensors, their supports, cabling, electronics and radiation shielding will all also feed into the design work for HL-LHC dumps.

10.4 CONCLUDING COMMENTS ON THE SCOPE OF THIS REPORT

This report describes the design and analysis associated with the hardware modifications carried out on the LHC beam dumps during LS2. It only describes the final designs and final versions of the analysis – there is not room or time to cover the many iterations needed to get to this point. The report also does not cover the many practical tests carried out in support of this work, the sub-contracting, manufacture, handling operations, survey measurements, assembly, scheduling, safety precautions and so on. A separate report will be issued on the lessons learnt and the challenges associated with the underground works, from the dump hardware modifications and tests in the UX65 cavern up to the transport to their respective dump caverns.

The report also does not include the extensive ongoing studies investigating the behaviour of the low-density graphite currently used in the absorbers. These studies will be coupled with the autopsy of at least one of the two radioactive dumps which were in operation until the end of LHC Run2.

11. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Reading between the lines of this report may give a small insight into the enthusiasm, commitment, patience, flexibility and determination that the many people at CERN who helped with this work demonstrated in order to pull all this together in the time available.

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Annex

A.1 Radio-Protection documents

Documentation regarding radiation dose estimations during RUN 3 and dismantling activities:

- RP considerations about the LHC TDE upgrade (RUN3) can be found in [109] or directly in [EDMS 2281124](#)

A.2 Instrumentation documents

- Diagrams showing the nomenclature of the sensors installed during LS2 on the TDE can be found in [110] or directly in [EDMS 2422642](#)

A.3 Simulation documents and links

Additional data and documents related to thermo-mechanical simulations can be found in EDMS folder [94]. Direct links to these documents and files can be accessed via following links:

- Properties for LS-DYNA® Material Data can be found [here](#).
- Material data for ANSYS® can be found [here](#).
- Animations of the simulated high frequency vibrations of the dump:
 - Full TDE system ([here](#))
 - Frame support system ([here](#))
 - Wire rope ([here](#))
- Animations of the simulated high frequency vibrations induced in the windows:
 - Upstream Window ([here](#))
 - Downstream Window ([here](#))
- Animations of the beam induced thermomechanical load in the upstream window:
 - Nominal scenario: Temperature ([here](#)), Von Mises Stress ([here](#))
 - Flashover scenario: Temperature ([here](#)), Von Mises Stress ([here](#))
- Animations of the beam induced thermomechanical load in the downstream window:
 - Nominal scenario: Temperature ([here](#)), Von Mises Stress ([here](#))
 - Flashover scenario: Temperature ([here](#)), Von Mises Stress ([here](#))
 - Retrigger scenario: Temperature ([here](#)), Von Mises Stress ([here](#))
 - 2H4V scenario: Temperature ([here](#)), Von Mises Stress ([here](#))